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1 CHAPTER I 1. INTRODUCTION Dyes and pigments are the most important colourants used to add a colour or to change the colour of something absorbed from the aqueous solution. Dyes can be defined as organic chemical compounds which have property of producing the phenomenon of colour by light absorption. It must be soluble in the application medium, usually water, at some points during the coloration process and usually exhibit some substantivity for the material being dyed and be absorbed from the aqueous solution. These are intensely coloured materials that retained in substances by physical absorption, mechanical retention and by formation of covalent chemical bonds or complexes with salts or metals. Dyes are the colorant

that has substantivity for a substrate, either inherent or induced by reactants (

Anita Pal. 2017). Dyes are used for imparting color

to an infinite variety of materials like textiles, paper, wood, varnishes, leather, ink, fur, foodstuff, cosmetics, medicine, etc.

Dyes are broadly categorized into two types namely; synthetic dyes obtained from chemical substance or derived through chemical process and natural dyes obtained from

natural sources. The term natural dyes

covers all the dyes derived from natural sources such as plants, insects and minerals (

Gupta, 1990).

Dyes

and textile are an important part of our everyday life. In the production of clothes, dyeing is a very important process. Natural dyes are

comprised of dyes

processing. They impart colour when applied to substrate. This phenomenon is known as dyeing.

Main sources of natural dyes are vegetable, animals and minerals. They can be obtained from any part of plants viz. leaves, fruits, seeds, flowers, barks and

roots (

Marjo

Moeye, 1993).

Natural dyes are pleasing to the eye and the mind because natural dyes are pigments derived from nature. Moreover,

uses of natural dyes in textile industry can reduce environmental pollution. Nowadays the use of synthetic dyes in textile industry is increasing rapidly (

<http://www.nopr.niscair.res.in/bisteream>). Productions of synthetic dyes make use of petrochemical source, and some of these dyes contain carcinogenic amines. The

application of such dyes causes serious health hazards and influences negatively the eco-balance of nature.

Research across the world

has shown that synthetic dyes are suspected to release harmful chemicals that are allergic, carcinogenic and detrimental to human health. Use of synthetic dyes

2 involves release of enormous amount of hazardous chemicals in the environment during their production and subsequent use (

Anita Pal, 2017). Natural dyes, obtained from natural sources are renewable and sustainable bioresource products, with minimum environmental impact and are known for their use, not only in colouration of textiles but also as food ingredients and cosmetics since antiquity. They

produce very uncommon, soothing and soft shades as compared to synthetic dyes.

Plant leaves, fruits and other parts are potential sources of natural dyes. Dyes from these sources are non-allergic, non-toxic as no petrochemicals or catalysts are used in the extraction and manufacturing (Anita Pal, 2017).

Above all, they are environment-friendly and can be recycled after use.

Natural dyes find application in many ways in clothes, foods, pharmaceuticals, paintings, paints and cosmetics. Due to above reasons, many advanced countries are spending huge amounts on research in natural dyes because of being safe and eco- friendly (Anita Pal, 2017). Mangroves (*Ceriops decandra* (Griff.) Ding Hou) contains tannin and may be used for tannin industry. It is found high tannin content especially in members of the Rhizophoraceae. Mangrove barks are rich in tannin ranging from 15-36% and can produce reddish brown dyes. The bark yield a colouring matter which produces beautiful, red shades on cotton, wool and silk (Buppha Somboon, 2016).

The aim of this research work is to produce the natural dye powder from

mangrove bark, to study the suitable extraction medium by using water and different volume of ethanol (95%)-water mixture, to study the effect of extraction medium on the concentration of natural dye solution by UV spectrophotometer and to evaluate the fastness properties of dyed cotton fabrics.

3 CHAPTER II 2. LITERATURE REVIEW 2.1 Botanical Aspect of Mangrove Botanical Name - *Ceriops decandra* (Griff.) Ding Hou Family Name - Rhizophoraceae English Name - Mangrove Local Name - Madama Figure (2.1) Mangrove Trees Figure (2.2) Mangrove Barks

4 Mangroves are found in the tropical and subtropical coasts which are bathed by warm ocean currents. Mangroves cannot survive in winter conditions and need warm temperatures above 24°C. Mangrove forests are salt tolerant forest ecosystem and they are formed when the marine water reached to the coastal area. In Myanmar, mangrove forests occur in the coastal area of Rakhine State, Tanintharyi Division and delta area of Ayeyarwady Division. Mangrove forests are one of the most productive and biologically diverse wetlands on earth. It is an ecosystem that is made up of both a community of living things and the non-living environment. The mangrove ecosystem does not have as many species of plants and animals as other ecosystems due to the harsh and constantly changing environment (Zaw Win Myint, 2008). In general, geography, coastal topography and tidal regime determine the presence or absence and extent of the mangroves. Structure, physical properties and chemical composition, salinity, acidity of soil and sediments, the nature of the substratum as well as the climate determine the development, growth and productivity of mangrove ecosystem. Although small in comparison with the world's total forests, they play a very important role in the ecosystem of the region. They prevent soil erosion by acting as a wind and water break. They maintain moisture and breeding grounds for many plants and animals both on land and in the sea. They also provide food, construction materials, fibbers, and medicinal plants to dwellers in and near the coastal zones (Zaw Win Myint, 2008). Mangroves could be identified as three types; the red mangrove, the black mangrove and the white mangrove. The red mangrove can be distinguished by the reddish color to the bark of the trunk roots. This type of mangrove is also called the "Walking Tree". The black mangrove is the largest and tallest of the three types listed above because of their age. They are found upland to the red mangroves, located at higher elevations and are the most cold tolerant. The bark of this tree is dark which gives it the name black mangrove while the white mangroves are located at higher elevations than both the red and black mangroves. This type can also be identified by its leaves. Each type of mangrove is located at different areas along the coastline and plays a distinct role in the respective areas they are located (Diana Maikut, 2004).

5 2.2 Uses of Mangroves The uses of mangroves falls into two categories, firstly the use of the mangrove ecosystem as a whole or its conversion to other uses, and secondly, the use of products from the mangrove ecosystem. The uses of mangroves are many and varied. A fundamental function of all forests has been to supply timber for cooking, heating and constructing dwellings, and mangrove forests are no exception. Traditionally, people have used mangroves for the benefit of the local community, but increasing populations have led to an increasing non-sustainable abuse of the resources. In Malaysia, where mangroves occur in profusion, an important cottage industry is the manufacture of shingles for roof thatching. Basketry, corks and floats are obtained from the pneumatophores. It has been exported from the Philippines to various parts of the world for utilization in the textile industry and extracts of stilt roots exhibited mosquito larvicidal activity. In Sri Lanka, it is used in making masks for many traditional cultural activities. Pulp for paper, matchsticks, household utensils, agricultural implements and toys are some other products produced

from mangroves (<https://www.aims.gov.au/docs/projectnet/mangroves-uses.html>). The importance of bark tannins has declined in many Asian countries, but mangrove tannin is still used in India and Bangladesh for leather curing and in Sri Lanka tannin is used traditionally in curing fishnets. The tannins comprise two groups of phenolic constituents, hydrolysable and condensed, which are important economically as agents for the synthesis of certain medicines. Their potential value as cytotoxic and/or antineoplastic agents and as antimicrobial agents has been demonstrated. Mangrove plants are rich sources of saponins, alkaloids and flavonoids. Plant saponins have been shown to have interesting biological activities such as spermicidal and molluscicidal activity. The extraction of natural chemical compounds, in addition to those already known to the pharmacopoeia of the people, continues to this day and among the latest additions are an array of substances from glues to alkaloids and saponins and many other substances of interest to modern industry and medicine. An alternative source of wealth in the mangroves is the exploitation of the fish, molluscs and crustaceans that abound in

6 the mangrove areas (<https://www.aims.gov.au/docs/projectnet/mangroves-uses.html>). 2.3 Natural Dye

Natural dyes are dyes or colorants derived from plants, invertebrates, or minerals.

The majority of natural dyes are vegetable dyes from plant sources – roots, berries, bark, leaves, and wood and

other organic sources such as

fungi and lichens.

Textile dyeing date back to the Neolithic period. Throughout history, people have dyed their textiles using common, locally available materials.

Scarce dyestuffs that produced brilliant and permanent colors such as the natural invertebrate dyes Tyrian purple and crimson kermes were highly prized luxury items in the ancient and medieval world. Plant-based dyes such as woad, indigo, saffron, and madder were raised commercially and were important trade goods in the economies of Asia and Europe. Across Asia and Africa, patterned fabrics were produced using resist dyeing techniques to control the absorption of color in piece - dyed cloth. Dyes from the New World such as cochineal and logwood were brought to Europe by the Spanish treasure fleets, and the dyestuffs of Europe were carried by colonists to America .

The discovery of man-made synthetic dyes late in the 19th century ended the large-scale market for natural dyes (

Ashis Kumar Samanta, 2016). 2.4 Synthetic Dye The first human-made (synthetic) organic dye, mauveine was discovered serendipitously by William Henry Perkin in 1856.

Many thousands of synthetic dyes have since been prepared. Synthetic dyes quickly replaced the traditional natural dyes. They cost less, they offered a vast range of new colors, and they imparted better properties to the dyed materials (

<https://www.dyes-pigments.com/synthetic-dyes.html>). 2.5

Types of Dyes 2.5.1 Acid Dyes Acid dyes are water-soluble anionic dyes that are applied to fibers such as silk, wool, nylon and modified acrylic fibers using neutral to acid dye baths.

Attachment to the fiber is attributed, at least partly, to salt formation between anionic groups in the

7 dyes and cationic groups in the fiber. Acid dyes are not substantive to cellulosic fibers. Most synthetic food colors fall in this category. 2.5.2 Basic Dyes

Basic dyes are water - soluble cationic dyes that are mainly applied to acrylic fibers, but find some use for wool and silk. Usually acetic acid is added to the

dye bath

to help the uptake of the dye onto the fiber. Basic dyes are also used in the coloration of paper (

<http://en.wikipedia-org/wiki/dye>). 2.5.3

Direct Dyes Direct dyes

is normally carried out in a neutral or slightly alkaline

dye bath,

at or near boiling point, with the addition of either sodium chloride (NaCl) or sodium sulfate (Na_2SO_4). Direct dyes are used on cotton, paper, leather, wool, silk and nylon. They are also used as pH indicators and as biological stains. 2.5.4 Mordant Dyes Mordant dyes require a mordant, which improves the fastness of the dye against water, light and perspiration. The choice of mordant is very important as different mordants can change the final color significantly. Most natural dyes are mordant dyes and there is therefore a large literature base describing dyeing techniques. The most important mordant dyes are the synthetic mordant dyes, or chrome dyes, used for wool;

these comprise some 30% of dyes used for wool, and are especially useful for black and navy shades. The mordant, potassium dichromate, is applied as an after-treatment. It is important to note that many mordants, particularly those in the heavy metal category, can be hazardous to health and extreme care must be taken in using them (<http://en.wikipedia-org/wiki/dye>). 2.5.5

Vat Dyes Vat dyes are essentially insoluble in water and incapable of dyeing fibers directly. However,

reduction in alkaline liquor produces the water soluble alkali metal salt of the dye, which, in this leuco form, has an affinity for the textile

fiber. Subsequent oxidation reforms the original insoluble dye. The color of denim is due to indigo, the original vat dye.

8 2.5.6

Reactive Dyes Reactive dyes utilize a chromophore attached to a substituent that is capable of directly reacting with the fiber substrate. The covalent bonds that attach reactive dye to natural fibers make them among the most permanent of dyes. "Cold" reactive dyes, such as Procion MX, Cibacron F, and Drimarene K, are very easy to use because the dye can be applied at room temperature. Reactive dyes

are by far the best choice for dyeing cotton and other cellulose fibers at home or in the art studio (<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/dye>). 2.5.7

Disperse Dyes Disperse

dyes were originally developed for the dyeing of cellulose acetate,

and are water insoluble. The dyes are finely ground in the presence of a dispersing agent and sold as a paste, or spray-dried and sold as a powder. Their main use is to dye polyester but they can also be used to dye nylon,

cellulose triacetate, and acrylic fibres. In some cases, a dyeing temperature of 130 °C is required, and a pressurized dyebath is used. The very fine particle size gives a large surface area that aids dissolution to allow uptake by the fibre. The dyeing rate can be significantly influenced by the choice of dispersing agent used during the grinding. 2.5.8

Azoic Dyes Azoic dyes is a technique in which an insoluble azo dye is produced directly onto or within the fiber. This is achieved by treating a fiber with both diazoic and coupling components. With suitable adjustment of

dye bath

conditions the two components react to produce the required insoluble azo dye.

This technique of dyeing is unique controlled by the choice of the diazoic and coupling components. This method of dyeing cotton is declining in importance due to the toxic nature of the chemicals used. 2.5.9

Sulfur Dyes Sulfur dyes are two part "developed" dyes used to dye cotton with dark colors. The initial bath imparts a yellow or pale chartreuse color. This is

after treated

with a sulfur compound in place to produce the dark black we are familiar with in socks for instance. Sulfur Black 1 is the largest selling dye by volume (

<http://en.wikipedia-org/wiki/dye>).

9 2.6 Classification of Natural Dyes Natural dyes can be defined as those colorants (dyes and pigments) obtained from animal or vegetable matter with no processing involved. For textile dyeing, the most commonly used are mordant dyes, although some belong to other groups (vat, solvent, pigment, direct and acid). Most of the historically important colorants are members of the anthraquinone, naphthoquinone, indigoid and carotenoid groups. There are no natural dyes of the sulphur, disperse, azoic or ingrain types. Natural dyes can be classified in various ways. Early methods of classification were based simply on the alphabetical arrangement of dyes. Later on, numerous other methods of classification were adopted, which are as follows: • Classification based on chemical structure • Classification based on their origin or the sources from which they are obtained • Classification based on their methods of application • Classification based on their color. In the colour index, natural dyes are arranged and classified according to their chemical composition as well as their major applications. Natural dyes make up a separate section in the colour index, where they are arranged according to hue within their application category (Clark, 2011).

2.6.1 Classification Based on Chemical Structure Natural organic dyes and pigments belong to a wide range of chemical classes, such as indigoid, anthraquinonoids, naphthoquinones, polymethines, ketones, imines, quinones, flavones, flavanols, flavanones and chlorophyll. Some of the important chemical classes are represented in Table (2.1). 2.6.2 Classification According to Source Depending on their origin or the sources from which they are produced, natural dyes can be grouped into three distinct classes: those derived from vegetable sources; those derived from insect or other animal sources and those derived from mineral sources (Clark, 2011). 2.6.2.1 Dyes Derived from Vegetable Sources Vegetable dyes are obtained from various parts of plants and herbs including the stem, wood, roots, bark, leaves, flowers, fruits and skin of plants, which produce

10 distinct pale to dark shades on both natural as well as synthetic fibres. Some important examples of dyes derived from plants or vegetables are logwood, turmeric, pine wood, catechu, madder, etc. 2.6.2.2 Dyes Derived from Insects or Animal Sources

Some of the most important red dyes, based on the anthraquinone structure, are obtained from insects or animals. These dyes are characterized by good light fastness. They combine with metal salts

to form metal-complex dyes, which possess good wash fastness. Examples of this type of dye are Lac, Kermes, Cochineal, Lichen, etc (Clark, 2011). 2.6.2.3 Dyes Derived from Mineral Sources Natural dyes produced from mineral resources include chrome yellow, chrome orange, chrome green, iron buff, Prussian blue, manganese brown, mineral khaki, etc. Mineral colors are not dyes but inorganic compounds, insoluble in water and precipitated onto the fiber by double decomposition. Certain important minerals widely used as natural dyes are Cinebor (Sangraj), Red Lead (Sindur), Laminated Red earth (Gem), Ultramarine (Lajerd), Zinc white (Sajeda), etc (Clark, 2011).

11 Table (2.1) Important Chemical Classes of Natural Dyes

Chemical Class	Natural dye source	Substrate	Colour produced
Indigoids	Indigo (<i>Indigofera tinctoria</i>)	Tyrian purple	
	(<i>Purpurophragma</i> / <i>Murex brandaris</i>)	Cotton, wool and silk	Blue Blue purple/reddish purple
Anthraquinonoids	Madder (<i>Rubia tinctorum</i>)	Cochineal (<i>Coccus cacti</i>)	Wool and silk Wool, silk and cotton (printing)
			Pink, red crimson orange, brown Crimson, scarlet and pink
Alphanaphthaquinones	Heena or lawsone (leaves of <i>Lawsonia inermis</i>)		
	Juglone (shells of <i>Juglans regia</i>)	Wool and silk	Wool and silk Yellow to brown
Flavones	Weld (<i>Reseda luteola</i>)	Cotton, wool and silk	Yellow, orange and olive
Dihydropyrans	Logwood (compeachy wood, <i>Haematoxylum campechianum</i>)	Brazilwood (red wood species, <i>Caesalpinia echinat</i>)	Wool, silk, cotton and leather
			Wool, silk and cotton Black Crimson, black and purple
Anthocyanidins	Carajurin (leaves of <i>Bignonia chica</i>)	Cotton and silk	Orange
Carotenoids	Annatto (<i>Bixa orellana</i>)	Saffron (<i>Crocus sativus</i>)	Wool and silk Wool and silk
			Yellow and orange

(Clark, 2011).

12 2.6.3 Classification According to Method of Application According to this classification, natural dyes can be classified as either direct dyes or mordant dyes. Direct dyes may be further subdivided into: ? Direct dyes for cotton, e.g. turmeric, pomegranate, annatto, safflower, etc. ? Direct dyes for wool and silk, e.g. turmeric, pomegranate, annatto, safflower, etc. ? Acid dyes, e.g. saffron ? Basic dyes, e.g. Berberine. ? Direct dyes for cotton can be applied to all natural textile fibres; acid dyes can generally only be applied to wool and silk; basic dyes can be used for wool and silk as well as tannic acid treated cotton. On the other hand, mordant dyes are equally suitable for both animal and vegetable fibres. Important mordant dyes include madder, logwood and cochineal. There is a further class of dyes known as vat dyes, which are insoluble in water. These include indigo, woad and tyrian purple (Clark, 2011).

2.6.4 Classification Based on Colour Natural dyes are frequently categorized on the basis of the colour that they impart to the fibre substrate.

2.6.4.1 Natural Yellow Dyes Yellow symbolizes growth and happiness and is

perhaps the most abundant hue in nature. The number of plants that yield yellow dyes

is much higher than the number that yield other colours, and the Colour Index lists a total of 28 natural yellow dyes. Yellow is of particular significance in India, where it is still considered an auspicious colour with great religious significance.

2.6.4.2 Natural Red Dyes The Colour Index lists 32 natural red dyes: some are extracted from the roots or bark of plants, while others, such as cochineal, are camouflaged in the bodies dull grey insects. However, the sources of these dyes are limited. Throughout history, natural red dyes have been of significant and in some cases legendary importance. Almost all natural red dyes have a basic quinone structure. They are mainly

13 comprised of anthraquinones (alizarin, purpurin, munjistin, laccaic, etc.) or naphthoquinones (alkannin and shikonin); there is also one benzoquinone dye (carthamin). Some of the prominent natural red dyes, as obtained from plant, animal and mineral sources (Clark, 2011).

2.6.4.3 Natural Blue Dyes The Colour Index lists only

three natural blue dyes, namely natural indigo, sulphated natural indigo and the flowers of the Japanese *Tsuyukusa*, used mainly for paper making.

The most brilliant and the fastest blue shades are obtained from indigo on all fibres. The principal coloring matter is indigotin, whose main sources are Indigo (*Indigofera tinctoria*) and woad (*Isatis tinctoria*). 2.6.4.4 Natural Brown Dyes The majority of natural brown dyes are obtained from quinone-based dyes, naphthoquinones and anthraquinones. Generally, copper and iron salts are used as mordants and they tend to turn the colour to dull and deep shades, particularly browns. This dye is a tannin-based flavonoid, and is derived from *Acacia catechu* and wild *Acacia arabica* (Clark, 2011). 2.7 Chemistry of Natural Dyes In plants the coloured pigments are normally present in the leaves, flowers, heart wood, bark and roots. These pigments can be extracted from the plant parts using suitable solvents depending on the chemical nature of the coloured constituents. The major divisions of natural chromogens that are or could be used in food materials and pharmaceuticals are listed below, along with examples of pigments and sources. 2.7.1 Anthracenes The two major groups of the anthracenes contain several well-known dyes. Anthraquinones (yellow, pink and red pigments) include *Morinda citrifolia* (Morindone), *Alkanna tinctoria*, *Dactylopius coccus* (cochineal) (carminic acid), etc. (Alizarin) (Ruberethric acid). Naphthoquinones (brown, pink or purple pigments) include *Juglans nigra*, *Juglans regia* (Juglone), *Lawsonia innermis* (Lawsone) (Clark, 2011).

14 2.7.2 Carotenoids These are a family of yellow and orange pigments found in most photosynthesizing organisms. Over 200 naturally occurring carotenoids have been identified but only a few are commercially available, including β -carotene, β -apo-8'-carotenal and canthaxanthin. The two major groups in the family are the carotenes (orange or red-orange) and the xanthophylls (yellow). β -carotene is the major carotenoid in algae and higher plants. Examples of carotenoids are *Christisonia bicolor* (Azafrin), *Careca papaya* fruits (anthera xanthin), *Bixa orellana* (Bixin), *Lillium hamsonii* (β -carotene). 2.7.3 Carotenes Carotene was first isolated as red crystals from carrots in 1831. It is closely related to vitamin A and generally occurs as a mixture of α -, - and γ -carotene in the ratio 15:85:0.1. Lycopene is the main colourant of tomatoes (Clark, 2011). 2.7.4 Xanthophylls These are oxygenated carotenes. Examples are *Tagetes patula*, *Capsicum annum* (red pigment) (Capsanthin), lutein (nettles, French marigolds), *cis*-bixin (annatto) and crocin (saffron). Annatto is used mainly for colouring dairy products and is derived from *B. orellana*. Saffron (*C. sativus*), whose main dye constituent is crocin, is a major colouring agent in use since Ancient Greece and Rome. 2.7.5 Betacyanins These red dyes, along with the related betaxanthins (yellows) were originally thought to be flavonoids; however, they differ in that they contain nitrogen and do not undergo the same reversible colour change as anthocyanins when exposed to different pH levels. They are glycosylated, like anthocyanins. They are reported to be present only in a few families of the *Chenopodiaceae*, such as the beet, portulacca and goosefoot families. Betanin is an extract from the red beet (*Beta vulgaris*), containing red and yellow pigments, which is used mainly as a food colouring. Betanin is the major component (95%) of the red pigments in the extract (Clark, 2011).

15 2.7.6 Flavins Flavins are very common in living organisms, riboflavin and two of its derivatives being the three most common. Their precise physiological role in the plant is unknown but it is thought that they may be involved as receptors of blue light and UV-A (the receptors for UV-B are unknown). Riboflavin (an alloxan adduct) is a yellow dye closely related

to vitamin B2, used for colouring food. This colourant can be synthesized. 2.7.7 Indigoid Dyes Examples of natural dyes containing indigoid are *Indigofera tinctoria*, *Wrightia tinctoria* and *Murex brandaris* (shellfish). The two most important dyes in this group are Tyrian purple, derived from the molluscs *Murex trunculus*, *M. brandaris* and *Purpura lapillus*, and Indigo. The main dye chemical in tyrian purple is 6,6'-dibromoindigo; the natural source is no longer used because of the large number of shellfish needed to produce even a small amount of the dye and because of the relative rarity of the shellfish. Indigo is known to be present in a small number of plants: indigo (*Indigofera* spp.), woad (*Isatis tinctoria* and other species), a Japanese knotweed (*Polygonum tinctoriu*). These plants contain the glucoside indican or isatan B, which is soluble in water and hydrolyzed to indoxyl in the dyeing process. Oxidation, usually by exposure to air, turns the indoxyl to indigotin (or indigo blue), which is insoluble in water, ether and alcohol. Other dyes such as indirubin and kaempferol may also be present in these plants. Most industry analysts believe that there will always be a comparatively high demand for indigo dyes, and they are the most important dyes in terms of volume (Clark, 2011). 2.7.8 Chlorophyll Pigments Chlorophyll is the major pigment used by plants for capturing light energy. A chlorophyll molecule consists of a porphyrin head (four pyrrole rings containing nitrogen arranged in a ring around a magnesium ion) and a long hydrocarbon tail. The hydrocarbon tail is lipid-soluble. There are four types of chlorophyll: chlorophyll a, found in all higher plants, algae and cyanobacteria; chlorophyll b, found in higher plants and green algae; chlorophyll c, found in diatoms, dinoflagellates and brown algae; and chlorophyll d, found only in red algae. The dye is extracted from natural sources (usually stinging nettle, spinach, alfalfa or corn) and used extensively in

16 coloring inks, resins, soaps and waxes, edible fats, cosmetics, liniments, lotions, perfume, mouthwashes and leather. The dyestuff is known as C.I. Natural Green 3, C.I. Number 75810. It is very difficult to prepare pure chlorophyll chemically and the commercial product contains a mixture of chlorophylls a and b (in the ratio of 3:1) and several carotenoids. The commercial process for extracting chlorophyll from plant material involves many steps using solvents such as petroleum ether and acetone (Clark, 2011). 2.8 Chemical Compounds in Plants 2.8.1 Phenolic Compound The term phenolic compound embraces a wide range of plant substances which possess in common an aromatic ring bearing one or more hydroxyl substituents. Phenolic substances tend to be water-soluble, since they most frequently occur combined with sugar as glycosides and they are usually located in the cell vacuole. Among the natural phenolic compounds, of which over a thousand structures are known, the flavonoids form the largest group but simple monocyclic phenols, phenylpropanoids and phenolic quinones all exist in considerable numbers (Harbone, 1984). Several important groups of polymeric materials in plants the lignins, melanins and tannins are polyphenolic and occasional phenolic units are encountered in proteins, alkaloids and among the terpenoids. Phenolic compounds are all aromatic, so that they all show intense absorption in the UV region of the spectrum. In addition, phenolic compounds characteristically exhibit bathochromic shifts in their spectra in the presence of alkali. Spectral methods are, therefore, especially important for the identification and quantitative analysis of phenols (Harbone, 1984). Phenolic compounds represent the largest category of phytochemicals and are most widely distributed in the plant kingdom. Phenolics are hydroxyl group (-OH) containing class of chemical compounds where the (-OH) group is bonded directly to an aromatic

hydrocarbon group. Phenol (C_6H_5OH) is considered the simplest class of this group of natural compounds (Deepak Koche, 2016). 2.8.2 Flavonoid The flavonoids are all structurally derived from the parent substance flavone. Flavonoids are mainly water soluble compounds. Flavonoids contain conjugated

17 aromatic systems and thus show intense absorption bands in the UV and visible regions of the spectrum (Harbone, 1984). Flavonoids are the largest group of plant phenols and also the most studied one. They are polyphenolic compounds that are ubiquitous in nature and occur as glycosides, glucosides and methylated derivatives. More than 4,000 flavonoids have been recognized, many of which occur in vegetables, fruits and beverages like tea, coffee and fruit drinks (Pridham, 1960). 2.8.3 Tannin Tannins occur widely in vascular plants, their occurrence in the angiosperms being particularly associated with woody tissues. By definition, they have the ability to react with protein, forming stable water insoluble co-polymers. Industrially, tannins are substances of plant origin which because of their ability to cross-link with protein are capable of transforming raw animal skins into leather (Harbone, 1984). Tannins are the most important ingredients in the dyeing with natural dyes producing yellow, brown, grey and black colours. They also modify the affinity of fibres towards different dyes. A back tanning process improves the wash fastness of some dyes. However, the treatment with tannins makes dyeings dull. Tannins are naturally occurring compounds of high molecular weight (about 500–3000) containing phenolic hydroxyl groups (Gulrajani, 2001). In the dyeing of textiles, tannins form the basis of 'so called' natural mordant. As stated above, tannins are phenolic compounds and those tannins, which have *o*-dihydroxy (catechol) groups can form metal chelates, giving different colour with different metals. An after-treatment with metal salts not only alters the light sorption characteristics of tannins but also makes them insoluble in water. Hence, they are fixed on the textile substrate, giving good washing fastness (Gulrajani, 2001). 2.8.4 Alkaloids Alkaloids are natural products that contain heterocyclic nitrogen atoms and are always basic in character. The name of alkaloids derives from the 'alkaline' nature and it was used to describe any nitrogen-containing base (Muller-Harvey, 1999). Almost all the alkaloids have a bitter taste. The alkaloid quinine, for example, is one of the bitter tasting substances known and is significantly bitter (1×10^{-5}) at a molar concentration. Alkaloids are so numerous and involve such a variety of

18 molecular structure that their rational classification is difficult. However, the best approach is to group them into families, depending on the type of heterocyclic ring system present in the molecule (Krishnan et al., 1983). 2.8.5 Polyphenol Polyphenols constitute one of the most numerous and widely distributed groups of natural products in the plant kingdom. More than 8000 phenolic structures are currently known, and among them over 4000 flavonoids have been identified. Although polyphenols are chemically characterized as compounds with phenolic structural features, this group of natural products is highly diverse and contains several sub-groups of phenolic compounds. Fruits, vegetables, whole grains and other types of foods and beverages such as tea, chocolate and wine are rich sources of polyphenols. The diversity and wide distribution of polyphenols in plants have led to different ways of categorizing these naturally occurring compounds. Polyphenols have been classified by their source of origin, biological function, and chemical structure. Also, the majority of polyphenols in plants exist as glycosides with different sugar units and acylated sugars at

different positions of the polyphenol skeletons (<http://www.mdpi.com/journal/nutrients>).

2.8.6 Saponins Saponins have a high molecular weight and a high polarity and their isolation in a state of purity presents some difficulties. Such plants contain a high percentage of glycosides known as saponins which are characterized by their property of producing a frothing aqueous solution. As glycosides they are hydrolysed by acids to give an aglycone (sapogenin) and various sugars and related uronic acids. According to the structure of the aglycone or sapogenin, two kinds of saponin are recognized the steroidal and the pentacyclic triterpenoid types (Treace and Evans, 2009).

2.9 Mordants Natural dyes are either substantive, meaning that they do not require a mordant, or adjective, meaning that a mordant is required. Adjective dyes only dye materials which have been mordanted with a metallic salt or with the addition of a metallic salt to the dyebath itself. Examples of such dyes are logwood, madder, cochineal and fustic, among others. In their pure state, adjective dyes are generally

19 only slightly coloured and produce poor results when used alone (Gupta, 1990). Mordants are chemicals in the form of metallic salts which are generally used to create an affinity between the fibre and the pigment. The main objective of the mordant when used with adjective dyes is to open up the pores so that the colourant can penetrate the fibres, thereby helping in the fixation of the dyestuffs on the substrate. However, mordants can also be used with dyes which may be applied directly. In this case their function is to form an insoluble compound with the dyestuff within the fibre itself, thereby improving the fastness properties of the dyed material (Gupta, 1990).

2.9.1 Types of Mordants There are three types of mordant, namely (i) Metallic salts or metallic mordants (ii) Tannins and tannic acid (iii) Oils or oil mordants.

2.9.1.1 Metallic Mordants Naturally occurring metal salts were once used as mordants in order to ensure reasonable fastness of color to sunlight and washing. Today, metal salts of aluminium, chromium, iron, copper and tin are also used. Some of the important metallic mordants are alum, potassium dichromate, ferrous sulphate, copper sulphate, stannous chloride and stannic chloride. Most natural dyes are able to form metal complexes and thereby produce different shades (hues). Therefore virtually all types of metal salts can in fact be used for this purpose. However, some restrictions on the use of metal salts were drawn up in the EC Control of Substances Hazardous to Health Act, 1989. The maximum permissible amounts of different metals in the final product are as follows (Patel, 2016).

2.9.1.2 Tannins and Tannic Acid Tannins are important in processes that use natural dyes producing yellow, brown, grey and black colours. They also improve the affinity of fibres to different dyes. Tannins are mainly used in the preservation of leather, glues, stains and mordants. Vegetable tannins are bitter and astringent substances that occur as

20 excretions in the bark, leaves, fruits, galls, etc. of plants. These excretions may be used directly or in concentrated form. Tannins are naturally occurring phenolic compounds of high molecular weight (ranging from 500 to 3000). The phenolic hydroxyl group allows them to form effective cross-links between proteins and other macro-molecules. Tannins which contain o-dihydroxy (Catechol) group can form chelates, which give different colours with different metals (Patel, 2016).

2.9.1.3

Oil Mordants Oil mordants are

mainly used in dyeing processes using madder, producing Turkey

red colour. The main object of the oil mordant is to form a complex with alum,

which is

used as the principal mordant. Alum is soluble in water and does not have affinity for cotton, so is easily washed out from the treated

fabrics. The naturally occurring oils contain fatty acids such as palmitic, stearic, oleic

and ricinoleic acid, and their glycerides. The $-COOH$ group of fatty acids react with metal salts and are converted into $-COOM$ (M denotes the metal; for example, in the case of alum salts, aluminium). It has also been found that when concentrated sulphonic acid is treated with oils, sulphonated oils are produced,

which have better metal binding capacity than natural oils, due to the introduction of the sulphuric acid group –

SO_3H . This can react with metal salts to produce $-SO_3M$. The bound metal can then form a complex with a mordant dye such as madder, producing a Turkey red colour with superior fastness and hue (Patel, 2016). 2.10 Application of Mordants to Textiles Metallic mordants are soluble in water and are only loosely held by cotton fibres. These mordants must therefore be precipitated onto the fabric by one of two methods: conversion of the mordants into insoluble form and treatment of the fibres with oil or tannic acid, followed by impregnation of the treated fabric with a mordant solution. In the latter method, the metallic mordants are fixed to the cotton by oil or tannic acid. Alum is a widely used mordant for cotton; the addition of an alkali to an alum solution produces aluminium sulphate, which is also used as a mordant, and is extensively used for dyeing of Turkey red colour on cotton. Copper salts are used in cotton dyeing as oxidizing agents for the production of cutch browns and logwood blacks. Copper sulphate is frequently employed in the dyeing of black shades on

21 cotton and for this purpose it is generally fixed with the help of tannic acid. Tin mordants produce exceptionally brilliant colours. Wool is more receptive to natural dyes and mordants than cotton. It can absorb both acids and bases effectively due to its amphoteric nature.

When treated with a metallic salt, wool hydrolyses the salt into an acidic and a basic component. The basic component is absorbed at the $-COOH$ groups while the acidic component is removed in the course of washing. Aluminium sulphate is quite effective as a mordant for wool and is sometimes used without the addition of other substances. Due to low cost and ease of application, the mordanting of wool with sodium or potassium dichromate is widely adopted as a technique. This provides full bright shades with fairly good fastness properties. The brightness of the shade can be further improved by addition of an organic acid such as formic, oxalic or tartaric acid. Ferrous sulphate is not very frequently used as a mordant for wool. Copper sulphate is used in conjunction with aluminium sulphate and ferrous sulphate in the dyeing of logwood blue and logwood black. Among the tin salts, stannous chloride is used as a mordant for wool. Silk possesses similar amphoteric properties to wool and can absorb both acids and bases. Alum is not a preferred mordant for

silk since it diminishes its lustre and pliability. Iron salts are also used both for mordanting and weighing of silk, with excellent black colours produced on iron mordanted silk. Finally, stannous chloride is regarded as one of the most important mordants for silk and can also be used as a weighing agent (Patel, 2016).

2.11 Mordants Used in Natural Dyeing

2.11.1 Alum

Potassium aluminum sulfate $KAl(SO_4)_2$ is the mordant most frequently used by dyers for protein (animal) and cellulose (plant) fibres and fabrics. It is commonly called alum. Alum is a white powder that is safe for hands and easy to use. Alum produces bright shades and gives relatively good light fastness. It is used in excess, alum will make wool feel sticky. If an aluminum pan is used it will contribute to the brightness of the color, but will not guarantee the color fastness. It is inexpensive and safe to use. This form of alum is refined from bauxite, the raw state of aluminum ore, and is free from the impurities (such as iron) some other alums may contain (<https://maiwahandprints.blogspot.com/2013/01/natural-dyes-mordants-part-1.html>).

2.11.2 Copper Sulphate

Use copper sulphate $CuSO_4$, a beautiful blue color when dissolved in water. Copper darkness colors and gives a greenish cast. It provides good color-fastness and is not as hard on fibers as iron. A solid copper pot (if affordable) will make an excellent copper mordant (Kumar, 2015).

2.12 Simple Methods of Dye Extraction

Mostly natural dyes are obtained from various parts of plants like stems, flowers, roots etc. They are also extracted from minerals and dried bodies of insects. Some plants may have more than one color depending on which plant which is used for extraction. The extraction method of vegetable natural dyes basically depends on the method

in which the dye is extracted. There are mainly four methods used in

the extraction of natural dyes.

1. Aqueous method: The dyestuff is boiled at the temperature of $100^\circ C$ in soft water and the dye solution obtained after boiling is filtered and the optical density is recorded.
2. Alkaline method: Initially 1 % alkaline solution is prepared by adding sodium carbonate or sodium hydroxide in water. The material is entered in it and boiled at $100^\circ C$. The dye solution is filtered and optical density is recorded.
3. Acidic method: Prepare 1% of an acidic solution by adding HCL in soft water. Enter the dye material and boil it at $100^\circ C$. Filter the dye solution and record the optical density.
4. Alcoholic method: By adding an equal amount of alcohol and water the alcoholic solution is prepared. The dye material is entered and boiling is carried at $100^\circ C$ and the dye solution is filtered (<http://www.textilemates.com/natural-dye-importance>).

2.13 Extraction

By extraction is meant the process of removing from a mixture, usually an aqueous solution, one or more substances by shaking with a liquid in which the substances to be removed are soluble (James F. Norris, 1924).

2.13.1 Extracting Using Aqueous Solution

This type of extraction also known as the traditional/conventional method has been used to extract natural dyes from diverse sources. The main medium of extraction is water with or without addition of salt/acid/alcohol or alkaline. For optimal extraction conditions, the finely cut material or plant part is dissolved in measured quantity of water and extraction carried out under varying conditions such as extraction temperature, time, pH, material to liquid ratio, concentration of salt and mordant.

In each case, the optical density or absorbance value of the aqueous extract can be evaluated using UV-Vis absorbance spectrophotometer, FT-IR and other chromatography measures (Agulei Karen Desta. 2016). The aqueous extraction under normal conditions is boiling either the dried or fresh samples from low temperatures to the boiling point of water, cooling the filtrate, filtering and storing it for further analysis. However, to optimize the extraction method of colour components in aqueous media, the sample/material is dried, finely cut, ground to powdered form, and finally extracted in water under a standard process. The extraction process of dye liquor is then

carried out under varying condition such as extraction time, extraction temperature, pH of extraction liquor, concentration of colour/source material and material to liquor ratio (

MLR). In each case, the optical density or absorbance value at a particular (maximum) absorbance wavelength for the aqueous extract of the natural dye material can be estimated using UV-Vis absorbance spectrophotometer. The continued usage of this technique has led to the optimization of extraction conditions of some natural dyes (Agulei Karen Desta. 2016).

2.13.2 Solvent Extraction Flavonoids and anthocyanins are soluble in polar solvents with the glucosides and aglycones more soluble in water and alcohols respectively. These phenolics are commonly extracted from plant materials with water/alcohol or methanol/ethanol mixtures acidified with mineral acids to prevent the degradation of the non-acylated anthocyanin pigments. This method has been applied successfully in the extraction of a variety of organic compounds ranging from herbs to other plant material, as well as natural colourant from natural source dye materials. Literature relating to the extraction of natural dyes using solvent extraction technique includes 50% ethanol and methanol for the extraction of natural dye (Harborne, 1984).

24 However due to the rigorous environmental regulations, Supercritical Fluid extraction (SCFE) technique has gained wide acceptance in recent years as an alternative to conventional solvent extraction for separation of organic compound in many analytical and industrial processes. This method has also been applied successfully in the extraction of organic compounds from herbs and other plant material as well as natural colourant from natural products. In another experimental carried out research to assess the dyeing and colouring potentials of ethanol extracts from the leaves. The leaves are collected, chopped, dried and ground to fine powder to allow most intimate contact with solvent (Agulei Karen Desta. 2016). Measured quantities of pulverized samples are then fed into the soxhlet extractor and mixed with absolute ethanol as the solvent in a ratio of 1:50 (powdered plant sample to ethanol solvent). The mixture of solvent-sample is refluxed for 3 hrs. The extract phases generated through several operations of the extraction process are distilled to recover parts of the solvent before evaporating to dryness to obtain dried solid dye samples. The crude extracts are recrystallized using carbon tetrachloride as solvent and finally air dried to obtain purified dye samples. Apart from the mentioned techniques above, other methods of extraction of natural dyes include ultrasound-assisted extraction, supercritical fluid extraction, microwave-assisted extraction and enzymatic extraction. Although the methods of extraction of natural dyes are vast, aqueous method and solvent (using ethanol and methanol) extraction method are employed because of lack of equipment. These

methods have also proven that they yield good fastness properties (Agulei Karen Desta. 2016). 2.14 Simple Distillation In a simple distillation, the distilling flask should be only one-third to one-half full of the liquid being distilled. With a flask that is too full, liquid can easily bump over into the condenser. If the flask is nearly empty, a substantial fraction of the material will be needed just to fill the flask and distilling head with vapor. When the desired liquid is dissolved in a large quantity of a solvent with a lower boiling point, the distillation should be interrupted after almost all of the solvent has been distilled and the higher-boiling liquids should be poured into a smaller distilling flask before continuing the distillation (Jerry R. Mohrig, 2010).

25 2.15 UV-Vis Spectrophotometry The hue and absorbance of the dye is determined using UV-Vis spectral scan of aqueous or non-aqueous extract/solution of the purified natural dye whose UV- zone and visible zone range from 190 to 700 nm or higher. The presence of dye along this range is indicated by peaks and troughs in different wave length. Peaks and troughs in visible zone indicate the main colour and absorption, while the UV-Zone with or without peaks, shows the property of the dye under UV-light which may be correlated with its fastness behavior. Various UV-Visible spectroscopic studies have been conducted by different scientists such as a number of UV-Vis spectral scan on a number of natural dyes namely madder, cochineal, neem, beet sugar and indigo using different solvents for extraction (Agulei Karen Desta. 2016). 2.16 Infrared (IR) Spectroscopy IR spectra may be measured on plant substances in an automatic recording IR spectrophotometer either in solution (in chloroform or carbon tetrachloride 0-5%), as a mull with nujol oil or in the solid state, mixed with potassium bromide. In the latter case, a thin disc is prepared under unhydrous conditions from a powder containing about 1mg of material and 10 to 100mg KBr, using a mould and press. The range of measurement is from 4000 to 667 cm^{-1} (or 2.5 to 15 μm) and the spectrum takes about three minutes to be recorded. The region in the IR spectrum above 1200 cm^{-1} shows spectral bands or peaks due to the vibrations of individual bonds or functional groups in the molecule under examination. The region

below 1200 cm^{-1} shows bands due to the vibrations of the whole molecule and,

because of its complexity, is known as the 'fingerprint' region. Intensities of the various bands are recorded subjectively on a simple scale as being either strong (S), medium (M) or weak (W). The fact that many functional groups can be identified by their characteristic vibration frequencies makes the IR spectrum the simplest and often the most reliable method of assigning a compound to its class. In spite of this, IR spectroscopy is most frequently used in phytochemical studies as a 'fingerprinting' device, for comparing a natural with a synthetic sample. The complexity of the IR spectrum lends itself particularly well to this purpose and such comparisons are very important in the complete identification of many types of plant constituent (Harbone, 1984).

26 2.17 Mercerization Mercerization refers to the treatment of cotton yarns or fabrics with caustic soda solution. Considerable quantities of cotton yarns and fabrics are mercerized to improve lustre and/or dye uptake and more recently without tension to produce stretch materials. Cotton fabrics are mercerized in grey or bleached condition or after boiling off in

alkali. Grey mercerization is frequently practised to save on additional drying cost. The objective of mercerizing is to swell the cotton fibre, increasing its lustre, tensile strength, dimensional stability and dyeability. Traditionally, a cold solution of 25-26% by mass of sodium hydroxide is used, although better penetration and more even treatment is obtained with the more recent hot mercerizing technique. The time of impregnation is rarely sufficient for maximum swelling, so that even with the mercerization of bleached cotton, the addition of wetting agent is advantageous. Until recently, products based on cresylic acid (a mixture of o-, m- and p-cresols) were popular. Such products are toxic and non- biodegradable in nature (Graif, 1996). 2.18

Methods of Mordanting Used in Dyeing with Natural Dyes 2.18.1 Pre-mordanting Pre-mordanting

is a technique which involves primarily mordanting the fabric before dyeing i.e. the mordant is applied to the fabric prior to dyeing. It's the most common method of mordanting practiced on cotton, cellulosic and some animal fibers such as cochineal because these often in unmordanted form don't have affinity for many natural dyes. The advantage of this method is that the standing baths

can be reused many times after replenishing with the mordants. This makes the process economical as well as reducing the pollution load hence sufficient for large-scale application. The

procedures for mordanting are; (i) Dissolve the mordant and added to a dye bath containing ample amount of water. (ii) Add the substrate and bring the whole mixture to boil for a period of about $\frac{3}{4}$ of an hour. (iii) Cool the solution. (iv) Gently remove the substrate to ensure even take-up of the mordant. (v) Rinse the substrate to remove unfixed dyes, dry under room temperature and analyze. The fabric can afterwards be dyed (Saxena et al., 2014).

27 2.18.2 Post Mordanting In this method, the fabric after dyeing is treated with the

mordant in a separate bath. The final colour is developed during the last phase. Iron salts are very often applied in this manner for producing grey and black

colours. The procedures are as follows; (i) Dissolve mordant in ample amount of water. (ii) During simmering (after dyeing), add solution to dye bath in the final five to ten minutes. (iii) Cool solution, remove substrate. (iv) Rinse with cold water to remove unfixed dyes, dry and analysis (Saxena et al., 2014). 2.18.3 Simultaneous Mordanting As the name states, both the dyeing and mordanting process is carried out in the same dye bath and at the same time. For cotton and other cellulose, the

mordant is usually added to the dye bath at the start of dyeing so that both

mordanting and dyeing processes take place concurrently. The procedures for this method are; (i) First dissolve mordant in a separate bath. (ii) Transfer mordant solution to the dye bath and add the wetted fabric. (iii) Bring whole mixture to boil while stirring at intervals

using a stirring rod. (iv) Simmering until maximum dye uptake. (v) Cool solution, remove fabric, rinse with mild detergent, dry and analyze (Saxena et al., 2014). 2.19 Testing the Color Fastness of Dyed Materials The outstandingly important property of a dyed material is the fastness of the shade. The primary object of all fastness tests made on dyed materials is to determine whether they will give satisfaction in subsequent processing or ultimate use, so minimizing the possibility of complaints due to lack of fastness. Fastness tests may be divided into those of consumer significance, such as fastness to cross-dyeing, rubbing perspiration and salt-water staining, and those concerning only to the producer, such fastness to cross-dyeing or unshrinkable treatments. Assessment of fastness is done by the use of Grey Scales which is possible to compare loss of colour or staining of any hue irrespective of depth (Lyle, 1977).

28 2.19.1 Grey Scale for Colour Change This

scale consists of nine pairs of standard grey chips, each pair representing a difference in colour or contrast (shade and strength) corresponding to a numerical fastness rating.

The results of colour fastness tests are rated by comparing the difference in colour of tested specimen and original fabric with the differences represented by the scale (

Lyle, 1977). Table (2.2) Signification of Colour Fastness to Washing and Rubbing Fatness Rating Properties Degree of Alteration in Shade and Strength 5 Excellent Negligible or no change 4 Good Slightly changed 3 Fair Noticeable changed 2 Poor Considerably changed 1 Very Poor Much changed (Lyle, 1977). 2.19.2 Grey Scale for Staining This scale is used to evaluate undyed fabrics. The scale consists of one pair of white and nine pairs of grey and white colour chips each representing a visual difference in colour or contrast (shade and strength) corresponding to a numerical rating for staining. The staining of undyed cloth in

colour fastness tests is rated by comparing the difference in colour of the stained and unstained cloth with the differences represented by the scale.

A piece of an unstained fabric and the test specimen is placed in the same plane (oriented in the same direction) and the Grey Scale for staining is placed beside them under standard conditions of lighting. The visual difference between the original

29 sample and test specimen is compared and the difference is noted as represented by the Grey Scale. The rating of the test specimen is the number on the Grey Scale that corresponds to the contrast between the original and test specimens (Lyle, 1977). 2.19.3 Washing Fastness Consumers launder their fabric at some time in the lifespan of the textile. Change of colour or staining of another garment during laundering is generally immediately evident to the consumer and has a high impact on consumer satisfaction. Like light fastness testing there are a huge number of different iterations of the wash fastness test. The wide variety of test methods have mostly arisen due to the variety of washing methods available, cultural practices, the material being washed, and the end use of the product. The development of detergents and bleaches has influenced the development of new wash fastness test methods. It is important when selecting a wash fastness test method to choose one that best

simulates the washing environment of the fabric's end use. If no end use has yet been selected then it is important to clearly label the level of wash fastness testing that has been conducted on the fabric. The most common washing methods in use today are dry cleaning, hand washing, gentle machine washing, machine washing, permanent press and industrial laundering. Each of these methods has one or more wash fastness tests to determine fabric colour suitability (Hurren, 2008).

2.19.4 Rubbing Fastness Rub fastness is of significant importance to prints, as the colour is provided by a pigment that is fixed to the exterior of the fibre. The pigment on the surface of the fabric is the first component to come under attack when a fabric is rubbed or abraded. Crocking is a simple method for determining fastness to rubbing. The standard 10 cycles employed in the crocking test may not be enough to break down a faulty pigment binder system, so some rub fastness test methods involve an increased number of rubbing cycles. There are test methods and testing equipment developed that have an increased abrasive effect on the fabric surface. These include oscillating drum, wire mesh and emery abrasion testers. Each of these testers abrades the surface more than the crock meter and they are used for textiles that require high resistance to abrasion such as military fabrics.

30 After rub fastness testing the rubbed surface is often appraised for colour change or frosting. Frosting is common in prints and is the pigment rubbing away from the surface of the fabric exposing the natural fibre colour below. This can also be called fibrillation, as single fibres poke through the surface of the print. Frosting is easily identified in a loss of depth of shade of the print (Hurren, 2008).

31 CHAPTER III 3. MATERIALS AND METHODS 3.1 Sources of Raw Materials In this research work, mangrove barks were collected from Bogale Township in Ayeyarwady Region. 95% ethanol, alum, copper (II) sulphate, sulphuric acid, hydrochloric acid, magnesium ribbon, ferric chloride, potassium ferric cyanide, vinegar, sodium hydroxide were purchased from Academy Chemical Group, No. 101, 28 th St, Pabedan Township, Yangon Region. Glasswares were obtained from Department of Industrial Chemistry Laboratory, Dagon University.

3.2 Preparation of Mangrove Bark Powder Before extraction of the natural dyestuff, the pieces of mangrove stem were cleaned with water by brushing to remove the adhering dirt and soil. Then, the pieces of mangrove stem were cut with knife to debark and they were dried at room temperature and then cut into small pieces. The pieces were ground in a grinder and powered samples were screened by passing through Tyler screen of (-100) mesh size and stored in plastic bags for further works.

3.3 Phytochemical Tests on the Bark of Mangrove Powder Before the extraction of natural dyestuff, phytochemical investigation was carried out to study the main compounds which are present or absent in the mangrove bark. The experiment was conducted according to the procedures mentioned in "A Guide to Modern Techniques of Plant Analysis" (Harbone, 1984). The detailed methods for preparation of reagent solution are shown in Appendix. The results of phytochemical investigation of mangrove bark powder are shown in Table (4.1).

3.3.1 Test for Phenolic Compounds Mangrove bark powder 0.2 g was mixed with distilled water and added a few drops of 1% FeCl₃. If violet color appeared, phenolic compounds were present.

3.3.2 Test for Tannins Mangrove bark powder 0.2 g and distilled water was added into a test tube. Then, the mixture was heated for 5 minutes and filtered. The filtrate was treated with 2

32 drops of 1% FeCl₃ solution. If deep blue precipitate appeared in the test tube, it can be noted that tannins were present in it. 3.3.3 Test for Flavonoids Mangrove bark powder 0.2 g was treated with 5 ml of 95% ethanol solution. The solution was warmed and metal magnesium was added. To this solution, 5-6 drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid was added. A pink color indicates the presence of flavonoids. 3.3.4 Test for Saponins Distilled water 5 ml was added to bark powder 0.2 g and the test tube was vigorously shaken for a few minutes. If frothing takes place in the test tube, saponins were present in it. 3.3.5 Test for Alkaloids Mangrove bark powder 0.2 g was boiled with 5 ml of 1% HCl for 5 min, then allowed to cool and filtered. The filtrate was tested with Dragendorff's reagent, an orange precipitate was formed. 3.3.6 Test for Polyphenols Mangrove bark powder 0.2 g was mixed with 5 ml of 95% ethanol and filtered. The filtrate was treated with 5 drops of the mixture of 1% FeCl₃ and 1% K₃Fe(CN)₆ solution. Greenish blue color was formed, it indicates the presence of

polyphenols. 3.4 Extraction of the Dye from Mangrove Bark Powder Using Water 3.4.1 Procedure

Mangrove bark powder 2.5 g

and 250 ml of water were boiled in a stainless steel pot and heated at 80 °C for 45 min.

Then the extracted dye solution was cooled and then filtered. 1 ml of extracted dye solution was diluted in 9 ml of distilled water. An aliquot was introduced in a quartz cell and analyzed in a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Model-UV mini-1240, Shimadzu Corporation, Japan). A scan from 470 to 560 nm was performed in order to generate the characteristic absorption spectra of the sample. The maximum absorbance value (optical density) was detected at 482 nm.

33 3.4.1.1

Effect of Extraction Time on the Concentration of Dye Solution

The same procedure mentioned in Section (3.4.1) was conducted by using different extraction time such as 15, 30, 60 and 75 min respectively. The extraction temperature and material to solvent ratios were kept at constant. 1 ml of each of the aliquots was diluted in 9 ml of distilled water and the optical density was measured at 482 nm. The suitable extraction time was determined based on highest value of optical density and

the concentration of dye solution was calculated. The results are shown in Table (4.4). 3.4.1.2 Effect of Extraction Temperature on the Concentration of Dye Solution

The same procedure mentioned in Section (3.4.1) was conducted by using different extraction temperature 50, 60, 70 and 90 °C respectively. The extraction time and material to solvent ratios were kept at constant. The extraction time and 1 ml of each of the aliquots was diluted in 9 ml of distilled water and the optical density was measured at 482 nm. The suitable extraction temperature was determined based on highest value of optical density and the concentration of dye solution was calculated and the results are shown in Table (4.5).

3.4.1.3

Effect of Material to Solvent Ratio on the Concentration of Dye Solution

The same procedure mentioned in Section (3.4.1) was conducted by using different material to solvent ratio 1, 1.5, 2 and 3 g respectively. The extraction time and temperature were kept at constant. 1 ml of each of the aliquots was diluted in 9 ml of distilled water and the optical density was measured at 482 nm. The suitable material to liquor ratio was determined based on highest value of optical density and the concentration of dye solution was calculated and the results are shown in Table (4.6). 3.4.2

Identification of the Compounds in the Extracted Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Using Water by FT-IR Spectrophotometer

The chemical characteristic profiles and identification of functional groups associated to its specific colour of the extracted dye powder was determined by Perlin Elmer GX FT-IR spectrophotometer. The results are shown in Tables (4.2).

34 3.4.3

Dyeing Process of Cotton Fabrics Using Dye Powder Extracted with Water 3.4.3.1 Dyeing Procedure Mercerization

of

Cotton Fabrics Firstly, 3 g of caustic soda was dissolved in 1 L of warm water before adding to the cotton fabrics.

To prepare mercerized cotton fabrics, 1 yard of cotton fabrics were simmered in caustic soda solution for 30 min and rinsed with water. After completion of this step, the cotton fabrics were put into vinegar solution (4 ml acetic acid to 1 L of water) for 30 min to neutralize it.

To prepare clean cotton fabrics, the cotton fabrics were rinsed with water and then dried at room temperature. After that, the cotton fabrics were tested with a few drops of iodine. The cotton fabrics were cleaned if purple black color did not appear. Pre-Mordanting of Cotton Fabrics In this method, mordant solution was prepared by heating 1 g of alum with 200 ml of water.

This solution was heated to a temperature of 80 °C and 25cm × 25cm of cleaned cotton fabric was simmered in solution for about 30 min. During mordanting, the fabric was frequently stirred with a glass rod

to obtain good penetration of mordant into the cotton fabric. After that, mordant solution was removed and the mordanted cotton fabric was rinsed with water.

The above experiment was also carried out with 0.2

g of copper (II) sulphate as mordant to obtain the mordanted cotton fabrics. Dyeing of Mordanted Cotton Fabrics Dye powder 0.5 g and 200 ml of water were added in the stainless steel pot and heated at 60 °C

and then the mordanted fabric was simmered in this solution for 45 min. Then the fabric was rinsed with water and allowed to air drying. 3.4.3.2

Effect of Dyeing Temperature on Color Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Pre-mordanting Method

The experimental work in this section was based on the procedure mentioned in Section (3.4.3.1). In order to ascertain the effect of dyeing temperature, the same weight of 0.5 g sample and 200 ml of water were used with different dyeing

35 temperature of 50, 70, 80 and 90°C. The dyeing time was 45 min. The results are shown in Tables (4.7) and (4.9). 3.4.3.3

Effect of Dyeing Time on Color Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Pre-mordanting Method

The

experimental work in this section was based on the procedure mentioned in Section (3.4.3.1). In order to ascertain the effect of dyeing time, the same weight of 0.5 g sample and 200 ml of water were used with different dyeing time of 30, 60, 75 and 90 min. The dyeing temperature was 60°C. The results are shown in Tables (4.8)

and (4.10). 3.4.4

Testing the Color Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics 3.4.4.1 Fastness to Washing

In this case, Launder Meter washing machine (Model No. L-4) containing 4- rack test bottle was used. The operation was carried out with Test No.3 of ISO 105.

The required soap solution was prepared with (5 g) of soap per liter

and (2 g) of soda per liter. The dye fabric of (10cm × 10cm) was cut out. The cotton and polyester/ cotton blend fabric were used as adjacent fabrics. The specimen to be tested was placed between the two pieces of adjacent fabrics. The specimens were sewn along each side to form a composite specimen. The composite specimen was placed in the wash pot of the machine and soap solution was added. The steel cover was closed and the soap solution was heated to a temperature of $60 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. After that the composite specimen was tested at $60 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for 30minutes. At the end of operation, the specimen was lifted from the pot and rinsed thoroughly. The stitching of the composite specimen was broken but the fabric must contact at the line of stitching on two corners. Finally, the specimens were

dried at room temperature. The change in color of the specimen was assessed by comparing with the original dyed fabrics and the rating is defined by using Grey Scale for color change.

The staining of the white cotton fabric was also assessed by Grey Scale for staining. The degree of fastness rating of dyed cotton fabrics were determined by using Grey Scale and the results are shown in Table (4.7) to (4.10) and Fig (4.3) to (4.6).

36 3.4.4.2

Fastness to Rubbing

The rubbing fastness of dyed fabric was determined by JIS STDL-0241 Rubbing Tester Machine. The test specimen (25cm × 5cm) and a piece of white bleached cotton fabric about 5 cm were cut parallel to wrap direction for rubbing fastness test. In rubbing fastness test, the test specimen was mounted on the white bleached cotton cloth and placed on the rubbing tester. The rubbing distance was 100 mm. The test specimen was rubbed 100times with (500 g) load at the speed of 30 circles per minute. The white bleached cotton cloth and the test specimen were rubbed together on the tester by the aid of motor. Six different materials were tested simultaneously on the machine. In this study, both dry and wet rubbing fastness tests were carried out. In rubbing fastness test, the rubbed cotton fabric was wetted with water and the amount of water was two times of the fabric weight. The fabric was finally dried at room temperature.

The color stained on bleached cotton fabrics were compared by Grey Scale for staining and the degree of fastness rating was determined. The degree of fastness rating of dyed cotton fabrics were determined by using Grey Scale and the results are shown in Table (4.7) to (4.10) and Fig (4.3)

to (4.6). 3.5 Extraction of the Dye from Mangrove Bark Powder Using 95% Ethanol- Water Mixture 3.5.1 Procedure

Mangrove bark powder 2.5 g was added in 2-neck round bottom flask. 65 ml of 95% ethanol and 185 ml of water (1:3) were added into the flask. The round bottomed flask was fitted with condenser. Then, the extraction was carried out at 70 °C for 90 min. After extraction, the extracted dye solution was cooled and filtered. 1 ml of extracted dye solution was diluted in 9 ml of distilled water. An aliquot was introduced in a quart cell and analyzed in a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Model-UV mini-1240, Shimadzu Corporation, Japan). The maximum absorbance value (optical density) was detected at 482 nm. 3.5.1.1

Effect of Ethanol -Water Ratio on the Concentration of Dye Solution

The same procedure as mentioned in Section (3.5.1) was conducted by varying the ethanol and water ratio in the range of 1:1, 1:2, 1:4 and 1:5 respectively. The

absorbance value of natural dye solution was determined by the same procedure as mentioned in Section (3.5.1) and the results are shown in Table (4.11). 3.5.1.2

Effect of Extraction Time on the Concentration of Dye Solution

The same procedure as mentioned in Section (3.5.1) was conducted by using different extraction time such as 30, 60, 120 and 150 min respectively and the ethanol: water ratio was (1:3). The absorbance value of natural dye solution was determined by the same procedure as mentioned in Section (3.5.1) and the results are shown in Table (4.12). 3.5.1.3

Effect of Extraction Temperature on the Concentration of Dye Solution

The same procedure as mentioned in Section (3.5.1) was conducted by using different extraction temperature such as 50, 60, 80 and 90 °C respectively and the extraction time for 90 min. The absorbance value of natural dye solution was determined by the same procedure as mentioned in Section (3.5.1) and the results are shown in Table (4.13). 3.5.2

Identification of the Compounds in the Extracted Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Using 95% Ethanol-Water Mixture by FT-IR Spectrophotometer

The chemical characteristic profiles and identification of functional groups associated to its specific colour of the extracted dye powder was determined by Perlin Elmer GX FT-IR spectrophotometer. The results are shown in Tables (4.3). 3.5.3

Dyeing Process of Cotton Fabrics Using Dye Powder Extracted with 95% Ethanol-Water Mixture 3.5.3.1 Dyeing Procedure Mercerization of

Cotton Fabrics Cotton fabrics were mercerized according to the same procedure as mentioned in Section (3.4.3.1). Pre-mordanting Method Mordanting of Cotton Fabrics Mercerized cotton fabrics were mordanted according to the same procedure as mentioned in Section (3.4.3.1).

38 Dyeing of Mordanted Cotton Fabrics Mordanted cotton fabrics were dyed according to the same procedure as mentioned in Section (3.4.3.1). 3.5.3.2

Effect of Dyeing Temperature on Color Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Pre-mordanting Method The procedure of dyeing

of mordanted cotton fabric was used as mentioned in Section (3.4.3.2). The results are shown in Tables (4.14) and (4.16). 3.5.3.3

Effect of Dyeing Time on Color Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Pre-mordanting Method

The

procedure of dyeing of mordanted cotton fabric as mentioned in Section (3.4.3.3). The results are shown in Tables (4.15) and (4.17). 3.5.4

Testing the Color Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics 3.5.4.1 Fastness to Washing

In this

experiments, color fastness of dyed cotton fabrics were determined according to the same procedure as mentioned in Section (3.4.4.1). The results are shown in Table (4.14) to (4.17) and Fig (4.7) to (4.10). 3.5.4.2 Fastness to Rubbing The rubbing fastness of dyed cotton fabrics were determined according to the same procedure as mentioned in Section (3.4.4.2). The results are shown in Table (4.14) to (4.17) and Fig (4.7) to (4.10).

39 Figure (3.1)

Mangrove Bark and Mangrove Bark Powder Figure (3.2) Extraction Apparatus for Natural Dye Figure (3.3) Distillation Apparatus for Natural Dye

40

CHAPTER IV 4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION In the extraction of natural dye from mangrove bark powder, the

phytochemical investigation was carried out to determine the presence or absence of chemical compounds. According to the

result of Table (4.1),

phenolic compound, tannins, flavonoids, saponins, alkaloids and polyphenols were present in mangrove bark powder. Figures (4.1) and (4.2) show the comparison of FT-IR spectrums of natural dye powder extracted by water and extracted by 95 % ethanol-water mixture.

Table (4.2) indicates the

structural assignment for FT-IR spectrum of natural dye powder extracted by water.

The bending vibration of alkenes group was found at 781.17 cm^{-1} . Alcohol and phenol group gave the absorption band at 1060.85 cm^{-1} and 1112.93 cm^{-1} . The absorption band at 1284.59 cm^{-1} and 1317.38 cm^{-1} which was attributed to CH symmetric bending vibration. CH asymmetric bending vibration was found at 1446.61 cm^{-1} . The band at 1519.91 cm^{-1} and 1616.35 cm^{-1} were characteristics of stretching vibration of aromatic groups. The band at 2924.09 cm^{-1} was characteristics of stretching vibration of alkanes group. In addition, absorption band at 3392.79 cm^{-1} indicated the presence of amines group. Table (4.3) describes the functional group present in the natural dye powder extracted by 95% ethanol-water medium. Stretching band of alkenes group was found at 781.17 cm^{-1} . Alcohol and phenol group gave the absorption band at 1060.85 cm^{-1} and 1112.93 cm^{-1} . The absorption band at 1284.59 cm^{-1} and 1375.25 cm^{-1} which was attributed to CH symmetric bending vibration. CH asymmetric bending vibration was found at 1446.61 cm^{-1} . The band at 1521.84 cm^{-1} and 1616.35 cm^{-1} were characteristics of stretching region of aromatic groups. The stretching vibration of carbonyl group was found at 1732.08 cm^{-1} . The band at 2924.09 cm^{-1} was characteristics of stretching region of alkanes group. In addition, absorption band at 3385.07 cm^{-1} indicated the presence of amines group. The

effect of extraction time on the concentration of dye solution

was carried out using the extraction time such as 15, 30, 45, 60 and 75 min and the results are shown in Table (4.4). The absorbance values of dye solution were measured by UV-Vis spectrophotometer. According to the results, the suitable

41 extraction time was found to be 45 min because of the maximum absorbance value and concentration of (2.581) ($8.35 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol/L}$) at 482 nm. Table (4.5) shows the

effect of extraction temperature on concentration of dye solution. From the results, the concentration of dye solution

increased with increasing temperature from 50 to 80 °C and then decreased at 90 °C. The suitable extraction temperature was found to be at 80 °C because it gave the maximum absorbance value and concentration (2.601) (8.42×10^{-4} mol/L) than the other extraction temperature. Table (4.6) indicates the

effect of material to solvent ratio on the concentration of dye solution

using the different material to solvent ratio such as 1:250, 1.5:250, 2:250, 2.5:250 and 3:250. It was found that the suitable material to solvent ratio was 2.5 g powder and 250 ml water because of the maximum absorbance value and concentration of (2.601) (8.42×10^{-4} mol/L) at 482 nm. Table (4.7) shows the

effect of dyeing temperature on color fastness of dyed cotton fabrics using natural dye powder extracted by water. From the results, the color fastness of dyed cotton fabrics

dyeing with pre-mordanting method using alum mordant were nearly the same at 60 to 90 °C and so the dyeing temperature 60 °C was selected because of the rubbing fastness grade of dry mark 4 (good) and wet mark 3 (fair) and it save electricity cost and energy consumption.

The effect of dyeing time on the fastness of cotton fabrics was studied at the different dyeing times such as 30, 45, 60, 75

and 90 min at the temperature of 60 °C. The results are shown in Table (4.8) respectively. The dyeing time 60 min was more suitable than the other conditions because of the rubbing fastness of dry mark 4 (good) and wet mark 3 (fair). According to the results of Table (4.9), the cotton fabrics dyeing by pre- mordanting method at 60 °C using copper (II) sulphate mordant was more suitable than the other conditions and selected from the aspect of electricity cost and energy consumption. Table (4.10) indicates the results of

color fastness of dyed cotton fabrics using pre-mordanting method

with copper (II) sulphate. It was also found that dyed cotton fabric dyeing at 60 °C for 60 min was more suitable because of the change of shade mark 3 (fair). Table (4.11) to (4.13) show the extraction of natural dye solution using alcoholic medium. The effect of ethanol-water ratio on concentration of dye solution were determined by using UV-Vis spectrophotometer. From the results of

42 Table (4.11), the absorbance value and concentration of dye solution was found to be maximum (1.14) (3.69×10^{-4} mol/L) at 482 nm using solvent ratio of 1:3. From the results of Table (4.12), the extraction of dye solution at 80 °C for 90 min was more suitable than the other conditions because of the maximum absorbance value and concentration of (1.14) (3.69×10^{-4} mol/L) at 482 nm. It can be clearly seen that the increase in extraction time gave decrease in concentration of dye solution. According to the results of Table (4.13), it was found that the dye solution extracted at 70 °C for 90 min was more suitable than the other

condition because of the absorbance value and concentration of dye solution (1.183) (3.83 ? 10⁻⁴ mol/L). Table (4.14) to (4.17) show the effect of dyeing temperature and

time on color

fastness of dyed cotton fabrics using natural dye powder extracted by 95% ethanol- water mixture.

From the results of Table (4.14), the cotton fabrics dyed by pre- mordanting method at 50 °C for 45 min using alum mordant was more suitable than the other conditions because it gave change of shade mark of 2 (poor). According to the results of Table (4.15), the cotton fabrics dyeing with alum at 50 °C for 60 min was suitable condition because

of the rubbing fastness of dry mark 4 (good) and wet mark 3-4 (fair-good).

From the results of Table (4.16), the color fastness of cotton fabrics dyed at 60 °C to 90 °C were nearly the same and dyeing temperature at 60 °C for 45 min was selected from the aspect of electricity cost. From the results of Table (4.17), the suitable dyeing time was 60 min at 60 °C because

of the rubbing fastness of dry mark 4 (good), wet mark 3 (fair) and change of shade mark 3 (fair).

43

Table (4.1) Phytochemical Investigation of Mangrove Bark Powder Sr.No. Tests Extract Reagents Observation Inference
 1 Phenolic Compound Distilled Water 1%FeCl₃ Violet Color +
 2 Tannins Distilled Water 1%FeCl₃ Deep Blue Precipitate +
 3 Flavonoids 95% Ethanol Conc: H₂SO₄ + Mg Pink Color +
 4 Saponins Distilled Water Shaken Vigorously Frothing +
 5 Alkaloids 1%HCL Dragendroff's Reagent Orange Precipitate +
 6 Polyphenols 95% Ethanol 1% FeCl₃ + 1% K₃Fe(CN)₆ Greenish Blue Color +
 Note: (+) = present, (-) = absent
 The experiments were carried out at the Laboratory of Industrial Chemistry Department, Dagon University.

44 Table (4.2)

Structural Assignment for FT-IR Spectrum of Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Extracted by Water

Sr. No. Wave number, cm⁻¹ Functional Group Observed Literature
 1 3392.79 3500-3000 ???
 Stretching vibration of amines groups
 2 2924.09 > 3000 ???CH Stretching vibration of alkanes groups
 3 1616.35, 1519.91 ~1600 ?C=C Stretching vibration of aromatic groups
 4 1446.61 <1400 ?as CH CH asymmetric bending vibration
 5 1317.38, 1284.59 > 1400 ?s CH CH symmetric bending vibration
 6 1112.93, 1060.85 1260-1000 ?-CO Stretching vibration of alcohol and phenol group
 7 781.17 795-770 ??CH Bending vibration of alkenes group
 The experiments were conducted at the Laboratory of Chemistry Department, West Yangon University.

45 Table (4.3)

Structural Assignment for FT-IR Spectrum of Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Extracted by 95 % Ethanol-Water Mixture

Sr. No. Wave number, cm⁻¹ Functional Group Observed Literature
 1 3385.07 3500-3000 ???
 Stretching vibration of amines groups
 2 2924.09 > 3000 ???CH Stretching vibration of alkanes groups
 3 1732.08 ~1700 ?C=O Stretching vibration of carbonyl groups
 4 1616.35, 1521.84 ~1600 ?C=C Stretching vibration of aromatic groups
 5 1446.61 < 1400 ??s CH CH asymmetric bending vibration
 6 1375.25, 1284.59 > 1400 ?s CH CH symmetric bending vibration
 7 1112.93, 1060.85 1260-1000 ?-CO Stretching vibration of alcohol and phenol group
 8 781.17 795-770 ??CH Bending vibration of alkenes group
 The experiments were conducted at the Laboratory of Chemistry Department, West Yangon University.

46 Table (4.4)

Effect of Extraction Time on the Concentration of Dye Solution Extracted by Water

Wavelength = 482 nm Sr. No. Extraction Time (min) Extraction Temp. (°C) Material to solvent ratio Absorbance Values Concentration (mol/L) Mangrove bark powder (g) Water (ml)
 1 15 90 2.5 250 1.869 6.05 x 10⁻⁴
 2 30 90 2.5 250 2.117 6.85 x 10⁻⁴
 3 45* 90 2.5 250 2.581 8.35 x 10⁻⁴
 4 60 90 2.5 250 2.415 7.82 x 10⁻⁴
 5 75 90 2.5 250 1.733 5.61 x 10⁻⁴
 *the most suitable condition
 The experiments were conducted at the Laboratory of Industrial Chemistry Department, Dagon University. Table (4.5)

Effect of Extraction Temperature on the Concentration of Dye Solution Extracted by Water

Wavelength = 482 nm Sr. No.

Extraction Temp. (°C)

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Extraction Time (min) Material to solvent ratio Absorbance Values Concentration (mol/L) Mangrove bark powder (g) Water (ml)
 1 50 45 2.5 250 1.699 5.49 x 10⁻⁴
 2 60 45 2.5 250 1.820 5.89 x 10⁻⁴
 3 70 45 2.5 250 1.822 5.9 x 10⁻⁴
 4 80* 45 2.5 250 2.601 8.42 x 10⁻⁴
 5 90 45 2.5 250 2.581 8.35 x 10⁻⁴
 *the most suitable condition
 The experiments were conducted at the Laboratory of Industrial Chemistry Department, Dagon University.

47 Table (4.6)

Effect of

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Material to Solvent Ratio on the Concentration of Dye Solution Extracted by Water

Wavelength = 482 nm *

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the most suitable condition The experiments were conducted at the Laboratory of Industrial Chemistry Department, Dagon University. Sr. No. Material to solvent ratio

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Extraction Time (min) Extraction Temp. (°C) Absorbance Values Concentration (mol/L)
 Mangrove bark powder (g) Water (ml) 1 1.0 250 45 80 1.243 4.02 x 10⁻⁴ 2 1.5 250 45 80 1.606
 5.19 x 10⁻⁴ 3 2.0 250 45 80 1.662 6.21 x 10⁻⁴ 4 2.5* 250 45 80 2.601 8.42 x 10⁻⁴ 5 3.0 250 45
 80 1.685 5.45 x 10⁻⁴

48

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Table (4.7)

Effect of Dyeing Temperature on Color Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Extracted by Water and Alum Mordant

Dye powder = 0.5 g Volume of dye solution = 200 ml Dyeing Method = Pre-mordanting method Weight of mercerized cotton fabrics = 25cm x 25cm Alum = 1 g Mordanting temperature and time = 80 °C, 30 min *

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the most suitable condition Note: 5 = excellent, 4 = good, 3 = fair, 2 = poor, 1 = very poor, p/c = polyester+cotton The experiments were conducted at the

No. (1), Development Centre for Textile Technology Industry, Textile Industry, Mayangone Township, Yangon Region.

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Sr. No. Sample Code Dyeing Condition Washing Fastness (60°C, 30min) Rubbing Fastness (500g,100 times) Temp. (°C) Time (min) Change of shade Staining on cotton Dry Wet Cotton p/c
 c 1 A 1 50 45 1 4 4 4 2 2 A 2 60* 45 1 4 4 4 3 3 A 3 70 45 1 4 4 4 3 4 A 4 80 45 1 4 4 4 3-4 5 A 5
 90 45 1 4 4 4 3

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Table (4.8)

Effect of Dyeing Time on Color Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Extracted by Water and Alum Mordant

Dye powder = 0.5 g Volume of dye solution = 200 ml Dyeing Method = Pre-mordanting method Weight of mercerized cotton fabrics = 25cm ? 25cm Alum = 1 g Mordanting temperature and time = 80°C, 30 min *

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the most suitable condition Note: 5 = excellent, 4 = good, 3 = fair, 2 = poor, 1 = very poor, p/c = polyester+cotton The experiments were conducted at the

No. (1), Development Centre for Textile Technology Industry, Textile Industry, Mayangone Township, Yangon Region.

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Sr. No. Sample Code Dyeing Condition Washing Fastness (60°C, 30min) Rubbing Fastness (500g,100 times) Time. (min) Temp (°C) Change of shade Staining on cotton Dry Wet Cotton p/c
 c 1 B 1 30 60 1 4 4 4 3 2 B 2 45 60 1 4 4 3-4 2-3 3 B 3 60* 60 2 4 4 4 3 4 B 4 75 60 1 4 4 3-4 2-3 5
 B 5 90 60 1 4 4 4 3

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Table (4.9)

Effect of Dyeing Temperature on Color Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Extracted by Water and Copper (II) Sulphate Mordant

Dye powder = 0.5 g Volume of dye solution = 200 ml Dyeing Method = Pre-mordanting method Weight of mercerized cotton fabrics = 25cm ? 25cm Copper (II) sulphate = 0.2 g Mordanting temperature and time = 80°C, 30 min *

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the most suitable condition Note: 5 = excellent, 4 = good, 3 = fair, 2 = poor, 1 = very poor, p/c = polyester+cotton The experiments were conducted at the

No. (1), Development Centre for Textile Technology Industry, Textile Industry, Mayangone Township, Yangon Region.

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Sr. No. Sample Code Dyeing Condition Washing Fastness (60°C, 30min) Rubbing Fastness (500g,100 times) Temp. (°C) Time (min) Change of shade Staining on cotton Dry Wet Cotton p/c
 c 1 C 1 50 45 3 4 4 4 3 2 C 2 60* 45 3 4 4 4 3-4 3 C 3 70 45 3 4 4 4 3-4 4 C 4 80 45 3 4 4 4 3-4 5 C
 5 90 45 2 4 4 4 3

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Table (4.10)

Effect of Dyeing Time on Color Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Extracted by Water and Copper (II) Sulphate Mordant

Dye powder = 0.5 g Volume of dye solution = 200 ml Dyeing Method = Pre-mordanting method Weight of mercerized cotton fabrics = 25cm x 25cm Copper (II) sulphate = 0.2 g Mordanting temperature and time = 80°C, 30 min *

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the most suitable condition Note: 5 = excellent, 4 = good, 3 = fair, 2 = poor, 1 = very poor, p/c = polyester+cotton The experiments were conducted at the

No. (1), Development Centre for Textile Technology Industry, Textile Industry, Mayangone Township, Yangon Region.

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Sr. No. Sample Code Dyeing Condition Washing Fastness (60°C, 30min) Rubbing Fastness (500g,100 times) Time (min) Temp. (°C) Change of shade Staining on cotton Dry Wet Cotton p/c
 c 1 D 1 30 60 1 4 4 4 3 2 D 2 45 60 2 4 4 4 3 3 D 3 60* 60 3 4 4 4 3 4 D 4 75 60 1 4 4 4 3 5 D 5 90
 60 1 4 4 4 3

52

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Table (4.11)

Effect of Ethanol -Water Ratio on the Concentration of Dye Solution Extracted by 95% Ethanol-Water Mixture Weight of

mangrove bark powder = 2.5 g Wavelength = 482 nm Sr. No. Solvent Ratio Extraction Time (min) Extraction Temp. (°C) Absorbance Value Concentration (mol/ L) Ethanol : Water 1 1 : 1 90 80 0.795 2.57 x 10⁻⁴ 2 1: 2 90 80 0.821 2.67 x 10⁻⁴ 3 1: 3* 90 80 1.14 3.69 x 10⁻⁴ 4 1: 4 90 80 0.601 1.95 x 10⁻⁴ 5 1: 5 90 80 0.842 2.73 x 10⁻⁴ *the most suitable condition The

experiments were conducted at the Laboratory of Industrial Chemistry Department, Dagon University.

53 Table (4.12)

Effect of Extraction Time on the Concentration of Dye Solution Extracted by 95 % Ethanol-Water Mixture Weight of

mangrove bark powder = 2.5 g Wavelength = 482 nm Sr. No. Extraction Time (min) Extraction Temp. (°C) Solvent Ratio Absorbance Value Concentration (mol/L) Ethanol : Water 1 30 80 1: 3 0.95 3.07 x 10⁻⁴ 2 60 80 1: 3 1.06 3.43 x 10⁻⁴ 3 90* 80 1: 3 1.14 3.69 x 10⁻⁴ 4 120 80 1: 3 0.917 2.97 x 10⁻⁴ 5 150 80 1: 3 0.717 2.32 x 10⁻⁴ *the most suitable condition The experiments were conducted at the Laboratory of Industrial Chemistry Department, Dagon University.

54 Table (4.13)

Effect of Extraction Temperature on the Concentration of Dye Solution Extracted by 95 % Ethanol-Water Mixture Weight of

mangrove bark powder = 2.5 g Wavelength = 482 nm Sr. No. Extraction Temp. (°C) Extraction Time (min) Solvent Ratio Absorbance Value Concentration (mol/L) Ethanol : Water 1 50 90 1: 3 0.852 2.76 x 10⁻⁴ 2 60 90 1: 3 0.964 3.12 x 10⁻⁴ 3 70* 90 1: 3 1.183 3.83 x 10⁻⁴ 4 80 90 1: 3 1.14 3.69 x 10⁻⁴ 5 90 90 1: 3 0.985 3.19 x 10⁻⁴ *the most suitable condition The experiments were conducted at the Laboratory of Industrial Chemistry Department, Dagon University.

55 Table (4.14)

Effect of Dyeing Temperature on Color

Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Extracted by 95 % Ethanol-Water Mixture

and Alum Mordant

Dye powder = 0.5 g Volume of dye solution = 200 ml Dyeing Method = Pre-mordanting method Weight of mercerized cotton fabrics = 25cm x 25cm Alum = 1 g Mordanting temperature and time = 80 °C, 30 min *

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the most suitable condition Note: 5 = excellent, 4 = good, 3 = fair, 2 = poor, 1 = very poor p/c = polyester + cotton The experiments were conducted at the

No. (1), Development Centre for Textile Technology Industry, Textile Industry, Mayangone Township, Yangon Region.

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Sr. No. Sample Code Dyeing Condition Washing Fastness (60 °C, 30min) Rubbing Fastness (500g,100 times) Temp. (°C) Time (min) Change of shade Staining on cotton Dry Wet Cotton p/c
 c 1 E 1 50* 45 2 4 4 4 3 2 E 2 60 45 1 4 4 4 3 3 E 3 70 45 1 4 4 4 3 4 E 4 80 45 1 4 4 4 3 5 E 5 90
 45 1 4 4 4 3

56

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Table (4.15)

Effect of Dyeing Time on Color

Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Extracted by 95 % Ethanol- Water Mixture

and Alum Mordant

Dye powder = 0.5 g Volume of dye solution = 200 ml Dyeing Method = Pre-mordanting method Weight of mercerized cotton fabrics = 25cm x 25cm Alum = 1 g Mordanting temperature and time = 80 °C, 30 min *

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the most suitable condition Note: 5 =excellent, 4 = good, 3 = fair, 2 = poor, 1 = very poor p/c = polyester + cotton The experiments were conducted at the

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Sr. No. Sample Code Dyeing Condition Washing Fastness (60°C, 30min) Rubbing Fastness (500g,100 times) Time (min) Temp. (°C) Change of shade Staining on cotton Dry Wet Cotton p/c
 c 1 F 1 30 50 1 4 4 4 3 2 F 2 45 50 1 4 4 4 3 3 F 3 60* 50 1 4 4 4 3-4 4 F 4 75 50 1 4 4 4 3 5 F 5 90
 50 1 4 4 4 3

57

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Table (4.16)

Effect of Dyeing Temperature on Color

Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Extracted by 95 % Ethanol-Water Mixture

and Copper (II) Sulphate Mordant

Dye powder = 0.5 g Volume of dye solution = 200 ml Dyeing Method = Pre-mordanting method Weight of mercerized cotton fabrics = 25cm ? 25cm Copper (II) sulphate = 0.2 g Mordanting temperature and time = 80 °C, 30 min *

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the most suitable condition Note: 5 =excellent, 4 = good, 3 = fair, 2 = poor, 1 = very poor p/c = polyester + cotton The experiments were conducted at the

No. (1), Development Centre for Textile Technology Industry, Textile Industry, Mayangone Township, Yangon Region.

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Sr. No. Sample Code Dyeing Condition Washing Fastness (60 °C, 30min) Rubbing Fastness (500g,100 times) Temp. (°C) Time (min) Change of shade Staining on cotton Dry Wet Cotton p/c
c 1 G 1 50 45 2 4 4 3 2 2 G 2 60* 45 3 4 4 3-4 3 3 G 3 70 45 3 4 4 4 3 4 G 4 80 45 3 4 4 4 3-4 5 G
5 90 45 3 4 4 3-4 3

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Table (4.17)

Effect of Dyeing Time on Color

Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Extracted by 95 % Ethanol- Water Mixture

and Copper (II) Sulphate Mordant

Dye powder = 0.5 g Volume of dye solution = 200 ml Dyeing Method = Pre-mordanting method Weight of mercerized cotton fabrics = 25cm ? 25cm Copper (II) sulphate = 0.2 g Mordanting temperature and time = 80 °C, 30 min *

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the most suitable condition Note: 5 =excellent, 4 = good, 3 = fair, 2 = poor, 1 = very poor p/c = polyester + cotton The experiments were conducted at the

No. (1), Development Centre for Textile Technology Industry, Textile Industry, Mayangone Township, Yangon Region.

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Sr. No. Sample Code Dyeing Condition Washing Fastness (60°C, 30min) Rubbing Fastness (500g,100 times) Time (min) Temp. (°C) Change of shade Staining on cotton Dry Wet Cotton p/c
 1 H 1 30 60 3 4 4 4 3 2 H 2 45 60 3 4 4 4 3 3 H 3 60* 60 3 4 4 4 3 4 H 4 75 60 2 4 4 4 3 5 H 5 90
 60 2 4 4 4 3

59

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Figure (4.1)

FT-IR Spectrum of Extracted Mangrove Bark Dye Powder by Water

60 Figure (4.2) FT-IR Spectrum of Extracted Mangrove Bark Dye Powder by 95% Ethanol-Water Mixture

61

Sr. No. Sample Code Original Sample Washing Fastness (I.S.O Test No.3) (06 °C, 30min) Rubbing Fastness (500g,100 times) Dry mark Wet mark 1 A 1 2 A 2 3 A 3 4 A 4 5 A 5 Figure (4.3)

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Color Fastness of Cotton Fabrics Dyeing with Extracted Dye Powder Using Water (Mordanted with Alum)

62

Sr. No. Sample Code Original Sample Washing Fastness (I.S.O Test No.3) (06 °C, 30min) Rubbing Fastness (500g,100 times) Dry mark Wet mark 1 B 1 2 B 2 3 B 3 4 B 4 5 B 5 Figure (4.4)

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100%

Color Fastness of Cotton Fabrics Dyeing with Extracted Dye Powder Using Water (Mordanted with Alum)

63

Sr. No. Sample Code Original Sample Washing Fastness (I.S.O Test No.3) (06 °C, 30min) Rubbing Fastness (500g,100 times) Dry mark Wet mark 1 C 1 2 C 2 3 C 3 4 C 4 5 C 5 Figure (4.5)

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100%

Color Fastness of Cotton Fabrics Dyeing with Extracted Dye Powder Using Water (Mordanted with Copper (II) Sulphate)

64

Sr. No. Sample Code Original Sample Washing Fastness (I.S.O Test No.3) (06 °C, 30min)
 Rubbing Fastness (500g,100 times) Dry mark Wet mark 1 D 1 2 D 2 3 D 3 4 D 4 5 D 5 Figure
 (4.6)

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100%

Color Fastness of Cotton Fabrics Dyeing with Extracted Dye Powder Using Water (Mordanted with Copper (II) Sulphate)

65

Sr. No. Sample Code Original Sample Washing Fastness (I.S.O Test No.3) (06 °C, 30min)
 Rubbing Fastness (500g,100 times) Dry mark Wet mark 1 E 1 2 E 2 z 3 E 3 4 E 4 5 E 5 Figure
 (4.7)

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Color Fastness of Cotton Fabrics Dyeing with Extracted Dye Powder Using 95% Ethanol-Water Mixture (Mordanted with Alum)

66

Sr. No. Sample Code Original Sample Washing Fastness (I.S.O Test No.3) (06 °C, 30min)
 Rubbing Fastness (500g,100 times) Dry mark Wet mark 1 F 1 2 F 2 3 F 3 4 F 4 5 F 5 Figure (4.8)

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Color Fastness of Cotton Fabrics Dyeing with Extracted Dye Powder Using 95% Ethanol-Water Mixture (Mordanted with Alum)

67

Sr. No. Sample Code Original Sample Washing Fastness (I.S.O Test No.3) (06 °C, 30min)
 Rubbing Fastness (500g,100 times) Dry mark Wet mark 1 G 1 2 G 2 3 G 3 4 G 4 5 G 5 Figure
 (4.9)

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Color Fastness of Cotton Fabrics Dyeing with Extracted Dye Powder Using 95% Ethanol-Water Mixture (Mordanted with Copper (II) Sulphate)

68 Figure (4.10) Color Fastness of Cotton Fabrics Dyeing with Extracted Dye Powder Using 95% Ethanol-Water Mixture (Mordanted with Copper (II) Sulphate)

Sr. No. Sample Code Original Sample Washing Fastness (I.S.O Test No.3) (06 °C, 30min)
Rubbing Fastness (500g,100 times) Dry mark Wet mark 1 H 1 2 H 2 3 H 3 4 H 4 5 H 5

69

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CONCLUSION

In this research work natural dye was extracted from mangrove bark

using two different media such as aqueous and alcoholic media. According to the results of phytochemical tests, it was found that the colour compounds such as

phenolic compound, tannins, flavonoids, saponins, alkaloids and polyphenols were present in mangrove bark. From the results of FT-IR

analysis, the structural assignment

of natural dye powder extracted by water and extracted by 95% ethanol-water mixture

were nearly the same. From the results of absorbance values and concentration of dye solution, it can be concluded that the suitable conditions for extraction of natural dye by using aqueous media were found to be material to solvent ratio (1:100) and extraction temperature 80 °C for 45 min. It was also found that the most suitable conditions for extraction of natural dye solution were ethanol-water ratio (1:3), extraction time 90 min and extraction temperature 70 °C. It can be seen that the concentration of dye solution was decreased in increasing extraction time and temperature. According to the results of absorbance values and the concentration of dye solution extracted by aqueous media at 80 °C for 45 min was (2.601) and the dye solution extracted by alcoholic media at 70 °C for 90 min was (1.183). It can be concluded that the aqueous media was more suitable than the alcoholic media. The colour fastness of

cotton fabrics dyeing by natural dye powder extracted by water at 60 °C for 60 min using copper (II) sulphate gave the better results

than the colour fastness results of dyed cotton fabrics using alum. The colour

fastness of cotton fabrics dyeing by natural dye powder extracted by 95% ethanol-water mixture

at 60°C for 60 min using copper (II) sulphate gave the better results

than the colour fastness results of dyed cotton fabrics using alum. The cotton fabrics dyeing by pre-mordanting method with copper (II) sulphate gave attractive colour and acceptable fastness properties than the alum mordant. It was observed that

the cotton fabric dyeing by natural dye powder extracted by water at 60°C for 60 min using copper (II) sulphate gave the better

result

of the rubbing fastness of dry mark 4 (good), wet mark 3-4 (fair-good) and change of shade mark

of 3 (fair) than the colour

fastness of dyed cotton fabrics dyeing by natural dye powder extracted by 95% ethanol-water mixture

at 60°C for 60 min.

70 SUGGESTIONS FOR FUTURE WORK For future research work, natural dye solution should be extracted from mangrove bark using different solvents such as n-hexane and methanol and converted into powder form. Extraction of natural dyes from mangrove bark should also be conducted using alkali and acidic media. Mangrove dye powder should be used for the preparation of food colourant and medicinal products. Furthermore, more studies dyeing processes should also be conducted on protein fibres such as silk and wool and also synthetic fibres such as nylon and polyester by using extracted dye powder from mangrove bark. Studies should also be conducted by using other mordants such as wood ash, salt, and iron etc. For accessing the quality and stability of dyeing product, fastness to perspiration and light fastness should also be conducted.

71 HYPOTHETICAL PROCESS DESIGNS

72

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Washing Debarking Drying Screening Grinding Figure A: Process Flow Diagram for the Extraction of Natural Dye Powder from Mangrove Bark (using Water) Extraction Water Natural Dye Powder Pieces of Mangrove Stem Evaporation Drying Grinding

73 Washing Debarking Drying Screening Grinding Pieces of Mangrove Stem Extraction Distillation Evaporation Drying Natural Dye Powder Figure B: Process Flow Diagram for the Extraction of Natural Dye Powder from Mangrove Bark (using 95% Ethanol-Water Mixture) 95%

Ethanol-Water Mixture Grinding

74 Simmering Washing Washing Cleaned Cotton Fabrics Mercerized Cotton Fabrics Cotton fabrics

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Figure C: Process Flow Diagram for the Mercerizing of Cotton Fabrics

caustic soda solution (3 g/ L)

75 Simmering in Mordant Solution Washing Mordanted Fabric Dyeing Cleaned Cotton Fabrics Washing Air drying Dyed Cotton Fabric

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Figure D: Process Flow Diagram for Dyeing of Cotton Fabrics Using Pre-mordanting Method 0.5 g dye powder and 200 ml water

76 APPENDICES APPENDIX A COST ESTIMATION FOR THE EXTRACTED NATURAL DYE POWDER FROM MANGROVE BARK POWDER (USING WATER) Basis: 100g / day Capacity of one package = 50g Production day = 300 days / year One shift = 8 hours Yield of extracted natural dye powder = 20% Sr. No. Direct Production Cost Amount Cost / unit (Kyat) Total Cost (Kyat) 1 Raw Materials Mangrove bark powder Pure water Filter paper 500g/day 50L/day 5sheets/day K. 5/ g K. 25/L K. 35/sheet 750,000 375,000 52,500 2 Labour Cost Supervisor Unskilled worker 1 No. 2 No. K. 5000/ day K. 4000/ day 1,500,000 2,400,000 3 Utilities Cost Electricity Water 20unit/ day 50L/day K. 75/ unit K. 5/ L 450,000 75,000 4 Packaging and labelling 10package/day K.10/ package 30,000 Total Cost 5,632,500 Purchased equipment cost, P = K.300,000 Salvage value, L = K. 10,000 Service Life, n = 10 years

77 Annual straight line depreciation = $P - L / n = 100000 - 10000 / 10 = 90000$? = K. 29,000 Manufacturing Cost = Direct Production Cost + Fixed Charges = K. 5632500 + K. 29000 = K. 5661500 Manufacturing Cost/ package = $3000 / 50 = 60$ 5661500 = K. 1887.2/ package Only raw materials, labour, utilities and packing costs were taken into consideration for direct production costs. Only depreciation on equipment was taken into consideration in fixed charges.

78 COST ESTIMATION FOR THE EXTRACTED NATURAL DYE POWDER FROM MANGROVE BARK POWDER (USING 95% ETHANOL-WATER MIXTURE) Basis: 100g / day Capacity of one package = 50g Production day = 300 days / year One shift = 8 hours Yield of extracted natural dye powder = 16% Sr. No. Direct Production Cost Amount Cost / unit (Kyat) Total Cost (Kyat) 1 Raw Materials Mangrove bark powder Ethanol Water Filter paper 625g/day 16.25L/day 48.75L/day 5sheets/day K. 5/g K. 1700/L K. 25/L K. 35/sheet 937,500 8,287,500 365,625 52,500 2 Labour Cost Supervisor Unskilled worker 1 No. 2 No. K. 5000/ day K. 4000/ day 1,500,000 2,400,000 3 Utilities Cost Electricity Water 30unit/day 50L/day K. 75/ unit K. 5/ L 675,000 75,000 4 Packaging and labelling 10package/day K.10/package 30,000 Total Cost 14,323,125

Water Mixture) Basis: 50 yards of dyed cotton fabric/ day Capacity of one package = 10 yard
Production day = 300 days/ year

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One shift = 8 hours Purchased equipment cost, P = K.300, 000 Salvage value, L = K. 10, 000
Service Life, n = 10 years Annual straight line depreciation =

P - L n

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100%

Sr. No. Direct Production Cost Amount Cost / unit (Kyat) Total Cost (Kyat) 1 2 Raw Materials
Extracted dye powder Water Cotton fabrics Chemicals Sodium hydroxide Acetic acid Copper
(II) sulphate 300g/day 120L/day 50yards/day 150g/day 200ml/day 120g/day K. 479/g K. 25/L
K. 1300/yard K. 40/g K. 15/ml K. 40/g 43,110,000 900,000 19,500,000 1,800,000 900,000
1,440,000 3 4 Labour Cost Supervisor Unskilled worker Utilities Cost Electricity Water 1 No. 2
No. 20unit/day 100L/day K. 5000/ day K. 4000/ day K. 75/ unit K. 5/ L 1,500,000 2,400,000
450,000 75,000 5 Packaging and labelling 50package/day K.100/package 150,000 Total Cost
72,225,000

83 = 10 10000 300000 ? =

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K. 29,000 Manufacturing Cost = Direct Production Cost + Fixed Charges = K. 72225000 + K.
29000 = K. 72,254,000 Manufacturing Cost/ package = 1500 72254000 = K. 48169.3/ package
Manufacturing Cost/ yard = K. 4816.9/ yard Only raw materials, labour, utilities and packing
costs were taken into consideration for direct production costs. Only depreciation on
equipment was taken into consideration in fixed charges.

84 APPENDIX B 1. Preparation of Dragendorff's Reagent Solution A: A 1.7 g bismuth nitrate in
100 ml mixture of water - acetic acid, H₂O - HOAc (80:20). Solution B: A 40 g of potassium
iodide in 100 ml distilled water. The reagent was prepared by mixing 5 ml solution A with 5
ml solution B together with 20 ml of acetic acid and 70 ml of distilled water into reagent
bottle. 2. Calculation of Concentration of Dye Solution According to Beer- Lambert law, A =
Where, A= Absorbance of the solution ϵ = Molar absorptivity (L/ mol cm) l = Cell path length
(cm) c = Concentration of absorbing species (mol/L) For example: A = 0.795 ϵ = 30900 L/mol
cm (Pratap Reddy, 2005) l = 1cm c = ? c = = 30900 79.0 \times 10 = 2.57 \times 10⁻⁵ \times 10 = 2.57 \times 10⁻⁴
mol/L

85

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1 CHAPTER I 1. INTRODUCTION Dyes and pigments are the most important colourants used to add a colour or to change the colour of something absorbed from the aqueous solution. Dyes can be defined as organic chemical compounds which have property of producing the phenomenon of colour by light absorption. It must be soluble in the application medium, usually water, at some points during the coloration process and usually exhibit some substantivity for the material being dyed and be absorbed from the aqueous solution. These are intensely coloured materials that retained in substances by physical absorption, mechanical retention and by formation of covalent chemical bonds or complexes with salts or metals. Dyes are the colorant

that has substantivity for a substrate, either inherent or induced by reactants (

Anita Pal. 2017). Dyes are used for imparting color

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?CHAPTER I 1. INTRODUCTION Dyes and pigments are the most important colourants used to add a colour or to change the colour of something absorbed from the aqueous solution. Dyes can be defined as organic chemical compounds which have property of producing the phenomenon of colour by light absorption. It must be soluble in the application medium, usually water, at some points during the coloration process and usually exhibit some substantivity for the material being dyed and be absorbed from the aqueous solution. These are intensely coloured materials that retained in substances by physical absorption, mechanical retention and by formation of covalent chemical bonds or complexes with salts or metals. Dyes are the colorant that has substantivity for a substrate, either inherent or induced by reactants (Anita Pal. 2017). Dyes are used for imparting color to an infinite variety of materials like textiles, paper, wood, varnishes, leather, ink, fur, foodstuff, cosmetics, medicine, etc. Dyes are broadly categorized into two types

to an infinite variety of materials like textiles, paper, wood, varnishes, leather, ink, fur, foodstuff, cosmetics, medicine, etc.

Dyes are broadly categorized into two types namely; synthetic dyes obtained from chemical substance or derived through chemical process and natural dyes obtained from

natural sources. The term natural dyes

covers all the dyes derived from natural sources such as plants, insects and minerals (

Gupta, 1990).

Dyes

and textile are an important part of our everyday life. In the production of clothes, dyeing is a very important process.

Natural dyes are

comprised of dyes

processing. They impart colour when applied to substrate. This phenomenon is known as dyeing.

Main sources of natural dyes are vegetable, animals and minerals. They can be obtained from any part of plants viz. leaves, fruits, seeds, flowers, barks and

roots (

namely; synthetic dyes obtained from chemical substance or derived through chemical process and natural dyes obtained from natural sources. The term natural dyes covers all the dyes derived from natural sources such as plants, insects and minerals (Gupta, 1990). Dyes and textile are an important part of our everyday life. In the production of clothes, dyeing is a very important process. Natural dyes are comprised of dyes processing. They impart colour when applied to substrate. This phenomenon is known as dyeing. Main sources of natural dyes are vegetable, animals and minerals. They can be obtained from any part of plants viz. leaves, fruits, seeds, flowers, barks and roots (Marjo Moeye, 1993). Natural dyes are pleasing to the eye and the mind because natural dyes are pigments derived from nature. Moreover, uses of natural dyes in textile industry can reduce environmental pollution. Nowadays the use of synthetic dyes in textile industry is increasing rapidly (<http://www.nopr.niscair.res.in/bisteream>). Productions of synthetic dyes make use of petrochemical source, and some of these dyes contain carcinogenic amines. The application of such dyes causes serious health hazards and influences negatively the eco-balance of nature. Research across the world has shown that synthetic dyes are suspected to release harmful chemicals that are allergic, carcinogenic and detrimental to human health. Use of synthetic dyes involves release of enormous amount of hazardous chemicals in the environment during their production and subsequent use (Anita Pal, 2017). Natural dyes, obtained from natural sources are renewable and sustainable bioresource products, with minimum environmental impact and are known

Marjo

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2 involves release of enormous amount of hazardous chemicals in the environment during their production and subsequent use (

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for their use, not only in colouration of textiles but also as food ingredients and cosmetics since antiquity. They produce very uncommon, soothing and soft shades as compared to synthetic dyes. Plant leaves, fruits and other parts are potential sources of natural dyes. Dyes from these sources are non-allergic, non-toxic as no petrochemicals or catalysts are used in the extraction and manufacturing (Anita Pal, 2017). Above all, they are environment-friendly and can be recycled after use. Natural dyes find application in many ways in clothes, foods, pharmaceuticals, paintings, paints and cosmetics. Due to above reasons, many advanced countries are spending huge amounts on research in natural dyes because of being safe and eco-friendly (Anita Pal, 2017). Mangroves (*Ceriops decandra* (Griff.) Ding Hou) contains tannin and may be used for tannin industry. It is found high tannin content especially in members of the Rhizophoraceae. Mangrove barks are rich in tannin ranging from 15-36% and can produce reddish brown dyes. The bark yield a colouring matter which produces beautiful, red shades on cotton, wool and silk (Buppha Somboon, 2016). The aim of this research work is to produce the natural dye powder from mangrove bark, to study the suitable extraction medium by using water and different volume of ethanol (95%)-water mixture, to study the effect of extraction medium on the concentration of natural dye solution by UV spectrophotometer and to evaluate the fastness properties of dyed cotton fabrics. CHAPTER II 2. LITERATURE REVIEW 2.1 Botanical Aspect of Mangrove Botanical Name - *Ceriops decandra* (Griff.) Ding Hou Family Name -

environmental impact and are known for their use, not only in colouration of textiles but also as food ingredients and cosmetics since antiquity. They

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The aim of this research work is to produce the natural dye powder from

Rhizophoraceae English Name - Mangrove Local Name - Madama

Figure (2.1) Mangrove Trees

Figure (2.2) Mangrove Barks

Mangroves are found in the tropical and subtropical coasts which are bathed by warm ocean currents. Mangroves cannot survive in winter conditions and need warm temperatures above 24°C. Mangrove forests are salt tolerant forest ecosystem and they are formed when the marine water reached to the coastal area. In Myanmar, mangrove forests occur in the coastal area of Rakhine State, Tanintharyi Division and delta area of Ayeyarwady Division. Mangrove forests are one of the most productive and biologically diverse wetlands on earth. It is an ecosystem that is made up of both a community of living things and the non-living environment. The mangrove ecosystem does not have as many species of plants and animals as other ecosystems due to the harsh and constantly changing environment (Zaw Win Myint, 2008). In general, geography, coastal topography and tidal regime determine the presence or absence and extent of the mangroves. Structure, physical properties and chemical composition, salinity, acidity of soil and sediments, the nature of the substratum as well as the climate determine the development, growth and productivity of mangrove ecosystem. Although small in comparison with the world's total forests, they play a very important role in the ecosystem of the region. They prevent soil erosion by acting as a wind and water break. They

mangrove bark, to study the suitable extraction medium by using water and different volume of ethanol (95%)-water mixture, to study the effect of extraction medium on the concentration of natural dye solution by UV spectrophotometer and to evaluate the fastness properties of dyed cotton fabrics.

3 CHAPTER II 2. LITERATURE REVIEW 2.1 Botanical Aspect of Mangrove Botanical Name - *Ceriops decandra* (Griff.) Ding Hou Family Name - Rhizophoraceae English Name - Mangrove Local Name - Madama Figure (2.1) Mangrove Trees Figure (2.2) Mangrove Barks

4 Mangroves are found in the tropical and subtropical coasts which are bathed by warm ocean currents. Mangroves cannot survive in winter conditions and need warm temperatures above 24°C. Mangrove forests are salt tolerant forest ecosystem and they are formed when the marine water reached to the coastal area. In Myanmar, mangrove forests occur in the coastal area of Rakhine State, Tanintharyi Division and delta area of Ayeyarwady Division. Mangrove forests are one of the most productive and biologically diverse wetlands on earth. It is an ecosystem that is made up of both a community of living things and the non-living environment. The mangrove ecosystem does not have as many species of plants and animals as other ecosystems due to the harsh and constantly changing environment (Zaw Win Myint, 2008). In general, geography, coastal topography and tidal regime determine the presence or absence and extent of the mangroves. Structure, physical properties and chemical composition, salinity, acidity of soil and sediments, the nature of

maintain moisture and breeding grounds for many plants and animals both on land and in the sea. They also provide food, construction materials, fibbers, and medicinal plants to dwellers in and near the coastal zones (Zaw Win Myint, 2008). Mangroves could be identified as three types; the red mangrove, the black mangrove and the white mangrove. The red mangrove can be distinguished by the reddish color to the bark of the trunk roots. This type of mangrove is also called the "Walking Tree". The black mangrove is the largest and tallest of the three types listed above because of their age. They are found upland to the red mangroves, located at higher elevations and are the most cold tolerant. The bark of this tree is dark which gives it the name black mangrove while the white mangroves are located at higher elevations than both the red and black mangroves. This type can also be identified by its leaves. Each type of mangrove is located at different areas along the coastline and plays a distinct role in the respective areas they are located (Diana Maikut, 2004).

2.2 Uses of Mangroves The uses of mangroves falls into two categories, firstly the use of the mangrove ecosystem as a whole or its conversion to other uses, and secondly, the use of products from the mangrove ecosystem. The uses of mangroves are many and varied. A fundamental function of all forests has been to supply timber for cooking, heating and constructing dwellings, and mangrove forests are no exception. Traditionally, people have used mangroves for the benefit of the local community, but increasing populations have led to an increasing non-sustainable abuse of the resources. In Malaysia, where

the substratum as well as the climate determine the development, growth and productivity of mangrove ecosystem. Although small in comparison with the world's total forests, they play a very important role in the ecosystem of the region. They prevent soil erosion by acting as a wind and water break. They maintain moisture and breeding grounds for many plants and animals both on land and in the sea. They also provide food, construction materials, fibbers, and medicinal plants to dwellers in and near the coastal zones (Zaw Win Myint, 2008). Mangroves could be identified as three types; the red mangrove, the black mangrove and the white mangrove. The red mangrove can be distinguished by the reddish color to the bark of the trunk roots. This type of mangrove is also called the "Walking Tree". The black mangrove is the largest and tallest of the three types listed above because of their age. They are found upland to the red mangroves, located at higher elevations and are the most cold tolerant. The bark of this tree is dark which gives it the name black mangrove while the white mangroves are located at higher elevations than both the red and black mangroves. This type can also be identified by its leaves. Each type of mangrove is located at different areas along the coastline and plays a distinct role in the respective areas they are located (Diana Maikut, 2004).

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mangroves occur in profusion, an important cottage industry is the manufacture of shingles for roof thatching. Basketry, corks and floats are obtained from the pneumatophores. It has been exported from the Philippines to various parts of the world for utilization in the textile industry and extracts of stilt roots exhibited mosquito larvicidal activity. In Sri Lanka, it is used in making masks for many traditional cultural activities. Pulp for paper, matchsticks, household utensils, agricultural implements and toys are some other products produced from mangroves (

<https://www.aims.gov.au/docs/projectnet/mangroves-uses.html>).

The importance of bark tannins has declined in many Asian countries, but mangrove tannin is still used in India and Bangladesh for leather curing and in Sri Lanka tannin is used traditionally in curing fishnets. The tannins comprise two groups of phenolic constituents, hydrolysable and condensed, which are important economically as agents for the synthesis of certain medicines. Their potential value as cytotoxic and/or antineoplastic agents and as antimicrobial agents has been demonstrated. Mangrove plants are rich sources of saponins, alkaloids and flavonoids. Plant saponins have been shown to have interesting biological activities such as spermicidal and molluscicidal activity. The extraction of natural chemical compounds, in addition to those already known to the pharmacopoeia of the people, continues to this day and among the latest additions are an array of substances from glues to alkaloids and saponins and many other substances of interest to

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modern industry and medicine. An alternative source of wealth in the mangroves is the exploitation of the fish, molluscs and crustaceans that abound in the mangrove areas (<https://www.aims.gov.au/docs/projectnet/mangroves-uses.html>).

2.3 Natural Dye Natural dyes are dyes or colorants derived from plants, invertebrates, or minerals. The majority of natural dyes are vegetable dyes from plant sources – roots, berries, bark, leaves, and wood and other organic sources such as fungi and lichens. Textile dyeing date back to the Neolithic period. Throughout history, people have dyed their textiles using common, locally available materials. Scarce dyestuffs that produced brilliant and permanent colors such as the natural invertebrate dyes Tyrian purple and crimson kermes were highly prized luxury items in the ancient and medieval world. Plant-based dyes such as woad, indigo, saffron, and madder were raised commercially and were important trade goods in the economies of Asia and Europe. Across Asia and Africa, patterned fabrics were produced using resist dyeing techniques to control the absorption of color in piece - dyed cloth. Dyes from the New World such as cochineal and logwood were brought to Europe by the Spanish treasure fleets, and the dyestuffs of Europe were carried by colonists to America .The discovery of man-made synthetic dyes late in the 19th century ended the large-scale market for natural dyes (Ashis Kumar Samanta, 2016).

2.4 Synthetic Dye The first human-made (synthetic) organic dye, mauveine was discovered serendipitously by William Henry Perkin in 1856. Many thousands of synthetic dyes have since

pharmacopoeia of the people, continues to this day and among the latest additions are an array of substances from glues to alkaloids and saponins and many other substances of interest to modern industry and medicine. An alternative source of wealth in the mangroves is the exploitation of the fish, molluscs and crustaceans that abound in

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been prepared. Synthetic dyes quickly replaced the traditional natural dyes. They cost less, they offered a vast range of new colors, and they imparted better properties to the dyed materials (<https://www.dyes-pigments.com/synthetic-dyes.html>).

2.5 Types of Dyes 2.5.1 Acid Dyes Acid dyes are water-soluble anionic dyes that are applied to fibers such as silk, wool, nylon and modified acrylic fibers using neutral to acid dye baths. Attachment to the fiber is attributed, at least partly, to salt formation between anionic groups in the dyes and cationic groups in the fiber. Acid dyes are not substantive to cellulosic fibers. Most synthetic food colors fall in this category.

2.5.2 Basic Dyes Basic dyes are water - soluble cationic dyes that are mainly applied to acrylic fibers, but find some use for wool and silk. Usually acetic acid is added to the dye bath to help the uptake of the dye onto the fiber. Basic dyes are also used in the coloration of paper (<http://en.wikipedia-org/wiki/dye>).

2.5.3 Direct Dyes Direct dyes is normally carried out in a neutral or slightly alkaline dye bath, at or near boiling point, with the addition of either sodium chloride (NaCl) or sodium sulfate (Na₂SO₄). Direct dyes are used on cotton, paper, leather, wool, silk and nylon. They are also used as pH indicators and as biological stains.

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perspiration. The choice of mordant is very important as different mordants can change the final color significantly. Most natural dyes are mordant dyes and there is therefore a large literature base describing dyeing techniques. The most important mordant dyes are the synthetic mordant dyes, or chrome dyes, used for wool; these comprise some 30% of dyes used for wool, and are especially useful for black and navy shades. The mordant, potassium dichromate, is applied as an after-treatment. It is important to note that many mordants, particularly those in the heavy metal category, can be hazardous to health and extreme care must be taken in using them (<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/dye>).

2.5.5 Vat Dyes Vat dyes are essentially insoluble in water and incapable of dyeing fibers directly. However, reduction in alkaline liquor produces the water soluble alkali metal salt of the dye, which, in this leuco form, has an affinity for the textile fiber. Subsequent oxidation reforms the original insoluble dye. The color of denim is due to indigo, the original vat dye.

2.5.6 Reactive Dyes Reactive dyes utilize a chromophore attached to a substituent that is capable of directly reacting with the fiber substrate. The covalent bonds that attach reactive dye to natural fibers make them among the most permanent of dyes. "Cold" reactive dyes, such as Procion MX, Cibacron F, and Drimarene K, are very easy to use because the dye can be applied at room temperature. Reactive dyes are by far the best choice for dyeing cotton and other cellulose fibers at home or in the art studio (<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/dye>).

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2.5.7 Disperse Dyes Disperse dyes were originally developed for the dyeing of cellulose acetate, and are water insoluble. The dyes are finely ground in the presence of a dispersing agent and sold as a paste, or spray-dried and sold as a powder. Their main use is to dye polyester but they can also be used to dye nylon, cellulose triacetate, and acrylic fibres. In some cases, a dyeing temperature of 130 °C is required, and a pressurized dyebath is used. The very fine particle size gives a large surface area that aids dissolution to allow uptake by the fibre. The dyeing rate can be significantly influenced by the choice of dispersing agent used during the grinding.

2.5.8 Azoic Dyes Azoic dyes is a technique in which an insoluble azo dye is produced directly onto or within the fiber. This is achieved by treating a fiber with both diazoic and coupling components. With suitable adjustment of dye bath conditions the two components react to produce the required insoluble azo dye. This technique of dyeing is unique controlled by the choice of the diazoic and coupling components. This method of dyeing cotton is declining in importance due to the toxic nature of the chemicals used.

2.5.9 Sulfur Dyes Sulfur dyes are two part "developed" dyes used to dye cotton with dark colors. The initial bath imparts a yellow or pale chartreuse color. This is after treated with a sulfur compound in place to produce the dark black we are familiar with in socks for instance. Sulfur Black 1 is the largest selling dye by volume (<http://en.wikipedia-org/wiki/dye>). 2.6 Classification

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of Natural Dyes Natural dyes can be defined as those colorants (dyes and pigments) obtained from animal or vegetable matter with no processing involved. For textile dyeing, the most commonly used are mordant dyes, although some belong to other groups (vat, solvent, pigment, direct and acid). Most of the historically important colorants are members of the anthraquinone, naphthoquinone, indigoid and carotenoid groups. There are no natural dyes of the sulphur, disperse, azoic or ingrain types. Natural dyes can be classified in various ways. Early methods of classification were based simply on the alphabetical arrangement of dyes. Later on, numerous other methods of classification were adopted, which are as follows:

- Classification based on chemical structure
- Classification based on their origin or the sources from which they are obtained
- Classification based on their methods of application
- Classification based on their color.

In the colour index, natural dyes are arranged and classified according to their chemical composition as well as their major applications. Natural dyes make up a separate section in the colour index, where they are arranged according to hue within their application category (Clark, 2011).

2.6.1 Classification Based on Chemical Structure Natural organic dyes and pigments belong to a wide range of chemical classes, such as indigoid, anthraquinonoids, naphthoquinones, polymethines, ketones, imines, quinones, flavones, flavanols, flavanones and chlorophyll. Some of the important chemical classes are represented in Table (2.1).

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the sources from which they are produced, natural dyes can be grouped into three distinct classes: those derived from vegetable sources; those derived from insect or other animal sources and those derived from mineral sources (Clark, 2011).

2.6.2.1 Dyes Derived from Vegetable Sources Vegetable dyes are obtained from various parts of plants and herbs including the stem, wood, roots, bark, leaves, flowers, fruits and skin of plants, which produce distinct pale to dark shades on both natural as well as synthetic fibres. Some important examples of dyes derived from plants or vegetables are logwood, turmeric, pine wood, catechu, madder, etc.

2.6.2.2 Dyes Derived from Insects or Animal Sources Some of the most important red dyes, based on the anthraquinone structure, are obtained from insects or animals. These dyes are characterized by good light fastness. They combine with metal salts to form metal-complex dyes, which possess good wash fastness. Examples of this type of dye are Lac, Kermes, Cochineal, Lichen, etc (Clark, 2011).

2.6.2.3 Dyes Derived from Mineral Sources Natural dyes produced from mineral resources include chrome yellow, chrome orange, chrome green, iron buff, Prussian blue, manganese brown, mineral khaki, etc. Mineral colors are not dyes but inorganic compounds, insoluble in water and precipitated onto the fiber by double decomposition. Certain important minerals widely used as natural dyes are Cinebor

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(Sangraj), Red Lead (Sindur), Laminated Red earth (Gem), Ultramarine (Lajerd), Zinc white (Sajeda), etc (Clark, 2011).

Table (2.1) Important Chemical Classes of Natural Dyes

Chemical Class	Natural dye source	Substrate	Colour produced
Indigoids	Indigo (<i>Indigofera tinctoria</i>)	Tyrian purple	(<i>Purplehoemastroma/ Murex brandaris</i>) Cotton, wool and silk
		Cotton, wool and silk	Blue

Blue purple/reddish purple	Anthraquinonoids	Madder (<i>Rubia tinctorium</i>)	
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Cochineal (<i>Coccus cacti</i>)	Wool and silk		
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Wool, silk and cotton (printing)	Pink, red crimson orange, brown		
	Crimson, scarlet and pink	Alphanaphthaquinones	Heena or lawsone (leaves of <i>Lawsonia inermis</i>)
	Juglone (shells of <i>Juglans regia</i>)	Wool and silk	Wool and silk
	Yellow to brown	Brown	
	Flavones	Weld (<i>Reseda luteola</i>)	Cotton, wool and silk
	Yellow, orange and olive	Dihydropyrans	Logwood (compeachy wood, <i>Haematoxylum campechianum</i>)
	Brazilwood (red wood species, <i>Caesalpinia echinat</i>)	Wool, silk, cotton and leather	

Wool, silk and cotton	Black		
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Crimson, black and purple	Anthocyanidins	Carajurin (leaves of <i>Bignonia chica</i>)	Cotton and silk
Orange			

Carotenoids	Annatto (<i>Bixa orellana</i>)		
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Classification based on chemical structure • Classification based on their origin or the sources from which they are obtained • Classification based on their methods of application • Classification based on their color. In the colour index, natural dyes are arranged and classified according to their chemical composition as well as their major applications. Natural dyes make up a separate section in the colour index, where they are arranged according to hue within their application category (Clark, 2011).

2.6.1 Classification Based on Chemical Structure Natural organic dyes and pigments belong to a wide range of chemical classes, such as indigoid, anthraquinonoids, naphthoquinones, polymethines, ketones, imines, quinones, flavones, flavanols, flavanones and chlorophyll. Some of the important chemical classes are represented in Table (2.1).

2.6.2 Classification According to Source Depending on their origin or the sources from which they are produced, natural dyes can be grouped into three distinct classes: those derived from vegetable sources; those derived from insect or other animal sources and those derived from mineral sources (Clark, 2011).

2.6.2.1 Dyes Derived from Vegetable Sources Vegetable dyes are obtained from various parts of plants and herbs including the stem, wood, roots, bark, leaves, flowers, fruits and skin of plants, which produce

10 distinct pale to dark shades on both natural as well as synthetic fibres. Some important examples of dyes derived from plants or vegetables are logwood, turmeric, pine wood, catechu,

Saffron (*Crocus sativus*) Wool and silk Wool and silk Yellow and orange Yellow (Clark, 2011).

2.6.3 Classification According to Method of Application According to this classification, natural dyes can be classified as either direct dyes or mordant dyes. Direct dyes may be further subdivided into: • Direct dyes for cotton, e.g. turmeric, pomegranate, annatto, safflower, etc. • Direct dyes for wool and silk, e.g. turmeric, pomegranate, annatto, safflower, etc. • Acid dyes, e.g. saffron • Basic dyes, e.g. Berberine. • Direct dyes for cotton can be applied to all natural textile fibres; acid dyes can generally only be applied to wool and silk; basic dyes can be used for wool and silk as well as tannic acid treated cotton. On the other hand, mordant dyes are equally suitable for both animal and vegetable fibres. Important mordant dyes include madder, logwood and cochineal. There is a further class of dyes known as vat dyes, which are insoluble in water. These include indigo, woad and tyrian purple (Clark, 2011).

2.6.4 Classification Based on Colour Natural dyes are frequently categorized on the basis of the colour that they impart to the fibre substrate.

2.6.4.1 Natural Yellow Dyes Yellow symbolizes growth and happiness and is perhaps the most abundant hue in nature. The number of plants that yield yellow dyes is much higher than the number that yield other colours, and the Colour Index lists a total of 28 natural yellow dyes. Yellow is of particular significance

madder, etc. 2.6.2.2 Dyes Derived from Insects or Animal Sources

Some of the most important red dyes, based on the anthraquinone structure, are obtained from insects or animals. These dyes are characterized by good light fastness. They combine with metal salts

to form metal-complex dyes, which possess good wash fastness. Examples of this type of dye are Lac, Kermes, Cochineal, Lichen, etc (Clark, 2011). 2.6.2.3 Dyes Derived from Mineral Sources Natural dyes produced from mineral resources include chrome yellow, chrome orange, chrome green, iron buff, Prussian blue, manganese brown, mineral khaki, etc. Mineral colors are not dyes but inorganic compounds, insoluble in water and precipitated onto the fiber by double decomposition. Certain important minerals widely used as natural dyes are Cinebor (Sangraj), Red Lead (Sindur), Laminated Red earth (Gem), Ultramarine (Lajerd), Zinc white (Sajeda), etc (Clark, 2011).

11 Table (2.1) Important Chemical Classes of Natural Dyes

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Indigoids	Indigo (<i>Indigofera tinctoria</i>)	Tyrian purple	(Purplehoemastroma/ <i>Murex brandaris</i>)
		Cotton, wool and silk	
		Cotton, wool and silk	Blue Blue purple/reddish purple
Anthraquinonoids	Madder (<i>Rubia tinctorium</i>)	Cochineal (<i>Coccus cacti</i>)	Wool and silk Wool, silk and cotton (printing)
			Pink, red crimson orange, brown Crimson, scarlet and pink
Alphanaphthaquinones	Heena or lawsone (leaves of <i>Lawsonia</i>		

in India, where it is still considered an auspicious colour with great religious significance.

2.6.4.2 Natural Red Dyes The Colour Index lists 32 natural red dyes: some are extracted from the roots or bark of plants, while others, such as cochineal, are camouflaged in the bodies dull grey insects. However, the sources of these dyes are limited. Throughout history, natural red dyes have been of significant and in some cases legendary importance. Almost all natural red dyes have a basic quinone structure. They are mainly comprised of anthraquinones (alizarin, purpurin, munjistin, laccaic, etc.) or naphthoquinones (alkannin and shikonin); there is also one benzoquinone dye (carthamin). Some of the prominent natural red dyes, as obtained from plant, animal and mineral sources (Clark, 2011).

2.6.4.3 Natural Blue Dyes The Colour Index lists only three natural blue dyes, namely natural indigo, sulphated natural indigo and the flowers of the Japanese *Tsuyukusa*, used mainly for paper making. The most brilliant and the fastest blue shades are obtained from indigo on all fibres. The principal coloring matter is indigotin, whose main sources are Indigo (*Indigofera tinctoria*) and woad (*Isatis tinctoria*).

2.6.4.4 Natural Brown Dyes The majority of natural brown dyes are obtained from quinone-based dyes, naphthoquinones and anthraquinones. Generally, copper and iron salts are used as mordants and they tend to turn the colour to dull and deep shades, particularly browns. This dye is a tannin-based flavonoid,

innermis) Juglone (shells of *Juglans regia*) Wool and silk Wool and silk Yellow to brown Brown Flavones Weld (*Reseda luteola*) Cotton, wool and silk Yellow, orange and olive Dihydropyrans Logwood (compeachy wood, *Haematoxylum campechianum*) Brazilwood (red wood species, *Caesalpinia echinat*) Wool, silk, cotton and leather Wool, silk and cotton Black Crimson, black and purple Anthocyanidins Carajurin (leaves of *Bignonia chica*) Cotton and silk Orange Carotenoids Annatto (*Bixa orellana*) Saffron (*Crocus sativus*) Wool and silk Wool and silk Yellow and orange Yellow (Clark, 2011).

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According to this classification, natural dyes can be classified as either direct dyes or mordant dyes. Direct dyes may be further subdivided into: ? Direct dyes for cotton, e.g. turmeric, pomegranate, annatto, safflower, etc. ? Direct dyes for wool and silk, e.g. turmeric, pomegranate, annatto, safflower, etc. ? Acid dyes, e.g. saffron ? Basic dyes, e.g. Berberine. ? Direct dyes for cotton can be applied to all natural textile fibres; acid dyes can generally only be applied to wool and silk; basic dyes can be used for wool and silk as well as tannic acid treated cotton. On the other hand, mordant dyes are equally suitable for both animal and vegetable fibres. Important mordant dyes include madder, logwood and cochineal. There is a further class of dyes known as vat dyes, which are insoluble in water. These include indigo, woad and tyrian purple (Clark, 2011). 2.6.4 Classification Based on Colour Natural dyes are frequently categorized on the basis of the colour that they impart to the fibre substrate. 2.6.4.1

and is derived from *Acacia catechu* and wild *Acacia arabica* (Clark, 2011).

2.7 Chemistry of Natural Dyes In plants the coloured pigments are normally present in the leaves, flowers, heart wood, bark and roots. These pigments can be extracted from the plant parts using suitable solvents depending on the chemical nature of the coloured constituents. The major divisions of natural chromogens that are or could be used in food materials and pharmaceuticals are listed below, along with examples of pigments and sources. 2.7.1 Anthracenes The two major groups of the anthracenes contain several well-known dyes. Anthraquinones (yellow, pink and red pigments) include *Morinda citrifolia* (Morindone), *Alkanna tinctoria* , *Dactylopius coccus* (cochineal) (carminic acid), etc. (Alizarin) (Ruberethric acid). Naphthoquinones (brown, pink or purple pigments) include *Juglans nigra*, *Juglans regia* (Juglone), *Lawsonia innermis* (Lawsone) (Clark, 2011).

2.7.2 Carotenoids These are a family of yellow and orange pigments found in most photosynthesizing organisms. Over 200 naturally occurring carotenoids have been identified but only a few are commercially available, including β -carotene, β -apo-8'-carotenal and canthaxanthin. The two major groups in the family are the carotenes (orange or red-orange) and the xanthophylls (yellow). β -carotene is the major carotenoid in algae and higher plants. Examples of carotenoids are *Christisonia bicolor* (Azafrin), *Careca papaya* fruits (anthera xanthin), *Bixa orellana* (Bixin), *Lillium hamsonii* (β -carotene).

Natural Yellow Dyes Yellow symbolizes growth and happiness and is

perhaps the most abundant hue in nature. The number of plants that yield yellow dyes

is much higher than the number that yield other colours, and the Colour Index lists a total of 28 natural yellow dyes. Yellow is of particular significance in India, where it is still considered an auspicious colour with great religious significance. 2.6.4.2

Natural Red Dyes The Colour Index lists 32 natural red dyes: some are extracted from the roots or bark of plants, while others, such as cochineal, are camouflaged in the bodies dull grey insects. However, the sources of these dyes are limited. Throughout history, natural red dyes have been of significant and in some cases legendary importance. Almost all natural red dyes have a basic quinone structure. They are mainly

13 comprised of anthraquinones (alizarin, purpurin, munjistin, laccaic, etc.) or naphthoquinones (alkannin and shikonin); there is also one benzoquinone dye (carthamin). Some of the prominent natural red dyes, as obtained from plant, animal and mineral sources (Clark, 2011). 2.6.4.3 Natural Blue Dyes The Colour Index lists only

three natural blue dyes, namely natural indigo, sulphated natural indigo and the flowers of the Japanese Tsuyukusa, used mainly for paper making.

2.7.3 Carotenes Carotene was first isolated as red crystals from carrots in 1831. It is closely related to vitamin A and generally occurs as a mixture of α -, - and γ -carotene in the ratio 15:85:0.1. Lycopene is the main colourant of tomatoes (Clark, 2011).

2.7.4 Xanthophylls These are oxygenated carotenes. Examples are Tagetes patula, Capsicum annum (red pigment) (Capsanthin), lutein (nettles, French marigolds), cis-bixin (annatto) and crocin (saffron). Annatto is used mainly for colouring dairy products and is derived from B. orellana. Saffron (C. sativus), whose main dye constituent is crocin, is a major colouring agent in use since Ancient Greece and Rome.

2.7.5 Betacyanins These red dyes, along with the related betaxanthins (yellows) were originally thought to be flavonoids; however, they differ in that they contain nitrogen and do not undergo the same reversible colour change as anthocyanins when exposed to different pH levels. They are glycosylated, like anthocyanins. They are reported to be present only in a few families of the Chenopodiaceae, such as the beet, portulacca and goosefoot families. Betanin is an extract from the red beet (Beta vulgaris), containing red and yellow pigments, which is used mainly as a food colouring. Betanin is the major component (95%) of the red pigments in the extract (Clark, 2011).

2.7.6 Flavins Flavins are very common in living organisms, riboflavin and two of its derivatives being the three most common. Their precise physiological role in the plant is unknown but it is thought that they may be involved as receptors of blue

The most brilliant and the fastest blue shades are obtained from indigo on all fibres. The principal coloring matter is indigotin, whose main sources are Indigo (*Indigofera tinctoria*) and woad (*Isatis tinctoria*). 2.6.4.4 Natural Brown Dyes The majority of natural brown dyes are obtained from quinone-based dyes, naphthoquinones and anthraquinones. Generally, copper and iron salts are used as mordants and they tend to turn the colour to dull and deep shades, particularly browns. This dye is a tannin-based flavonoid, and is derived from *Acacia catechu* and wild *Acacia arabica* (Clark, 2011). 2.7 Chemistry of Natural Dyes In plants the coloured pigments are normally present in the leaves, flowers, heart wood, bark and roots. These pigments can be extracted from the plant parts using suitable solvents depending on the chemical nature of the coloured constituents. The major divisions of natural chromogens that are or could be used in food materials and pharmaceuticals are listed below, along with examples of pigments and sources. 2.7.1 Anthracenes The two major groups of the anthracenes contain several well-known dyes. Anthraquinones (yellow, pink and red pigments) include *Morinda citrifolia* (Morindone), *Alkanna tinctoria*, *Dactylopius coccus* (cochineal) (carminic acid), etc. (Alizarin) (Ruberethric acid). Naphthoquinones (brown, pink or purple pigments) include *Juglans nigra*, *Juglans regia* (Juglone), *Lawsonia innermis* (Lawsone) (Clark, 2011).

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light and UV-A (the receptors for UV-B are unknown). Riboflavin (an alloxan adduct) is a yellow dye closely related to vitamin B₂, used for colouring food. This colourant can be synthesized.

2.7.7 Indigoid Dyes Examples of natural dyes containing indigoid are *Indigofera tinctoria*, *Wrightia tinctoria* and *Murex brandaris* (shellfish). The two most important dyes in this group are Tyrian purple, derived from the molluscs *Murex trunculus*, *M. brandaris* and *Purpura lapillus*, and Indigo. The main dye chemical in tyrian purple is 6,6'-dibromoindigo; the natural source is no longer used because of the large number of shellfish needed to produce even a small amount of the dye and because of the relative rarity of the shellfish. Indigo is known to be present in a small number of plants: indigo (*Indigofera* spp.), woad (*Isatis tinctoria* and other species), a Japanese knotweed (*Polygonum tinctoriu*). These plants contain the glucoside indican or isatan B, which is soluble in water and hydrolyzed to indoxyl in the dyeing process. Oxidation, usually by exposure to air, turns the indoxyl to indigotin (or indigo blue), which is insoluble in water, ether and alcohol. Other dyes such as indirubin and kaempferol may also be present in these plants. Most industry analysts believe that there will always be a comparatively high demand for indigo dyes, and they are the most important dyes in terms of volume (Clark, 2011).

2.7.8 Chlorophyll Pigments Chlorophyll is the major pigment used by plants for capturing light energy. A chlorophyll molecule consists of a porphyrin head (four pyrrole rings containing nitrogen arranged in a ring around a magnesium ion) and a long

few are commercially available, including β -carotene, β -apo-8'-carotenal and canthaxanthin. The two major groups in the family are the carotenes (orange or red-orange) and the xanthophylls (yellow). β -carotene is the major carotenoid in algae and higher plants. Examples of carotenoids are *Christisonia bicolor* (Azafrin), *Careca papaya* fruits (anthera xanthin), *Bixa orellana* (Bixin), *Lillium hamsonii* (β -carotene). 2.7.3 Carotenes Carotene was first isolated as red crystals from carrots in 1831. It is closely related to vitamin A and generally occurs as a mixture of α -, β - and γ -carotene in the ratio 15:85:0.1. Lycopene is the main colourant of tomatoes (Clark, 2011). 2.7.4 Xanthophylls These are oxygenated carotenes. Examples are *Tagetes patula*, *Capsicum annum* (red pigment) (Capsanthin), lutein (nettles, French marigolds), cis-bixin (annatto) and crocin (saffron). Annatto is used mainly for colouring dairy products and is derived from *B. orellana*. Saffron (*C. sativus*), whose main dye constituent is crocin, is a major colouring agent in use since Ancient Greece and Rome. 2.7.5 Betacyanins These red dyes, along with the related betaxanthins (yellows) were originally thought to be flavonoids; however, they differ in that they contain nitrogen and do not undergo the same reversible colour change as anthocyanins when exposed to different pH levels. They are glycosylated, like anthocyanins. They are reported to be present only in a few families of the *Chenopodiaceae*, such as the beet, portulacca and goosefoot families. Betanin is an extract from the red beet (*Beta vulgaris*), containing red and yellow pigments, which is used mainly as a food colouring. Betanin is the major

hydrocarbon tail. The hydrocarbon tail is lipid-soluble. There are four types of chlorophyll: chlorophyll a, found in all higher plants, algae and cyanobacteria; chlorophyll b, found in higher plants and green algae; chlorophyll c, found in diatoms, dinoflagellates and brown algae; and chlorophyll d, found only in red algae. The dye is extracted from natural sources (usually stinging nettle, spinach, alfalfa or corn) and used extensively in coloring inks, resins, soaps and waxes, edible fats, cosmetics, liniments, lotions, perfume, mouthwashes and leather. The dyestuff is known as C.I. Natural Green 3, C.I. Number 75810. It is very difficult to prepare pure chlorophyll chemically and the commercial product contains a mixture of chlorophylls a and b (in the ratio of 3:1) and several carotenoids. The commercial process for extracting chlorophyll from plant material involves many steps using solvents such as petroleum ether and acetone (Clark, 2011).

2.8 Chemical Compounds in Plants 2.8.1 Phenolic Compound The term phenolic compound embraces a wide range of plant substances which possess in common an aromatic ring bearing one or more hydroxyl substituents. Phenolic substances tend to be water-soluble, since they most frequently occur combined with sugar as glycosides and they are usually located in the cell vacuole. Among the natural phenolic compounds, of which over a thousand structures are known, the flavonoids form the largest group but simple monocyclic phenols, phenylpropanoids and phenolic quinones all exist in considerable numbers (Harbone, 1984). Several important groups of polymeric

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materials in plants the lignins, melanins and tannins are polyphenolic and occasional phenolic units are encountered in proteins, alkaloids and among the terpenoids. Phenolic compounds are all aromatic, so that they all show intense absorption in the UV region of the spectrum. In addition, phenolic compounds characteristically exhibit bathochromic shifts in their spectra in the presence of alkali. Spectral methods are, therefore, especially important for the identification and quantitative analysis of phenols (Harbone, 1984). Phenolic compounds represent the largest category of phytochemicals and are most widely distributed in the plant kingdom. Phenolics are hydroxyl group (-OH) containing class of chemical compounds where the (-OH) group is bonded directly to an aromatic hydrocarbon group. Phenol (C₆H₅OH) is considered the simplest class of this group of natural compounds (Deepak Koche, 2016). 2.8.2 Flavonoid The flavonoids are all structurally derived from the parent substance flavone. Flavonoids are mainly water soluble compounds. Flavonoids contain conjugated aromatic systems and thus show intense absorption bands in the UV and visible regions of the spectrum (Harbone, 1984). Flavonoids are the largest group of plant phenols and also the most studied one. They are polyphenolic compounds that are ubiquitous in nature and occur as a glycones, glucosides and methylated derivatives. More than 4,000 flavonoids have been recognized, many of which occur in vegetables, fruits and beverages like tea, coffee and fruit drinks (Pridham, 1960).

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2.8.3 Tannin Tannins occur widely in vascular plants, their occurrence in the angiosperms being particularly associated with woody tissues. By definition, they have the ability to react with protein, forming stable water insoluble co-polymers. Industrially, tannins are substances of plant origin which because of their ability to cross-link with protein are capable of transforming raw animal skins into leather (Harbone, 1984). Tannins are the most important ingredients in the dyeing with natural dyes producing yellow, brown, grey and black colours. They also modify the affinity of fibres towards different dyes. A back tanning process improves the wash fastness of some dyes. However, the treatment with tannins makes dyeings dull. Tannins are naturally occurring compounds of high molecular weight (about 500–3000) containing phenolic hydroxyl groups (Gulrajani, 2001). In the dyeing of textiles, tannins form the basis of 'so called' natural mordant. As stated above, tannins are phenolic compounds and those tannins, which have o-dihydroxy (catechol) groups can form metal chelates, giving different colour with different metals. An after – treatment with metal salts not only alters the light sorption characteristics of tannins but also makes them insoluble in water. Hence, they are fixed on the textile substrate, giving good washing fastness (Gulrajani, 2001).

2.8.4 Alkaloids Alkaloids are natural products that contain heterocyclic nitrogen atoms and are always basic in character. The name of alkaloids derives from the 'alkaline' nature and it was used to describe any nitrogen-containing base (Muller-

usually located in the cell vacuole. Among the natural phenolic compounds, of which over a thousand structures are known, the flavonoids form the largest group but simple monocyclic phenols, phenylpropanoids and phenolic quinones all exist in considerable numbers (Harbone, 1984). Several important groups of polymeric materials in plants the lignins, melanins and tannins are polyphenolic and occasional phenolic units are encountered in proteins, alkaloids and among the terpenoids. Phenolic compounds are all aromatic, so that they all show intense absorption in the UV region of the spectrum. In addition, phenolic compounds characteristically exhibit bathochromic shifts in their spectra in the presence of alkali. Spectral methods are, therefore, especially important for the identification and quantitative analysis of phenols (Harbone, 1984). Phenolic compounds represent the largest category of phytochemicals and are most widely distributed in the plant kingdom. Phenolics are hydroxyl group (-OH) containing class of chemical compounds where the (-OH) group is bonded directly to an aromatic hydrocarbon group. Phenol (C₆H₅OH) is considered the simplest class of this group of natural compounds (Deepak Koche, 2016).

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Harvey, 1999). Almost all the alkaloids have a bitter taste. The alkaloid quinine, for example, is one of the bitter tasting substances known and is significantly bitter (1×10^{-5}) at a molar concentration. Alkaloids are so numerous and involve such a variety of molecular structure that their rational classification is difficult. However, the best approach is to group them into families, depending on the type of heterocyclic ring system present in the molecule (Krishnan et al., 1983).

2.8.5 Polyphenol

Polyphenols constitute one of the most numerous and widely distributed groups of natural products in the plant kingdom. More than 8000 phenolic structures are currently known, and among them over 4000 flavonoids have been identified. Although polyphenols are chemically characterized as compounds with phenolic structural features, this group of natural products is highly diverse and contains several sub-groups of phenolic compounds. Fruits, vegetables, whole grains and other types of foods and beverages such as tea, chocolate and wine are rich sources of polyphenols. The diversity and wide distribution of polyphenols in plants have led to different ways of categorizing these naturally occurring compounds. Polyphenols have been classified by their source of origin, biological function, and chemical structure. Also, the majority of polyphenols in plants exist as glycosides with different sugar units and acylated sugars at different positions of the polyphenol skeletons (<http://www.mdpi.com/journal/nutrients>).

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2.8.6 Saponins Saponins have a high molecular weight and a high polarity and their isolation in a state of purity presents some difficulties. Such plants contain a high percentage of glycosides known as saponins which are characterized by their property of producing a frothing aqueous solution. As glycosides they are hydrolysed by acids to give an aglycone (sapogenin) and various sugars and related uronic acids. According to the structure of the aglycone or sapogenin, two kinds of saponin are recognized the steroidal and the pentacyclic triterpenoid types (Treace and Evans, 2009).

2.9 Mordants Natural dyes are either substantive, meaning that they do not require a mordant, or adjective, meaning that a mordant is required. Adjective dyes only dye materials which have been mordanted with a metallic salt or with the addition of a metallic salt to the dyebath itself. Examples of such dyes are logwood, madder, cochineal and fustic, among others. In their pure state, adjective dyes are generally only slightly coloured and produce poor results when used alone (Gupta, 1990). Mordants are chemicals in the form of metallic salts which are generally used to create an affinity between the fibre and the pigment. The main objective of the mordant when used with adjective dyes is to open up the pores so that the colourant can penetrate the fibres, thereby helping in the fixation of the dyestuffs on the substrate. However, mordants can also be used with dyes which may be applied directly. In this case their function is to form an insoluble compound with the dyestuff

heterocyclic nitrogen atoms and are always basic in character. The name of alkaloids derives from the 'alkaline' nature and it was used to describe any nitrogen-containing base (Muller-Harvey, 1999). Almost all the alkaloids have a bitter taste. The alkaloid quinine, for example, is one of the bitter tasting substances known and is significantly bitter (1×10^{-5}) at a molar concentration. Alkaloids are so numerous and involve such a variety of

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within the fibre itself, thereby improving the fastness properties of the dyed material (Gupta, 1990).

2.9.1 Types of Mordants There are three types of mordant, namely (i) Metallic salts or metallic mordants (ii) Tannins and tannic acid (iii) Oils or oil mordants.

2.9.1.1 Metallic Mordants Naturally occurring metal salts were once used as mordants in order to ensure reasonable fastness of color to sunlight and washing. Today, metal salts of aluminium, chromium, iron, copper and tin are also used. Some of the important metallic mordants are alum, potassium dichromate, ferrous sulphate, copper sulphate, stannous chloride and stannic chloride. Most natural dyes are able to form metal complexes and thereby produce different shades (hues). Therefore virtually all types of metal salts can in fact be used for this purpose. However, some restrictions on the use of metal salts were drawn up in the EC Control of Substances Hazardous to Health Act, 1989. The maximum permissible amounts of different metals in the final product are as follows (Patel, 2016).

2.9.1.2 Tannins and Tannic Acid Tannins are important in processes that use natural dyes producing yellow, brown, grey and black colours. They also improve the affinity of fibres to different dyes. Tannins are mainly used in the preservation of leather, glues, stains and mordants. Vegetable tannins are bitter and astringent substances that occur as excretions in the bark, leaves, fruits, galls, etc. of plants. These excretions may be used directly or in concentrated form. Tannins are naturally occurring

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phenolic compounds of high molecular weight (ranging from 500 to 3000). The phenolic hydroxyl group allows them to form effective cross-links between proteins and other macromolecules. Tannins which contain o-dihydroxy (Catechol) group can form chelates, which give different colours with different metals (Patel, 2016). 2.9.1.3 Oil Mordants Oil mordants are mainly used in dyeing processes using madder, producing Turkey red colour. The main object of the oil mordant is to form a complex with alum, which is used as the principal mordant. Alum is soluble in water and does not have affinity for cotton, so is easily washed out from the treated fabrics. The naturally occurring oils contain fatty acids such as palmitic, stearic, oleic and ricinoleic acid, and their glycerides. The $-COOH$ group of fatty acids react with metal salts and are converted into $-COOM$ (M denotes the metal; for example, in the case of alum salts, aluminium). It has also been found that when concentrated sulphonic acid is treated with oils, sulphonated oils are produced, which have better metal binding capacity than natural oils, due to the introduction of the sulphuric acid group $-SO_3H$. This can react with metal salts to produce $-SO_3M$. The bound metal can then form a complex with a mordant dye such as madder, producing a Turkey red colour with superior fastness and hue (Patel, 2016).

2.10 Application of Mordants to Textiles Metallic mordants are soluble in water and are only loosely held by cotton fibres. These mordants must therefore be precipitated onto the fabric by one of two methods: conversion of the mordants into insoluble form

compound with the dyestuff within the fibre itself, thereby improving the fastness properties of the dyed material (Gupta, 1990).

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Tannins are important in processes that use natural dyes producing yellow, brown, grey and black colours. They also improve the affinity of fibres to different dyes. Tannins are mainly used in the preservation of leather, glues, stains and mordants. Vegetable tannins are bitter and astringent substances that occur as

20 excretions in the bark, leaves, fruits, galls, etc. of plants. These excretions may be used directly or in concentrated form. Tannins are naturally occurring phenolic compounds of high

and treatment of the fibres with oil or tannic acid, followed by impregnation of the treated fabric with a mordant solution. In the latter method, the metallic mordants are fixed to the cotton by oil or tannic acid. Alum is a widely used mordant for cotton; the addition of an alkali to an alum solution produces aluminium sulphate, which is also used as a mordant, and is extensively used for dyeing of Turkey red colour on cotton. Copper salts are used in cotton dyeing as oxidizing agents for the production of cutch browns and logwood blacks. Copper sulphate is frequently employed in the dyeing of black shades on cotton and for this purpose it is generally fixed with the help of tannic acid. Tin mordants produce exceptionally brilliant colours. Wool is more receptive to natural dyes and mordants than cotton. It can absorb both acids and bases effectively due to its amphoteric nature. When treated with a metallic salt, wool hydrolyses the salt into an acidic and a basic component. The basic component is absorbed at the $-COOH$ groups while the acidic component is removed in the course of washing. Aluminium sulphate is quite effective as a mordant for wool and is sometimes used without the addition of other substances. Due to low cost and ease of application, the mordanting of wool with sodium or potassium dichromate is widely adopted as a technique. This provides full bright shades with fairly good fastness properties. The brightness of the shade can be further improved by addition of an organic acid such as formic, oxalic or tartaric acid. Ferrous sulphate is not very frequently used as a mordant for wool. Copper sulphate is used in conjunction with aluminium sulphate and ferrous sulphate in the dyeing of logwood blue and logwood

molecular weight (ranging from 500 to 3000). The phenolic hydroxyl group allows them to form effective cross-links between proteins and other macro-molecules. Tannins which contain o-dihydroxy (Catechol) group can form chelates, which give different colours with different metals (Patel, 2016). 2.9.1.3

Oil Mordants Oil mordants are

mainly used in dyeing processes using madder, producing Turkey

red colour. The main object of the oil mordant is to form a complex with alum,

which is

used as the principal mordant. Alum is soluble in water and does not have affinity for cotton, so is easily washed out from the treated

fabrics. The naturally occurring oils contain fatty acids such as palmitic, stearic, oleic

and ricinoleic acid, and their glycerides. The $-COOH$ group of fatty acids react with metal salts and are converted into $-COOM$ (M denotes the metal; for example, in the case of alum salts, aluminium). It has also been found that when concentrated sulphonic acid is treated with oils, sulphonated oils are produced,

black. Among the tin salts, stannous chloride is used as a mordant for wool. Silk possesses similar amphoteric properties to wool and can absorb both acids and bases. Alum is not a preferred mordant for silk since it diminishes its lustre and pliability. Iron salts are also used both for mordanting and weighing of silk, with excellent black colours produced on iron mordanted silk. Finally, stannous chloride is regarded as one of the most important mordants for silk and can also be used as a weighing agent (Patel, 2016).

2.11 Mordants Used in Natural Dyeing 2.11.1 Alum Potassium aluminum sulfate $KAl(SO_4)_2$ is the mordant most frequently used by dyers for protein (animal) and cellulose (plant) fibres and fabrics. It is commonly called alum. Alum is a white powder that is safe for hands and easy to use. Alum produces bright shades and gives relatively good light fastness. It is used in excess, alum will make wool feel stickly. If an aluminum pan is used it will contribute to the brightness of the color, but will not guarantee the color fastness. It is inexpensive and safe to use. This form of alum is refined from bauxite, the raw state of aluminum ore, and is free from the impurities (such as iron) some other alums may contain (<https://maiwahandprints.blogspot.com/2013/01/natural-dyes-mordants-part-1.html>).

2.11.2 Copper Sulphate Use copper sulphate $CuSO_4$, a beautiful blue color when dissolved in water. Copper darkness colors and gives a greenish cast. It provides good color-fastness and is not as hard on fibers as iron. A solid copper pot (if affordable) will make an excellent copper mordant (Kumar, 2015).

which have better metal binding capacity than natural oils, due to the introduction of the sulphuric acid group –

SO₃H. This can react with metal salts to produce –SO₃M. The bound metal can then form a complex with a mordant dye such as madder, producing a Turkey red colour with superior fastness and hue (Patel, 2016). 2.10 Application of Mordants to Textiles
Metallic mordants are soluble in water and are only loosely held by cotton fibres. These mordants must therefore be precipitated onto the fabric by one of two methods: conversion of the mordants into insoluble form and treatment of the fibres with oil or tannic acid, followed by impregnation of the treated fabric with a mordant solution. In the latter method, the metallic mordants are fixed to the cotton by oil or tannic acid. Alum is a widely used mordant for cotton; the addition of an alkali to an alum solution produces aluminium sulphate, which is also used as a mordant, and is extensively used for dyeing of Turkey red colour on cotton. Copper salts are used in cotton dyeing as oxidizing agents for the production of cutch browns and logwood blacks. Copper sulphate is frequently employed in the dyeing of black shades on

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2.12 Simple Methods of Dye Extraction Mostly natural dyes are obtained from various parts of plants like stems, flowers, roots etc. They are also extracted from minerals and dried bodies of insects. Some plants may have more than one color depending on which plant which is used for extraction. The extraction method of vegetable natural dyes basically depends on the method in which the dye is extracted. There are mainly four methods used in the extraction of natural dyes. 1. Aqueous method: The dyestuff is boiled at the temperature of 100°C in soft water and the dye solution obtained after boiling is filtered and the optical density is recorded. 2. Alkaline method: Initially 1 % alkaline solution is prepared by adding sodium carbonate or sodium hydroxide in water. The material is entered in it and boiled at 100°C. The dye solution is filtered and optical density is recorded. 3. Acidic method: Prepare 1% of an acidic solution by adding HCL in soft water. Enter the dye material and boil it at 100°C. Filter the dye solution and record the optical density. 4. Alcoholic method: By adding an equal amount of alcohol and water the alcoholic solution is prepared. The dye material is entered and boiling is carried at 100°C and the dye solution is filtered (<http://www.textilemates.com/natural-dye-importance>).

2.13 Extraction By extraction is meant the process of removing from a mixture, usually an aqueous solution, one or more substances by shaking with a liquid in which the substances to be removed are soluble (James F. Norris, 1924).

2.13.1 Extracting Using Aqueous Solution This type of extraction also known as the traditional/conventional method has been

acidic component is removed in the course of washing. Aluminium sulphate is quite effective as a mordant for wool and is sometimes used without the addition of other substances. Due to low cost and ease of application, the mordanting of wool with sodium or potassium dichromate is widely adopted as a technique. This provides full bright shades with fairly good fastness properties. The brightness of the shade can be further improved by addition of an organic acid such as formic, oxalic or tartaric acid. Ferrous sulphate is not very frequently used as a mordant for wool. Copper sulphate is used in conjunction with aluminium sulphate and ferrous sulphate in the dyeing of logwood blue and logwood black. Among the tin salts, stannous chloride is used as a mordant for wool. Silk possesses similar amphoteric properties to wool and can absorb both acids and bases. Alum is not a preferred mordant for silk since it diminishes its lustre and pliability. Iron salts are also used both for mordanting and weighing of silk, with excellent black colours produced on iron mordanted silk. Finally, stannous chloride is regarded as one of the most important mordants for silk and can also be used as a weighing agent (Patel, 2016).

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used to extract natural dyes from diverse sources. The main medium of extraction is water with or without addition of salt/acid/alcohol or alkaline. For optimal extraction conditions, the finely cut material or plant part is dissolved in measured quantity of water and extraction carried out under varying conditions such as extraction temperature, time, pH, material to liquid ratio, concentration of salt and mordant. In each case, the optical density or absorbance value of the aqueous extract can be evaluated using UV-Vis absorbance spectrophotometer, FT-IR and other chromatography measures (Agulei Karen Desta. 2016). The aqueous extraction under normal conditions is boiling either the dried or fresh samples from low temperatures to the boiling point of water, cooling the filtrate, filtering and storing it for further analysis. However, to optimize the extraction method of colour components in aqueous media, the sample/material is dried, finely cut, ground to powdered form, and finally extracted in water under a standard process. The extraction process of dye liquor is then carried out under varying condition such as extraction time, extraction temperature, pH of extraction liquor, concentration of colour/source material and material to liquor ratio (MLR). In each case, the optical density or absorbance value at a particular (maximum) absorbance wavelength for the aqueous extract of the natural dye material can be estimated using UV-Vis absorbance spectrophotometer. The continued usage of this technique has led to the optimization of extraction conditions of some natural dyes (Agulei Karen Desta. 2016).

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2.13.2 Solvent Extraction Flavonoids and anthocyanins are soluble in polar solvents with the glucosides and aglycones more soluble in water and alcohols respectively. These phenolics are commonly extracted from plant materials with water/alcohol or methanol/ethanol mixtures acidified with mineral acids to prevent the degradation of the non-acylated anthocyanin pigments. This method has been applied successfully in the extraction of a variety of organic compounds ranging from herbs to other plant material, as well as natural colourant from natural source dye materials. Literature relating to the extraction of natural dyes using solvent extraction technique includes 50% ethanol and methanol for the extraction of natural dye (Harborne, 1984). However due to the rigorous environmental regulations, Supercritical Fluid extraction (SCFE) technique has gained wide acceptance in recent years as an alternative to conventional solvent extraction for separation of organic compound in many analytical and industrial processes. This method has also been applied successfully in the extraction of organic compounds from herbs and other plant material as well as natural colourant from natural products. In another experimental carried out research to assess the dyeing and colouring potentials of ethanol extracts from the leaves. The leaves are collected, chopped, dried and ground to fine powder to allow most intimate contact with solvent (Agulei Karen Desta. 2016). Measured quantities of pulverized samples are then fed into the soxhlet extractor and mixed with absolute ethanol as the solvent in a ratio of 1:50 (powdered plant sample to ethanol solvent). The mixture of solvent-sample is refluxed for 3 hrs. The

solution is filtered and optical density is recorded. 3. Acidic method: Prepare 1% of an acidic solution by adding HCL in soft water. Enter the dye material and boil it at 100°C. Filter the dye solution and record the optical density. 4. Alcoholic method: By adding an equal amount of alcohol and water the alcoholic solution is prepared. The dye material is entered and boiling is carried at 100°C and the dye solution is filtered (<http://www.textilemates.com/natural-dye-importance>). 2.13 Extraction By extraction is meant the process of removing from a mixture, usually an aqueous solution, one or more substances by shaking with a liquid in which the substances to be removed are soluble (James F. Norris, 1924).

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extract phases generated through several operations of the extraction process are distilled to recover parts of the solvent before evaporating to dryness to obtain dried solid dye samples. The crude extracts are recrystallized using carbon tetrachloride as solvent and finally air dried to obtain purified dye samples. Apart from the mentioned techniques above, other methods of extraction of natural dyes include ultrasound-assisted extraction, supercritical fluid extraction, microwave-assisted extraction and enzymatic extraction. Although the methods of extraction of natural dyes are vast, aqueous method and solvent (using ethanol and methanol) extraction method are employed because of lack of equipment. These methods have also proven that they yield good fastness properties (Agulei Karen Desta. 2016).

2.14 Simple Distillation In a simple distillation, the distilling flask should be only one-third to one-half full of the liquid being distilled. With a flask that is too full, liquid can easily bump over into the condenser. If the flask is nearly empty, a substantial fraction of the material will be needed just to fill the flask and distilling head with vapor. When the desired liquid is dissolved in a large quantity of a solvent with a lower boiling point, the distillation should be interrupted after almost all of the solvent has been distilled and the higher-boiling liquids should be poured into a smaller distilling flask before continuing the distillation (Jerry R. Mohrig, 2010).

2.15 UV-Vis Spectrophotometry The hue and absorbance of the dye is determined using UV-Vis spectral scan of aqueous or non-aqueous extract/solution of the purified natural dye whose UV-

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zone and visible zone range from 190 to 700 nm or higher. The presence of dye along this range is indicated by peaks and troughs in different wave length. Peaks and troughs in visible zone indicate the main colour and absorption, while the UV-Zone with or without peaks, shows the property of the dye under UV-light which may be correlated with its fastness behavior. Various UV-Visible spectroscopic studies have been conducted by different scientists such as a number of UV-Vis spectral scan on a number of natural dyes namely madder, cochineal, neem, beet sugar and indigo using different solvents for extraction (Agulei Karen Desta. 2016).

2.16 Infrared (IR) Spectroscopy IR spectra may be measured on plant substances in an automatic recording IR spectrophotometer either in solution (in chloroform or carbon tetrachloride 0-5%), as a mull with nujol oil or in the solid state, mixed with potassium bromide. In the latter case, a thin disc is prepared under unhydrous conditions from a powder containing about 1mg of material and 10 to 100mg KBr, using a mould and press. The range of measurement is from 4000 to 667 cm^{-1} (or 2.5 to 15 μm) and the spectrum takes about three minutes to be recorded. The region in the IR spectrum above 1200 cm^{-1} shows spectral bands or peaks due to the vibrations of individual bonds or functional groups in the molecule under examination. The region below 1200 cm^{-1} shows bands due to the vibrations of the whole molecule and, because of its complexity, is known as the 'fingerprint' region. Intensities of the various bands are recorded subjectively on a simple scale as being either strong (S),

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medium (M) or weak (W). The fact that many functional groups can be identified by their characteristic vibration frequencies makes the IR spectrum the simplest and often the most reliable method of assigning a compound to its class. In spite of this, IR spectroscopy is most frequently used in phytochemical studies as a 'fingerprinting' device, for comparing a natural with a synthetic sample. The complexity of the IR spectrum lends itself particularly well to this purpose and such comparisons are very important in the complete identification of many types of plant constituent (Harbone, 1984). 2.17 Mercerization Mercerization refers to the treatment of cotton yarns or fabrics with caustic soda solution. Considerable quantities of cotton yarns and fabrics are mercerized to improve lustre and/or dye uptake and more recently without tension to produce stretch materials. Cotton fabrics are mercerized in grey or bleached condition or after boiling off in alkali. Grey mercerization is frequently practised to save on additional drying cost. The objective of mercerizing is to swell the cotton fibre, increasing its lustre, tensile strength, dimensional stability and dyeability. Traditionally, a cold solution of 25-26% by mass of sodium hydroxide is used, although better penetration and more even treatment is obtained with the more recent hot mercerizing technique. The time of impregnation is rarely sufficient for maximum swelling, so that even with the mercerization of bleached cotton, the addition of wetting agent is advantageous. Until recently, products based on cresylic acid (a mixture of o-, m- and p-cresols) were popular. Such products are toxic and non-biodegradable in nature (Graif, 1996).

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2.18 Methods of Mordanting Used in Dyeing with Natural Dyes
2.18.1 Pre-mordanting Pre-mordanting is a technique which involves primarily mordanting the fabric before dyeing i.e. the mordant is applied to the fabric prior to dyeing. It's the most common method of mordanting practiced on cotton, cellulosic and some animal fibers such as cochineal because these often in unmordanted form don't have affinity for many natural dyes. The advantage of this method is that the standing baths can be reused many times after replenishing with the mordants. This makes the process economical as well as reducing the pollution load hence sufficient for large-scale application. The procedures for mordanting are; (i) Dissolve the mordant and added to a dye bath containing ample amount of water. (ii) Add the substrate and bring the whole mixture to boil for a period of about $\frac{3}{4}$ of an hour. (iii) Cool the solution. (iv) Gently remove the substrate to ensure even take-up of the mordant. (v) Rinse the substrate to remove unfixed dyes, dry under room temperature and analyze. The fabric can afterwards be dyed (Saxena et al., 2014). 2.18.2 Post Mordanting In this method, the fabric after dyeing is treated with the mordant in a separate bath. The final colour is developed during the last phase. Iron salts are very often applied in this manner for producing grey and black colours. The procedures are as follows; (i) Dissolve mordant in ample amount of water. (ii) During simmering (after dyeing), add solution to dye bath in the final five to ten minutes. (iii) Cool solution, remove substrate. (iv) Rinse with cold water to remove unfixed dyes, dry and analysis (Saxena et al., 2014). 2.18.3 Simultaneous Mordanting As the name states, both the dyeing and

IR spectrophotometer either in solution (in chloroform or carbon tetrachloride 0-5%), as a mull with nujol oil or in the solid state, mixed with potassium bromide. In the latter case, a thin disc is prepared under anhydrous conditions from a powder containing about 1mg of material and 10 to 100mg KBr, using a mould and press. The range of measurement is from 4000 to 667 cm^{-1} (or 2.5 to 15 μm) and the spectrum takes about three minutes to be recorded. The region in the IR spectrum above 1200 cm^{-1} shows spectral bands or peaks due to the vibrations of individual bonds or functional groups in the molecule under examination. The region

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mordanting process is carried out in the same dye bath and at the same time. For cotton and other cellulose, the mordant is usually added to the dye bath at the start of dyeing so that both mordanting and dyeing processes take place concurrently. The procedures for this method are; (i) First dissolve mordant in a separate bath. (ii) Transfer mordant solution to the dye bath and add the wetted fabric. (iii) Bring whole mixture to boil while stirring at intervals using a stirring rod. (iv) Simmering until maximum dye uptake. (v) Cool solution, remove fabric, rinse with mild detergent, dry and analyze (Saxena et al., 2014).

2.19 Testing the Color Fastness of Dyed Materials The outstandingly important property of a dyed material is the fastness of the shade. The primary object of all fastness tests made on dyed materials is to determine whether they will give satisfaction in subsequent processing or ultimate use, so minimizing the possibility of complaints due to lack of fastness. Fastness tests may be divided into those of consumer significance, such as fastness to cross-dyeing, rubbing perspiration and salt-water staining, and those concerning only to the producer, such as fastness to cross-dyeing or unshrinkable treatments. Assessment of fastness is done by the use of Grey Scales which is possible to compare loss of colour or staining of any hue irrespective of depth (Lyle, 1977). 2.19.1 Grey Scale for Colour Change This scale consists of nine pairs of standard grey chips, each pair representing a difference in colour or contrast (shade and strength) corresponding to a numerical fastness rating. The results of colour fastness tests are rated by

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comparing the difference in colour of tested specimen and original fabric with the differences represented by the scale (Lyle, 1977).

Table (2.2) Signification of Colour Fastness to Washing and Rubbing

Fatness Rating	Properties	Degree of Alteration in Shade and Strength
5	Excellent	Negligible or no change
4	Good	Slightly changed
3	Fair	Noticeable changed
2	Poor	Considerably changed
1	Very Poor	Much changed

(Lyle, 1977).

2.19.2 Grey Scale for Staining This scale is used to evaluate undyed fabrics. The scale consists of one pair of white and nine pairs of grey and white colour chips each representing a visual difference in colour or contrast (shade and strength) corresponding to a numerical rating for staining. The staining of undyed cloth in colour fastness tests is rated by comparing the difference in colour of the stained and unstained cloth with the differences represented by the scale. A piece of an unstained fabric and the test specimen is placed in the same plane (oriented in the same direction) and the Grey Scale for staining is placed beside them under standard conditions of lighting. The visual difference between the original sample and test specimen is compared and the difference is noted as represented by the Grey Scale. The rating of the test specimen is the number on the

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procedures for mordanting are; (i) Dissolve the mordant and added to a dye bath containing ample amount of water. (ii) Add the substrate and bring the whole mixture to boil for a period of about $\frac{3}{4}$ of an hour. (iii) Cool the solution. (iv) Gently remove the substrate to ensure even take-up of the mordant. (v) Rinse the substrate to remove unfixed dyes, dry under room temperature and analyze. The fabric can afterwards be dyed (Saxena et al., 2014).

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Simultaneous Mordanting As the name states, both the dyeing

Grey Scale that corresponds to the contrast between the original and test specimens (Lyle, 1977).

2.19.3 Washing Fastness Consumers launder their fabric at some time in the lifespan of the textile. Change of colour or staining of another garment during laundering is generally immediately evident to the consumer and has a high impact on consumer satisfaction. Like light fastness testing there are a huge number of different iterations of the wash fastness test. The wide variety of test methods have mostly arisen due to the variety of washing methods available, cultural practices, the material being washed, and the end use of the product. The development of detergents and bleaches has influenced the development of new wash fastness test methods. It is important when selecting a wash fastness test method to choose one that best simulates the washing environment of the fabric's end use. If no end use has yet been selected then it is important to clearly label the level of wash fastness testing that has been conducted on the fabric. The most common washing methods in use today are dry cleaning, hand washing, gentle machine washing, machine washing, permanent press and industrial laundering. Each of these methods has one or more wash fastness tests to determine fabric colour suitability (Hurren, 2008).

2.19.4 Rubbing Fastness Rub fastness is of significant importance to prints, as the colour is provided by a pigment that is fixed to the exterior of the fibre. The pigment on the surface of the fabric is the first component to come under attack when a fabric is rubbed or abraded. Crocking is a simple method for

and mordanting process is carried out in the same dye bath and at the same time. For cotton and other cellulose, the

mordant is usually added to the dye bath at the start of dyeing so that both

mordanting and dyeing processes take place concurrently. The procedures for this method are; (i) First dissolve mordant in a separate bath. (ii) Transfer mordant solution to the dye bath and add the wetted fabric. (iii) Bring whole mixture to boil while stirring at intervals using a stirring rod. (iv) Simmering until maximum dye uptake. (v) Cool solution, remove fabric, rinse with mild detergent, dry and analyze (Saxena et al., 2014).

2.19 Testing the Color Fastness of Dyed Materials The outstandingly important property of a dyed material is the fastness of the shade. The primary object of all fastness tests made on dyed materials is to determine whether they will give satisfaction in subsequent processing or ultimate use, so minimizing the possibility of complaints due to lack of fastness. Fastness tests may be divided into those of consumer significance, such as fastness to cross-dyeing, rubbing perspiration and salt-water staining, and those concerning only to the producer, such as fastness to cross-dyeing or unshrinkable treatments. Assessment of fastness is done by the use of Grey Scales which is possible to compare loss of colour or staining of any hue irrespective of depth (Lyle, 1977).

28 2.19.1 Grey Scale for Colour Change This

determining fastness to rubbing. The standard 10 cycles employed in the crocking test may not be enough to break down a faulty pigment binder system, so some rub fastness test methods involve an increased number of rubbing cycles. There are test methods and testing equipment developed that have an increased abrasive effect on the fabric surface. These include oscillating drum, wire mesh and emery abrasion testers. Each of these testers abrades the surface more than the crock meter and they are used for textiles that require high resistance to abrasion such as military fabrics. After rub fastness testing the rubbed surface is often appraised for colour change or frosting. Frosting is common in prints and is the pigment rubbing away from the surface of the fabric exposing the natural fibre colour below. This can also be called fibrillation, as single fibres poke through the surface of the print. Frosting is easily identified in a loss of depth of shade of the print (Hurren, 2008).

CHAPTER III 3. MATERIALS AND METHODS 3.1 Sources of Raw Materials In this research work, mangrove barks were collected from Bogale Township in Ayeyarwady Region. 95% ethanol, alum, copper (II) sulphate, sulphuric acid, hydrochloric acid, magnesium ribbon, ferric chloride, potassium ferric cyanide, vinegar, sodium hydroxide were purchased from Academy Chemical Group, No. 101, 28th St, Pabedan Township, Yangon Region. Glasswares were obtained from Department of Industrial Chemistry Laboratory, Dagon University.

3.2 Preparation of Mangrove Bark Powder Before extraction of the natural dyestuff, the pieces of mangrove stem were cleaned

scale consists of nine pairs of standard grey chips, each pair representing a difference

in colour or contrast (shade and strength) corresponding to a numerical fastness rating.

The results of colour fastness tests are rated by comparing the difference in colour of tested specimen and original fabric with the differences represented by the scale (

Lyle, 1977). Table (2.2) Signification of Colour Fastness to Washing and Rubbing Fatness Rating Properties Degree of Alteration in Shade and Strength 5 Excellent Negligible or no change 4 Good Slightly changed 3 Fair Noticeable changed 2 Poor Considerably changed 1 Very Poor Much changed (Lyle, 1977). 2.19.2 Grey Scale for Staining This scale is used to evaluate undyed fabrics. The scale consists of one pair of white and nine pairs of grey and white colour chips each representing a visual difference in colour or contrast (shade and strength) corresponding to a numerical rating for staining. The staining of undyed cloth in

colour fastness tests is rated by comparing the difference in colour of the stained and unstained cloth with the differences represented by the scale.

A piece of an unstained fabric and the test specimen is placed in the same plane (oriented in the same direction) and the Grey

with water by brushing to remove the adhering dirt and soil. Then, the pieces of mangrove stem were cut with knife to debark and they were dried at room temperature and then cut into small pieces. The pieces were ground in a grinder and powdered samples were screened by passing through Tyler screen of (-100) mesh size and stored in plastic bags for further works.

3.3 Phytochemical Tests on the Bark of Mangrove Powder Before the extraction of natural dyestuff, phytochemical investigation was carried out to study the main compounds which are present or absent in the mangrove bark. The experiment was conducted according to the procedures mentioned in "A Guide to Modern Techniques of Plant Analysis" (Harbone, 1984). The detailed methods for preparation of reagent solution are shown in Appendix. The results of phytochemical investigation of mangrove bark powder are shown in Table (4.1).

3.3.1 Test for Phenolic Compounds Mangrove bark powder 0.2 g was mixed with distilled water and added a few drops of 1% FeCl₃. If violet color appeared, phenolic compounds were present.

3.3.2 Test for Tannins Mangrove bark powder 0.2 g and distilled water was added into a test tube. Then, the mixture was heated for 5 minutes and filtered. The filtrate was treated with 2 drops of 1% FeCl₃ solution. If deep blue precipitate appeared in the test tube, it can be noted that tannins was present in it.

Scale for staining is placed beside them under standard conditions of lighting. The visual difference between the original

29 sample and test specimen is compared and the difference is noted as represented by the Grey Scale. The rating of the test specimen is the number on the Grey Scale that corresponds to the contrast between the original and test specimens (Lyle, 1977). 2.19.3 Washing Fastness Consumers launder their fabric at some time in the lifespan of the textile. Change of colour or staining of another garment during laundering is generally immediately evident to the consumer and has a high impact on consumer satisfaction. Like light fastness testing there are a huge number of different iterations of the wash fastness test. The wide variety of test methods have mostly arisen due to the variety of washing methods available, cultural practices, the material being washed, and the end use of the product. The development of detergents and bleaches has influenced the development of new wash fastness test methods. It is important when selecting a wash fastness test method to choose one that best simulates the washing environment of the fabric's end use. If no end use has yet been selected then it is important to clearly label the level of wash fastness testing that has been conducted on the fabric. The most common washing methods in use today are dry cleaning, hand washing, gentle machine washing, machine washing, permanent press and industrial laundering. Each of these methods has one or more wash fastness tests to determine fabric colour suitability (Hurren, 2008). 2.19.4 Rubbing Fastness Rub fastness is of significant importance to

3.3.3 Test for Flavonoids Mangrove bark powder 0.2 g was treated with 5 ml of 95% ethanol solution. The solution was warmed and metal magnesium was added. To this solution, 5-6 drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid was added. A pink color indicates the presence of flavonoids.

3.3.4 Test for Saponins Distilled water 5 ml was added to bark powder 0.2 g and the test tube was vigorously shaken for a few minutes. If frothing takes place in the test tube, saponins were present in it.

3.3.5 Test for Alkaloids Mangrove bark powder 0.2 g was boiled with 5 ml of 1% HCl for 5 min, then allowed to cool and filtered. The filtrate was tested with Dragendorff's reagent, an orange precipitate was formed.

3.3.6 Test for Polyphenols Mangrove bark powder 0.2 g was mixed with 5ml of 95% ethanol and filtered. The filtrate was treated with 5 drops of the mixture of 1% FeCl₃ and 1% K₃Fe(CN)₆ solution. Greenish blue color was formed, it indicates the presence of polyphenols.

3.4 Extraction of the Dye from Mangrove Bark Powder Using Water 3.4.1 Procedure Mangrove bark powder 2.5 g and 250 ml of water were boiled in a stainless steel pot and heated at 80 °C for 45 min. Then the extracted dye solution was cooled and then filtered. 1ml of extracted dye solution was diluted in 9 ml of distilled water. An aliquot was introduced in a quart cell and analyzed in a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Model-UV mini-1240,

prints, as the colour is provided by a pigment that is fixed to the exterior of the fibre. The pigment on the surface of the fabric is the first component to come under attack when a fabric is rubbed or abraded. Crocking is a simple method for determining fastness to rubbing. The standard 10 cycles employed in the crocking test may not be enough to break down a faulty pigment binder system, so some rub fastness test methods involve an increased number of rubbing cycles. There are test methods and testing equipment developed that have an increased abrasive effect on the fabric surface. These include oscillating drum, wire mesh and emery abrasion testers. Each of these testers abrades the surface more than the crock meter and they are used for textiles that require high resistance to abrasion such as military fabrics.

30 After rub fastness testing the rubbed surface is often appraised for colour change or frosting. Frosting is common in prints and is the pigment rubbing away from the surface of the fabric exposing the natural fibre colour below. This can also be called fibrillation, as single fibres poke through the surface of the print. Frosting is easily identified in a loss of depth of shade of the print (Hurren, 2008).

31 CHAPTER III 3. MATERIALS AND METHODS 3.1 Sources of Raw Materials In this research work, mangrove barks were collected from Bogale Township in Ayeyarwady Region. 95% ethanol, alum, copper (II) sulphate, sulphuric acid, hydrochloric acid, magnesium ribbon, ferric chloride, potassium ferric cyanide, vinegar, sodium hydroxide were purchased from Academy

Shimadzu Corporation, Japan). A scan from 470 to 560 nm was performed in order to generate the characteristics absorption spectra of the sample. The maximum absorbance value (optical density) was detected at 482 nm. 3.4.1.1 Effect of Extraction Time on the Concentration of Dye Solution The same procedure mentioned in Section (3.4.1) was conducted by using different extraction time such as 15, 30, 60 and 75 min respectively. The extraction temperature and material to solvent ratios were kept at constant. 1 ml of each of the aliquots was diluted in 9 ml of distilled water and the optical density was measured at 482 nm. The suitable extraction time was determined based on highest value of optical density and the concentration of dye solution was calculated. The results are shown in Table (4.4). 3.4.1.2 Effect of Extraction Temperature on the Concentration of Dye Solution The same procedure mentioned in Section (3.4.1) was conducted by using different extraction temperature 50, 60, 70 and 90°C respectively. The extraction time and material to solvent ratios were kept at constant. The extraction time and 1 ml of each of the aliquots was diluted in 9 ml of distilled water and the optical density was measured at 482 nm. The suitable extraction temperature was determined based on highest value of optical density and the concentration of dye solution was calculated and the results are shown in Table (4.5).

3.4.1.3 Effect of Material to Solvent Ratio on the Concentration of Dye Solution The same procedure mentioned in Section (3.4.1) was conducted by using different material to solvent ratio 1, 1.5, 2 and 3 g respectively. The extraction time and temperature

Chemical Group, No. 101, 28 th St, Pabedan Township, Yangon Region. Glasswares were obtained from Department of Industrial Chemistry Laboratory, Dagon University. 3.2 Preparation of Mangrove Bark Powder Before extraction of the natural dyestuff, the pieces of mangrove stem were cleaned with water by brushing to remove the adhering dirt and soil. Then, the pieces of mangrove stem were cut with knife to debark and they were dried at room temperature and then cut into small pieces. The pieces were ground in a grinder and powered samples were screened by passing through Tyler screen of (-100) mesh size and stored in plastic bags for further works. 3.3 Phytochemical Tests on the Bark of Mangrove Powder Before the extraction of natural dyestuff, phytochemical investigation was carried out to study the main compounds which are present or absent in the mangrove bark. The experiment was conducted according to the procedures mentioned in "A Guide to Modern Techniques of Plant Analysis" (Harbone, 1984). The detailed methods for preparation of reagent solution are shown in Appendix. The results of phytochemical investigation of mangrove bark powder are shown in Table (4.1). 3.3.1 Test for Phenolic Compounds Mangrove bark powder 0.2 g was mixed with distilled water and added a few drops of 1% FeCl₃. If violet color appeared, phenolic compounds were present. 3.3.2 Test for Tannins Mangrove bark powder 0.2 g and distilled water was added into a test tube. Then, the mixture was heated for 5 minutes and filtered. The filtrate was treated with 2

were kept at constant. 1 ml of each of the aliquots was diluted in 9 ml of distilled water and the optical density was measured at 482 nm. The suitable material to liquor ratio was determined based on highest value of optical density and the concentration of dye solution was calculated and the results are shown in Table (4.6).

3.4.2 Identification of the Compounds in the Extracted Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Using Water by FT-IR Spectrophotometer The chemical characteristic profiles and identification of functional groups associated to its specific colour of the extracted dye powder was determined by Perlin Elmer GX FT-IR spectrophotometer. The results are shown in Tables (4.2).

3.4.3 Dyeing Process of Cotton Fabrics Using Dye Powder Extracted with Water 3.4.3.1 Dyeing Procedure Mercerization of Cotton Fabrics Firstly, 3 g of caustic soda was dissolved in 1 L of warm water before adding to the cotton fabrics. To prepare mercerized cotton fabrics, 1 yard of cotton fabrics were simmered in caustic soda solution for 30 min and rinsed with water. After completion of this step, the cotton fabrics were put into vinegar solution (4 ml acetic acid to 1 L of water) for 30 min to neutralize it. To prepare clean cotton fabrics, the cotton fabrics were rinsed with water and then dried at room temperature. After that, the cotton fabrics were tested with a few drops of iodine. The cotton fabrics were cleaned if purple black color did not appear.

32 drops of 1% FeCl₃ solution. If deep blue precipitate appeared in the test tube, it can be noted that tannins was present in it.

3.3.3 Test for Flavonoids Mangrove bark powder 0.2 g was treated with 5 ml of 95% ethanol solution. The solution was warmed and metal magnesium was added. To this solution, 5-6 drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid was added. A pink color indicates the presence of flavonoids. 3.3.4 Test for Saponins Distilled water 5 ml was added to bark powder 0.2 g and the test tube was vigorously shaken for a few minutes. If frothing takes place in the test tube, saponins were present in it. 3.3.5 Test for Alkaloids Mangrove bark powder 0.2 g was boiled with 5 ml of 1% HCl for 5 min, then allowed to cool and filtered. The filtrate was tested with Dragendorff's reagent, an orange precipitate was formed. 3.3.6 Test for Polyphenols Mangrove bark powder 0.2 g was mixed with 5ml of 95% ethanol and filtered. The filtrate was treated with 5 drops of the mixture of 1% FeCl₃ and 1% K₃Fe(CN)₆ solution. Greenish blue color was formed, it indicates the presence of

polyphenols. 3.4 Extraction of the Dye from Mangrove Bark Powder Using Water 3.4.1 Procedure

Mangrove bark powder 2.5 g

and 250 ml of water were boiled in a stainless steel pot and heated at 80°C for 45 min.

Then the extracted dye solution was cooled and then filtered. 1ml of extracted dye solution was diluted in 9 ml of distilled

Pre-Mordanting of Cotton Fabrics In this method, mordant solution was prepared by heating 1 g of alum with 200 ml of water. This solution was heated to a temperature of 80°C and 25cm 25cm of cleaned cotton fabric was simmered in solution for about 30 min. During mordanting, the fabric was frequently stirred with a glass rod to obtain good penetration of mordant into the cotton fabric. After that, mordant solution was removed and the mordanted cotton fabric was rinsed with water. The above experiment was also carried out with 0.2 g of copper (II) sulphate as mordant to obtain the mordanted cotton fabrics.

Dyeing of Mordanted Cotton Fabrics Dye powder 0.5 g and 200 ml of water were added in the stainless steel pot and heated at 60°C and then the mordanted fabric was simmered in this solution for 45 min. Then the fabric was rinsed with water and allowed to air drying.

3.4.3.2 Effect of Dyeing Temperature on Color Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Pre-mordanting Method The experimental work in this section was based on the procedure mentioned in Section (3.4.3.1). In order to ascertain the effect of dyeing temperature, the same weight of 0.5 g sample and 200 ml of water were used with different dyeing temperature of 50, 70, 80 and 90°C. The dyeing time was 45 min. The results are shown in Tables (4.7) and (4.9).

3.4.3.3 Effect of Dyeing Time on Color Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Pre-mordanting Method The experimental work in this section was based on the procedure mentioned in Section

water. An aliquot was introduced in a quart cell and analyzed in a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Model-UV mini-1240, Shimadzu Corporation, Japan). A scan from 470 to 560 nm was performed in order to generate the characteristics absorption spectra of the sample. The maximum absorbance value (optical density) was detected at 482 nm.

3.4.1.1

Effect of Extraction Time on the Concentration of Dye Solution

The same procedure mentioned in Section (3.4.1) was conducted by using different extraction time such as 15, 30, 60 and 75 min respectively. The extraction temperature and material to solvent ratios were kept at constant. 1 ml of each of the aliquots was diluted in 9 ml of distilled water and the optical density was measured at 482 nm. The suitable extraction time was determined based on highest value of optical density and

the concentration of dye solution was calculated. The results are shown in Table (4.4). 3.4.1.2 Effect of Extraction Temperature on the Concentration of Dye Solution

The same procedure mentioned in Section (3.4.1) was conducted by using different extraction temperature 50, 60, 70 and 90 °C respectively. The extraction time and material to solvent ratios were kept at constant. The extraction time and 1 ml of each of the aliquots was diluted in 9 ml of distilled water and the optical density was measured at 482 nm. The suitable extraction

(3.4.3.1). In order to ascertain the effect of dyeing time, the same weight of 0.5 g sample and 200 ml of water were used with different dyeing time of 30, 60, 75 and 90 min. The dyeing temperature was 60 °C. The results are shown in Tables (4.8) and (4.10).

3.4.4 Testing the Color Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics 3.4.4.1

Fastness to Washing In this case, Launder Meter washing machine (Model No. L-4) containing 4-rack test bottle was used. The operation was carried out with Test No.3 of ISO 105. The required soap solution was prepared with (5 g) of soap per liter and (2 g) of soda per liter. The dye fabric of (10cm 10cm) was cut out. The cotton and polyester/ cotton blend fabric were used as adjacent fabrics. The specimen to be tested was placed between the two pieces of adjacent fabrics. The specimens were sewn along each side to form a composite specimen. The composite specimen was placed in the wash pot of the machine and soap solution was added. The steel cover was closed and the soap solution was heated to a temperature of $60 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. After that the composite specimen was tested at $60 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for 30minutes. At the end of operation, the specimen was lifted from the pot and rinsed thoroughly. The stitching of the composite specimen was broken but the fabric must contact at the line of stitching on two corners. Finally, the specimens were dried at room temperature. The change in color of the specimen was assessed by comparing with the original dyed fabrics and the rating is defined by using Grey Scale for color change. The staining of the white cotton fabric was also assessed by Grey Scale for staining. The degree

temperature was determined based on highest value of optical density and the concentration of dye solution was calculated and the results are shown in Table (4.5). 3.4.1.3

Effect of Material to Solvent Ratio on the Concentration of Dye Solution

The same procedure mentioned in Section (3.4.1) was conducted by using different material to solvent ratio 1, 1.5, 2 and 3 g respectively. The extraction time and temperature were kept at constant. 1 ml of each of the aliquots was diluted in 9 ml of distilled water and the optical density was measured at 482 nm. The suitable material to liquor ratio was determined based on highest value of optical density and the concentration of dye solution was calculated and the results are shown in Table (4.6).

3.4.2

Identification of the Compounds in the Extracted Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Using Water by FT-IR Spectrophotometer

The chemical characteristic profiles and identification of functional groups associated to its specific colour of the extracted dye powder was determined by Perlin Elmer GX FT-IR spectrophotometer. The results are shown in Tables (4.2).

34 3.4.3

Dyeing Process of Cotton Fabrics Using Dye Powder Extracted with Water 3.4.3.1 Dyeing Procedure Mercerization

of fastness rating of dyed cotton fabrics were determined by using Grey Scale and the results are shown in Table (4.7) to (4.10) and Fig (4.3) to (4.6).

3.4.4.2 Fastness to Rubbing The rubbing fastness of dyed fabric was determined by JIS STDL-0241 Rubbing Tester Machine. The test specimen (25cm 5cm) and a piece of white bleached cotton fabric about 5 cm were cut parallel to wrap direction for rubbing fastness test. In rubbing fastness test, the test specimen was mounted on the white bleached cotton cloth and placed on the rubbing tester. The rubbing distance was 100 mm. The test specimen was rubbed 100times with (500 g) load at the speed of 30 circles per minute. The white bleached cotton cloth and the test specimen were rubbed together on the tester by the aid of motor. Six different materials were tested simultaneously on the machine. In this study, both dry and wet rubbing fastness tests were carried out. In rubbing fastness test, the rubbed cotton fabric was wetted with water and the amount of water was two times of the fabric weight. The fabric was finally dried at room temperature. The color stained on bleached cotton fabrics were compared by Grey Scale for staining and the degree of fastness rating was determined. The degree of fastness rating of dyed cotton fabrics were determined by using Grey Scale and the results are shown in Table (4.7) to (4.10) and Fig (4.3) to (4.6).

3.5 Extraction of the Dye from Mangrove Bark Powder Using 95% Ethanol-Water Mixture 3.5.1 Procedure Mangrove bark powder 2.5 g was added in 2-neck round bottom flask. 65 ml of 95% ethanol and 185 ml of water (1:3) were added into the flask. The

of

Cotton Fabrics Firstly, 3 g of caustic soda was dissolved in 1 L of warm water before adding to the cotton fabrics.

To prepare mercerized cotton fabrics, 1 yard of cotton fabrics were simmered in caustic soda solution for 30 min and rinsed with water. After completion of this step, the cotton fabrics were put into vinegar solution (4 ml acetic acid to 1 L of water) for 30 min to neutralize it.

To prepare clean cotton fabrics, the cotton fabrics were rinsed with water and then dried at room temperature. After that, the cotton fabrics were tested with a few drops of iodine. The cotton fabrics were cleaned if purple black color did not appear. Pre-Mordanting of Cotton Fabrics In this method, mordant solution was prepared by heating 1 g of alum with 200 ml of water.

This solution was heated to a temperature of 80°C and 25cm² of cleaned cotton fabric was simmered in solution for about 30 min. During mordanting, the fabric was frequently stirred with a glass rod

to obtain good penetration of mordant into the cotton fabric. After that, mordant solution was removed and the mordanted cotton fabric was rinsed with water.

The above experiment was also carried out with 0.2

round bottomed flask was fitted with condenser. Then, the extraction was carried out at 70°C for 90 min. After extraction, the extracted dye solution was cooled and filtered. 1 ml of extracted dye solution was diluted in 9 ml of distilled water. An aliquot was introduced in a quart cell and analyzed in a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Model-UV mini-1240, Shimadzu Corporation, Japan). The maximum absorbance value (optical density) was detected at 482 nm.

3.5.1.1 Effect of Ethanol -Water Ratio on the Concentration of Dye Solution The same procedure as mentioned in Section (3.5.1) was conducted by varying the ethanol and water ratio in the range of 1:1, 1:2, 1:4 and 1:5 respectively. The absorbance value of natural dye solution was determined by the same procedure as mentioned in Section (3.5.1) and the results are shown in Table (4.11).

3.5.1.2 Effect of Extraction Time on the Concentration of Dye Solution The same procedure as mentioned in Section (3.5.1) was conducted by using different extraction time such as 30, 60, 120 and 150 min respectively and the ethanol: water ratio was (1:3). The absorbance value of natural dye solution was determined by the same procedure as mentioned in Section (3.5.1) and the results are shown in Table (4.12).

3.5.1.3 Effect of Extraction Temperature on the Concentration of Dye Solution The same procedure as mentioned in Section (3.5.1) was conducted by using different extraction temperature such

g of copper (II) sulphate as mordant to obtain the mordanted cotton fabrics. Dyeing of Mordanted Cotton Fabrics Dye powder 0.5 g and 200 ml of water were added in the stainless steel pot and heated at 60 °C

and then the mordanted fabric was simmered in this solution for 45 min. Then the fabric was rinsed with water and allowed to air drying. 3.4.3.2

Effect of Dyeing Temperature on Color Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Pre-mordanting Method

The experimental work in this section was based on the procedure mentioned in Section (3.4.3.1). In order to ascertain the effect of dyeing temperature, the same weight of 0.5 g sample and 200 ml of water were used with different dyeing

35 temperature of 50, 70, 80 and 90 °C. The dyeing time was 45 min. The results are shown in Tables (4.7) and (4.9). 3.4.3.3

Effect of Dyeing Time on Color Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Pre-mordanting Method

The

experimental work in this section was based on the procedure mentioned in Section (3.4.3.1). In order to ascertain the effect of dyeing time, the same weight of 0.5 g sample and 200 ml of water were used with different dyeing time of 30, 60, 75 and 90

as 50, 60, 80 and 90 °C respectively and the extraction time for 90 min. The absorbance value of natural dye solution was determined by the same procedure as mentioned in Section (3.5.1) and the results are shown in Table (4.13).

3.5.2 Identification of the Compounds in the Extracted Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Using 95% Ethanol-Water Mixture by FT-IR Spectrophotometer The chemical characteristic profiles and identification of functional groups associated to its specific colour of the extracted dye powder was determined by Perlin Elmer GX FT-IR spectrophotometer. The results are shown in Tables (4.3).

3.5.3 Dyeing Process of Cotton Fabrics Using Dye Powder Extracted with 95% Ethanol-Water Mixture 3.5.3.1 Dyeing Procedure Mercerization of Cotton Fabrics Cotton fabrics were mercerized according to the same procedure as mentioned in Section (3.4.3.1).

Pre-mordanting Method Mordanting of Cotton Fabrics Mercerized cotton fabrics were mordanted according to the same procedure as mentioned in Section (3.4.3.1). Dyeing of Mordanted Cotton Fabrics Mordanted cotton fabrics were dyed according to the same procedure as mentioned in Section (3.4.3.1).

3.5.3.2 Effect of Dyeing Temperature on Color Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Pre-mordanting Method The procedure of dyeing of mordanted cotton fabric was used as mentioned in

min. The dyeing temperature was 60°C. The results are shown in Tables (4.8)

and (4.10). 3.4.4

Testing the Color Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics 3.4.4.1 Fastness to Washing

In this case, Launder Meter washing machine (Model No. L-4) containing 4- rack test bottle was used. The operation was carried out with Test No.3 of ISO 105.

The required soap solution was prepared with (5 g) of soap per liter

and (2 g) of soda per liter. The dye fabric of (10cm ? 10cm) was cut out. The cotton and polyester/ cotton blend fabric were used as adjacent fabrics. The specimen to be tested was placed between the two pieces of adjacent fabrics. The specimens were sewn along each side to form a composite specimen. The composite specimen was placed in the wash pot of the machine and soap solution was added. The steel cover was closed and the soap solution was heated to a temperature of $60 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. After that the composite specimen was tested at $60 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for 30minutes. At the end of operation, the specimen was lifted from the pot and rinsed thoroughly. The stitching of the composite specimen was broken but the fabric must contact at the line of stitching on two corners. Finally, the specimens were

Section (3.4.3.2). The results are shown in Tables (4.14) and (4.16).

3.5.3.3 Effect of Dyeing Time on Color Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Pre-mordanting Method The procedure of dyeing of mordanted cotton fabric as mentioned in Section (3.4.3.3). The results are shown in Tables (4.15) and (4.17).

3.5.4 Testing the Color Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics 3.5.4.1
Fastness to Washing In this experiments, color fastness of dyed cotton fabrics were determined according to the same procedure as mentioned in Section (3.4.4.1). The results are shown in Table (4.14) to (4.17) and Fig (4.7) to (4.10).

3.5.4.2 Fastness to Rubbing The rubbing fastness of dyed cotton fabrics were determined according to the same procedure as mentioned in Section (3.4.4.2). The results are shown in Table (4.14) to (4.17) and Fig (4.7) to (4.10).

Figure (3.1) Mangrove Bark and Mangrove Bark Powder

Figure (3.2) Extraction Apparatus for Natural Dye

Figure (3.3) Distillation Apparatus for Natural Dye

CHAPTER IV 4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the extraction of natural dye from mangrove bark powder, the phytochemical investigation was carried out to determine the

dried at room temperature. The change in color of the specimen was assessed by comparing with the original dyed fabrics and the rating is defined by using Grey Scale for color change.

The staining of the white cotton fabric was also assessed by Grey Scale for staining. The degree of fastness rating of dyed cotton fabrics were determined by using Grey Scale and the results are shown in Table (4.7) to (4.10) and Fig (4.3) to (4.6).

36 3.4.4.2

Fastness to Rubbing

The rubbing fastness of dyed fabric was determined by JIS STDL-0241 Rubbing Tester Machine. The test specimen (25cm x 5cm) and a piece of white bleached cotton fabric about 5 cm were cut parallel to wrap direction for rubbing fastness test. In rubbing fastness test, the test specimen was mounted on the white bleached cotton cloth and placed on the rubbing tester. The rubbing distance was 100 mm. The test specimen was rubbed 100times with (500 g) load at the speed of 30 circles per minute. The white bleached cotton cloth and the test specimen were rubbed together on the tester by the aid of motor. Six different materials were tested simultaneously on the machine. In this study, both dry and wet rubbing fastness tests were carried out. In rubbing fastness test, the rubbed cotton fabric was wetted with water and the amount of water was two times of the fabric weight. The fabric was finally dried at room temperature.

presence or absence of chemical compounds. According to the result of Table (4.1),

phenolic compound, tannins, flavonoids, saponins, alkaloids and polyphenols were present in mangrove bark powder. Figures (4.1) and (4.2) show the comparison of FT-IR

spectrums

of natural dye powder extracted by water and extracted by 95 % ethanol-water mixture.

Table (4.2) indicates the structural assignment for FT-IR spectrum of natural dye powder extracted by water. The bending vibration of alkenes group was found at 781.17 cm^{-1} . . . Alcohol and phenol group gave the absorption band at 1060.85 cm^{-1} . . and 1112.93 cm^{-1} . . . The absorption band at 1284.59 cm^{-1} . . and 1317.38 cm^{-1} . . which was attributed to CH symmetric bending vibration. CH asymmetric bending vibration was found at 1446.61 cm^{-1} . . .The band at 1519.91 cm^{-1} . . and 1616.35 cm^{-1} . . were characteristics of stretching vibration of aromatic groups. The band at 2924.09 cm^{-1} . . was characteristics of stretching vibration of alkanes group. In addition, absorption band at 3392.79 cm^{-1} indicated the presence of amines group. Table (4.3) describes the functional group present in the natural dye powder extracted by 95% ethanol-water medium. Stretching band of alkenes group was found at 781.17 cm^{-1} . . . Alcohol and phenol group gave the absorption band at 1060.85 cm^{-1} . . and 1112.93 cm^{-1} . . . The

The color stained on bleached cotton fabrics were compared by Grey Scale for staining and the degree of fastness rating was determined. The degree of fastness rating of dyed cotton fabrics were determined by using Grey Scale and the results are shown in Table (4.7) to (4.10) and Fig (4.3)

to (4.6). 3.5 Extraction of the Dye from Mangrove Bark Powder Using 95% Ethanol- Water Mixture 3.5.1 Procedure

Mangrove bark powder 2.5 g was added in 2-neck round bottom flask. 65 ml of 95% ethanol and 185 ml of water (1:3) were added into the flask. The round bottomed flask was fitted with condenser. Then, the extraction was carried out at 70°C for 90 min. After extraction, the extracted dye solution was cooled and filtered. 1 ml of extracted dye solution was diluted in 9 ml of distilled water. An aliquot was introduced in a quart cell and analyzed in a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Model-UV mini-1240, Shimadzu Corporation, Japan). The maximum absorbance value (optical density) was detected at 482 nm. 3.5.1.1

Effect of Ethanol -Water Ratio on the Concentration of Dye Solution

The same procedure as mentioned in Section (3.5.1) was conducted by varying the ethanol and water ratio in the range of 1:1, 1:2, 1:4 and 1:5 respectively. The

absorption band at 1284.59 cm^{-1} . . and 1375.25 cm^{-1} . . which was attributed to CH symmetric bending vibration. CH asymmetric bending vibration was found at 1446.61 cm^{-1} . . .The band at 1521.84 cm^{-1} . . and 1616.35 cm^{-1} . . were characteristics of stretching region of aromatic groups. The stretching vibration of carbonyl group was found at 1732.08 cm^{-1} . . .The band at 2924.09 cm^{-1} . . was characteristics of stretching region of alkanes group. In addition, absorption band at 3385.07 cm^{-1} indicated the presence of amines group. The effect of extraction time on the concentration of dye solution was carried out using the extraction time such as 15, 30, 45, 60 and 75 min and the results are shown in Table (4.4). The absorbance values of dye solution were measured by UV-Vis spectrophotometer. According to the results, the suitable extraction time was found to be 45 min because of the maximum absorbance value and concentration of (2.581) ($8.3510 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mol/L) at 482 nm. Table (4.5) shows the effect of extraction temperature on concentration of dye solution. From the results, the concentration of dye solution increased with increasing temperature from 50 to 80°C and then decreased at 90°C. The suitable extraction temperature was found to be at 80°C because it gave the maximum absorbance value and concentration (2.601) ($8.42 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mol/L) than the other extraction temperature. Table (4.6) indicates the effect of material to solvent ratio on the concentration of dye solution using the different material to solvent ratio such as 1:250, 1.5:250, 2:250, 2.5:250 and 3:250. It was found that the suitable

37 absorbance value of natural dye solution was determined by the same procedure as mentioned in Section (3.5.1) and the results are shown in Table (4.11). 3.5.1.2

Effect of Extraction Time on the Concentration of Dye Solution

The same procedure as mentioned in Section (3.5.1) was conducted by using different extraction time such as 30, 60, 120 and 150 min respectively and the ethanol: water ratio was (1:3). The absorbance value of natural dye solution was determined by the same procedure as mentioned in Section (3.5.1) and the results are shown in Table (4.12). 3.5.1.3

Effect of Extraction Temperature on the Concentration of Dye Solution

The same procedure as mentioned in Section (3.5.1) was conducted by using different extraction temperature such as 50, 60, 80 and 90°C respectively and the extraction time for 90 min. The absorbance value of natural dye solution was determined by the same procedure as mentioned in Section (3.5.1) and the results are shown in Table (4.13). 3.5.2

Identification of the Compounds in the Extracted Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Using 95% Ethanol-Water Mixture by FT-IR Spectrophotometer

The chemical characteristic profiles and identification of functional groups associated to its specific colour of the

material to solvent ratio was 2.5 g powder and 250 ml water because of the maximum absorbance value and concentration of (2.601) ($8.42 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mol/L) at 482 nm. Table (4.7) shows the effect of dyeing temperature on color fastness of dyed cotton fabrics using natural dye powder extracted by water. From the results, the color fastness of dyed cotton fabrics dyeing with pre-mordanting method using alum mordant were nearly the same at 60 to 90°C and so the dyeing temperature 60°C was selected because of the rubbing fastness grade of dry mark 4 (good) and wet mark 3 (fair) and it save electricity cost and energy consumption. The effect of dyeing time on the fastness of cotton fabrics was studied at the different dyeing times such as 30, 45, 60, 75 and 90 min at the temperature of 60°C. The results are shown in Table (4.8) respectively. The dyeing time 60 min was more suitable than the other conditions because of the rubbing fastness of dry mark 4 (good) and wet mark 3 (fair). According to the results of Table (4.9), the cotton fabrics dyeing by pre-mordanting method at 60°C using copper (II) sulphate mordant was more suitable than the other conditions and selected from the aspect of electricity cost and energy consumption. Table (4.10) indicates the results of color fastness of dyed cotton fabrics using pre-mordanting method with copper (II) sulphate. It was also found that dyed cotton fabric dyeing at 60°C for 60 min was more suitable because of the change of shade mark 3 (fair). Table (4.11) to (4.13) show the extraction of natural dye solution using alcoholic medium. The effect of ethanol-water ratio on concentration of dye solution were determined by using UV-Vis spectrophotometer. From the results of Table (4.11), the

extracted dye powder was determined by Perlin Elmer GX FT-IR spectrophotometer. The results are shown in Tables (4.3). 3.5.3

Dyeing Process of Cotton Fabrics Using Dye Powder Extracted with 95% Ethanol-Water Mixture 3.5.3.1 Dyeing Procedure
Mercerization of

Cotton Fabrics Cotton fabrics were mercerized according to the same procedure as mentioned in Section (3.4.3.1). Pre-mordanting Method Mordanting of Cotton Fabrics Mercerized cotton fabrics were mordanted according to the same procedure as mentioned in Section (3.4.3.1).

38 Dyeing of Mordanted Cotton Fabrics Mordanted cotton fabrics were dyed according to the same procedure as mentioned in Section (3.4.3.1). 3.5.3.2

Effect of Dyeing Temperature on Color Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Pre-mordanting Method The procedure of dyeing

of mordanted cotton fabric was used as mentioned in Section (3.4.3.2). The results are shown in Tables (4.14) and (4.16). 3.5.3.3

Effect of Dyeing Time on Color Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Pre-mordanting Method

The

absorbance value and concentration of dye solution was found to be maximum (1.14) ($3.69 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mol/L) at 482 nm using solvent ratio of 1:3. From the results of Table (4.12), the extraction of dye solution at 80°C for 90 min was more suitable than the other conditions because of the maximum absorbance value and concentration of (1.14) ($3.69 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mol/L) at 482 nm. It can be clearly seen that the increase in extraction time gave decrease in concentration of dye solution. According to the results of Table (4.13), it was found that the dye solution extracted at 70°C for 90 min was more suitable than the other condition because of the absorbance value and concentration of dye solution (1.183) ($3.83 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mol/L). Table (4.14) to (4.17) show the effect of dyeing temperature and time on color

fastness of dyed cotton fabrics using natural dye powder extracted by 95% ethanol-water mixture.

From the results of Table (4.14), the cotton fabrics dyed by pre-mordanting method at 50°C for 45 min using alum mordant was more suitable than the other conditions because it gave change of shade mark of 2 (poor). According to the results of Table (4.15), the cotton fabrics dyeing with alum at 50°C for 60 min was suitable condition because of the rubbing fastness of dry mark 4 (good) and wet mark 3-4 (fair-good). From the results of Table (4.16), the color fastness of cotton fabrics dyed at 60°C to 90°C were nearly the same and dyeing temperature at 60°C for 45 min was selected from the aspect of electricity cost. From the results

procedure of dyeing of mordanted cotton fabric as mentioned in Section (3.4.3.3). The results are shown in Tables (4.15) and (4.17). 3.5.4

Testing the Color Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics 3.5.4.1 Fastness to Washing

In this

experiments, color fastness of dyed cotton fabrics were determined according to the same procedure as mentioned in Section (3.4.4.1). The results are shown in Table (4.14) to (4.17) and Fig (4.7) to (4.10). 3.5.4.2 Fastness to Rubbing The rubbing fastness of dyed cotton fabrics were determined according to the same procedure as mentioned in Section (3.4.4.2). The results are shown in Table (4.14) to (4.17) and Fig (4.7) to (4.10).

39 Figure (3.1)

Mangrove Bark and Mangrove Bark Powder Figure (3.2)
Extraction Apparatus for Natural Dye Figure (3.3) Distillation
Apparatus for Natural Dye

40

CHAPTER IV 4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION In the extraction of natural dye from mangrove bark powder, the phytochemical investigation was carried out to determine the presence or absence of chemical compounds. According to the

of Table (4.17), the suitable dyeing time was 60 min at 60°C because

of the rubbing fastness of dry mark 4 (good), wet mark 3 (fair) and change of shade mark 3 (fair).

Table (4.1) Phytochemical Investigation of Mangrove Bark Powder

Sr.No. Tests

Extract

Reagents

Observation

Inference

1

Phenolic Compound

Distilled Water

1%FeCl₃

Violet Color

+

result of Table (4.1),

phenolic compound, tannins, flavonoids, saponins, alkaloids and polyphenols were present in mangrove bark powder. Figures (4.1) and (4.2) show the comparison of FT-IR spectrums of natural dye powder extracted by water and extracted by 95 % ethanol-water mixture.

Table (4.2) indicates the

structural assignment for FT-IR spectrum of natural dye powder extracted by water.

The bending vibration of alkenes group was found at 781.17 cm^{-1} . Alcohol and phenol group gave the absorption band at 1060.85 cm^{-1} and 1112.93 cm^{-1} . The absorption band at 1284.59 cm^{-1} and 1317.38 cm^{-1} which was attributed to CH symmetric bending vibration. CH asymmetric bending vibration was found at 1446.61 cm^{-1} . The band at 1519.91 cm^{-1} and 1616.35 cm^{-1} were characteristics of stretching vibration of aromatic groups. The band at 2924.09 cm^{-1} was characteristics of stretching vibration of alkanes group. In addition, absorption band at 3392.79 cm^{-1} indicated the presence of amines group. Table (4.3) describes the functional group present in the natural dye powder extracted by 95% ethanol-water medium. Stretching band of alkenes group was found at 781.17 cm^{-1} . Alcohol and phenol group gave the absorption band at 1060.85 cm^{-1} and 1112.93 cm^{-1} . The absorption band at 1284.59 cm^{-1} and 1375.25 cm^{-1} which was attributed to CH symmetric bending

2

Tannins

Distilled Water

1%FeCl₃

Deep Blue Precipitate

+

3 Flavonoids

95% Ethanol

Conc: H₂SO₄ + Mg

Pink Color

+

4 Saponins

Distilled Water

Shaken Vigorously

Frothing

+

vibration. CH asymmetric bending vibration was found at 1446.61 cm⁻¹. The band at 1521.84 cm⁻¹ and 1616.35 cm⁻¹ were characteristics of stretching region of aromatic groups. The stretching vibration of carbonyl group was found at 1732.08 cm⁻¹. The band at 2924.09 cm⁻¹ was characteristics of stretching region of alkanes group. In addition, absorption band at 3385.07 cm⁻¹ indicated the presence of amines group. The

effect of extraction time on the concentration of dye solution

was carried out using the extraction time such as 15, 30, 45, 60 and 75 min and the results are shown in Table (4.4). The absorbance values of dye solution were measured by UV-Vis spectrophotometer. According to the results, the suitable

41 extraction time was found to be 45 min because of the maximum absorbance value and concentration of (2.581) (8.35 × 10⁻⁴ mol/L) at 482 nm. Table (4.5) shows the

effect of extraction temperature on concentration of dye solution. From the results, the concentration of dye solution

increased with increasing temperature from 50 to 80°C and then decreased at 90°C. The suitable extraction temperature was found to be at 80°C because it gave the maximum absorbance value and concentration (2.601) (8.42 × 10⁻⁴ mol/L) than the other extraction temperature. Table (4.6) indicates the

effect of material to solvent ratio on the concentration of dye solution

5 Alkaloids

1% HCL

Dragendroff's Reagent Orange Precipitate

+

6 Polyphenols

95% Ethanol

1% FeCl₃ + 1% K₃Fe(CN)₆ Greenish Blue Color

+

Note: (+) = present, (-) = absent The experiments were carried out at the Laboratory of Industrial Chemistry Department, Dagon University.

Table (4.2) Structural Assignment for FT-IR Spectrum of Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Extracted by Water

Sr. No. Wave number, cm⁻¹

Functional Group

Observed Literature

1 3392.79

3500-3000

using the different material to solvent ratio such as 1:250, 1.5:250, 2:250, 2.5:250 and 3:250. It was found that the suitable material to solvent ratio was 2.5 g powder and 250 ml water because of the maximum absorbance value and concentration of (2.601) (8.42×10^{-4} mol/L) at 482 nm. Table (4.7) shows the

effect of dyeing temperature on color fastness of dyed cotton fabrics using natural dye powder extracted by water. From the results, the color fastness of dyed cotton fabrics

dyeing with pre-mordanting method using alum mordant were nearly the same at 60 to 90 °C and so the dyeing temperature 60 °C was selected because of the rubbing fastness grade of dry mark 4 (good) and wet mark 3 (fair) and it save electricity cost and energy consumption.

The effect of dyeing time on the fastness of cotton fabrics was studied at the different dyeing times such as 30, 45, 60, 75

and 90 min at the temperature of 60 °C. The results are shown in Table (4.8) respectively. The dyeing time 60 min was more suitable than the other conditions because of the rubbing fastness of dry mark 4 (good) and wet mark 3 (fair). According to the results of Table (4.9), the cotton fabrics dyeing by pre-mordanting method at 60 °C using copper (II) sulphate mordant was more suitable than the other conditions and selected from the aspect of electricity cost and energy consumption. Table (4.10) indicates the results of

????

Stretching vibration of amines groups

2

2924.09

> 3000

???CH

Stretching vibration of alkanes groups

3

1616.35, 1519.91

~1600

?C=C

Stretching vibration of aromatic groups

4

1446.61

<1400

?as CH

color fastness of dyed cotton fabrics using pre-mordanting method

with copper (II) sulphate. It was also found that dyed cotton fabric dyeing at 60 °C for 60 min was more suitable because of the change of shade mark 3 (fair). Table (4.11) to (4.13) show the extraction of natural dye solution using alcoholic medium. The effect of ethanol-water ratio on concentration of dye solution were determined by using UV-Vis spectrophotometer. From the results of

42 Table (4.11), the absorbance value and concentration of dye solution was found to be maximum (1.14) (3.69×10^{-4} mol/L) at 482 nm using solvent ratio of 1:3. From the results of Table (4.12), the extraction of dye solution at 80 °C for 90 min was more suitable than the other conditions because of the maximum absorbance value and concentration of (1.14) (3.69×10^{-4} mol/L) at 482 nm. It can be clearly seen that the increase in extraction time gave decrease in concentration of dye solution. According to the results of Table (4.13), it was found that the dye solution extracted at 70 °C for 90 min was more suitable than the other condition because of the absorbance value and concentration of dye solution (1.183) (3.83×10^{-4} mol/L). Table (4.14) to (4.17) show the effect of dyeing temperature and

time on color

fastness of dyed cotton fabrics using natural dye powder extracted by 95% ethanol- water mixture.

CH asymmetric bending vibration

5 1317.38, 1284.59

> 1400

?s CH

CH symmetric bending vibration

6 1112.93, 1060.85

1260-1000

?-CO

Stretching vibration of alcohol and phenol group

7

781.17

795-770

??CH

Bending vibration of alkenes group

The experiments were conducted at the Laboratory of Chemistry Department, West Yangon University.

From the results of Table (4.14), the cotton fabrics dyed by pre-mordanting method at 50 °C for 45 min using alum mordant was more suitable than the other conditions because it gave change of shade mark of 2 (poor). According to the results of Table (4.15), the cotton fabrics dyeing with alum at 50 °C for 60 min was suitable condition because

of the rubbing fastness of dry mark 4 (good) and wet mark 3-4 (fair-good).

From the results of Table (4.16), the color fastness of cotton fabrics dyed at 60 °C to 90 °C were nearly the same and dyeing temperature at 60 °C for 45 min was selected from the aspect of electricity cost. From the results of Table (4.17), the suitable dyeing time was 60 min at 60 °C because

of the rubbing fastness of dry mark 4 (good), wet mark 3 (fair) and change of shade mark 3 (fair).

43

Table (4.1) Phytochemical Investigation of Mangrove Bark Powder

Sr.No.	Tests	Extract	Reagents	Observation	Inference
1	Phenolic Compound	Distilled Water	1%FeCl ₃	Violet Color	+
2	Tannins	Distilled Water	1%FeCl ₃	Deep Blue Precipitate	+
3	Flavonoids	95% Ethanol	Conc: H ₂ SO ₄ + Mg	Pink Color	+
4	Saponins	Distilled Water	Shaken Vigorously	Frothing	+
5	Alkaloids	1%HCL	Dragendroff's Reagent	Orange Precipitate	+
6	Polyphenols	95% Ethanol	1% FeCl ₃ + 1% K ₃ Fe(CN) ₆	Greenish	

Table (4.3) Structural Assignment for FT-IR Spectrum of Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Extracted by 95 % Ethanol-Water Mixture

Sr. No. Wave number, cm⁻¹

Functional Group

Observed Literature

1 3385.07

3500-3000

????

Stretching vibration of amines groups

2

2924.09

> 3000

???CH

Stretching vibration of alkanes groups

3

1732.08

Blue Color + Note: (+) = present, (-) = absent The experiments were carried out at the Laboratory of Industrial Chemistry Department, Dagon University.

44 Table (4.2)

Structural Assignment for FT-IR Spectrum of Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Extracted by Water

Sr. No. Wave number, cm⁻¹ Functional Group Observed
 Literature 1 3392.79 3500-3000 ???? Stretching vibration of amines groups
 2 2924.09 > 3000 ???CH Stretching vibration of alkanes groups
 3 1616.35, 1519.91 ~1600 ?C=C Stretching vibration of aromatic groups
 4 1446.61 <1400 ?as CH CH asymmetric bending vibration
 5 1317.38, 1284.59 > 1400 ?s CH CH symmetric bending vibration
 6 1112.93, 1060.85 1260-1000 ?-CO Stretching vibration of alcohol and phenol group
 7 781.17 795-770 ??CH Bending vibration of alkenes group
 The experiments were conducted at the Laboratory of Chemistry Department, West Yangon University.

45 Table (4.3)

Structural Assignment for FT-IR Spectrum of Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Extracted by 95 % Ethanol-Water Mixture

Sr. No. Wave number, cm⁻¹ Functional Group Observed
 Literature 1 3385.07 3500-3000 ???? Stretching vibration of amines groups
 2 2924.09 > 3000 ???CH Stretching vibration of alkanes groups
 3 1732.08 ~1700 ?C=O Stretching vibration of

~1700

?C=O

Stretching vibration of carbonyl groups

4

1616.35, 1521.84

~1600

?C=C

Stretching vibration of aromatic groups

5

1446.61

< 1400

??s CH

CH asymmetric bending vibration

6 1375.25, 1284.59

> 1400

?s CH

carbonyl groups 4 1616.35, 1521.84 ~1600 ν C=C Stretching vibration of aromatic groups 5 1446.61 < 1400 ν s CH CH asymmetric bending vibration 6 1375.25, 1284.59 > 1400 ν s CH CH symmetric bending vibration 7 1112.93, 1060.85 1260-1000 ν -CO Stretching vibration of alcohol and phenol group 8 781.17 795-770 ν CH Bending vibration of alkenes group The experiments were conducted at the Laboratory of Chemistry Department, West Yangon University.

46 Table (4.4)

Effect of Extraction Time on the Concentration of Dye Solution Extracted by Water

Wavelength = 482 nm Sr. No. Extraction Time (min) Extraction Temp. ($^{\circ}$ C) Material to solvent ratio Absorbance Values
Concentration (mol/L) Mangrove bark powder (g) Water (ml) 1 15 90 2.5 250 1.869 6.05×10^{-4} 2 30 90 2.5 250 2.117 6.85×10^{-4} 3 45* 90 2.5 250 2.581 8.35×10^{-4} 4 60 90 2.5 250 2.415 7.82×10^{-4} 5 75 90 2.5 250 1.733 5.61×10^{-4} *the most suitable condition
The experiments were conducted at the Laboratory of Industrial Chemistry Department, Dagon University. Table (4.5)

Effect of Extraction Temperature on the Concentration of Dye Solution Extracted by Water

Wavelength = 482 nm Sr. No.

CH symmetric bending vibration

7 1112.93, 1060.85

1260-1000

ν -CO

Stretching vibration of alcohol and phenol group

8

781.17

795-770

ν CH

Bending vibration of alkenes group

The experiments were conducted at the Laboratory of Chemistry Department, West Yangon University.

Table (4.4) Effect of Extraction Time on the Concentration of Dye Solution Extracted by Water Wavelength = 482 nm

Sr. No.

Extraction Time (min)

Extraction Temp. ($^{\circ}$ C)

Material to solvent ratio

Absorbance Values

Concentration

(mol/L)

Mangrove bark powder (g) Water (ml)

1 15

90

2.5

250 1.869

6.05×10^{-4}

2 30

90

2.5 250 2.117 6.85×10^{-4}

3 45*

90

2.5 250 2.581 8.35×10^{-4}

4 60
 90
 2.5 250 2.415 7.82 x 10⁻⁴
 5 75
 90
 2.5 250 1.733 5.61 x 10⁻⁴
 *

the most suitable condition The experiments were conducted at the Laboratory of Industrial Chemistry Department, Dagon University.

Table (4.5) Effect of Extraction Temperature on the Concentration of Dye Solution Extracted by Water Wavelength = 482 nm

Sr. No.

2	96%
Extraction Time (min) Material to solvent ratio Absorbance Values Concentration (mol/L) Mangrove bark powder (g) Water (ml) 1 50 45 2.5 250 1.699 5.49 x 10 ⁻⁴ 2 60 45 2.5 250 1.820 5.89	

2: thesis book.docx	96%
Extraction Time (min)	
Extraction Temp. (°C)	

8.42×10^{-4} 3 70 45 2.5 250 1.822 5.9 $\times 10^{-4}$ 4 80* 45 2.5 250 2.601
 8.42×10^{-4} 5 90 45 2.5 250 2.581 8.35×10^{-4} *the most suitable
 condition The experiments were conducted at the Laboratory of
 Industrial Chemistry Department, Dagon University.

47 Table (4.6)

Effect of

Material to solvent ratio

Absorbance Values

Concentration

(mol/L)

Mangrove bark powder (g) Water (ml)

1 15

90

2.5

250 1.869

6.05×10^{-4}

2 30

90

2.5 250 2.117 6.85×10^{-4}

3 45*

90

2.5 250 2.581 8.35×10^{-4}

4 60
 90
 2.5 250 2.415 7.82 x 10⁻⁴
 5 75
 90
 2.5 250 1.733 5.61 x 10⁻⁴
 *

the most suitable condition The experiments were conducted at the Laboratory of Industrial Chemistry Department, Dagon University.

Table (4.5) Effect of

3	100%
Material to Solvent Ratio on the Concentration of Dye Solution Extracted by Water	
Wavelength = 482 nm *	
4	84%

3: thesis book.docx	100%
Material to Solvent Ratio	
on the Concentration of Dye Solution Extracted by Water	
Wavelength = 482 nm	
4: thesis book.docx	84%

the most suitable condition The experiments were conducted at the Laboratory of Industrial Chemistry Department, Dagon University. Sr. No. Material to solvent ratio

the most suitable condition The experiments were conducted at the Laboratory of Industrial Chemistry Department, Dagon University. Table (4.6) Effect of

Material to Solvent Ratio

5 90%

Extraction Time (min) Extraction Temp. (°C) Absorbance Values
Concentration (mol/L) Mangrove bark powder (g) Water (ml) 1
1.0 250 45 80 1.243 4.02×10^{-4} 2 1.5 250 45 80 1.606 5.19×10^{-4}
3 2.0 250 45 80 1.662 6.21×10^{-4} 4 2.5* 250 45 80 2.601 8.42×10^{-4}
5 3.0 250 45 80 1.685 5.45×10^{-4}

48

5: thesis book.docx 90%

Extraction Time (min)

Extraction Temp. (°C)

Material to solvent ratio

Absorbance Values

Concentration

(mol/L)

Mangrove bark powder (g) Water (ml)

1 15

90

2.5

250 1.869

6.05 x 10⁻⁴
 2 30
 90
 2.5 250 2.117 6.85 x 10⁻⁴
 3 45*
 90
 2.5 250 2.581 8.35 x 10⁻⁴
 4 60
 90
 2.5 250 2.415 7.82 x 10⁻⁴
 5 75
 90
 2.5 250 1.733 5.61 x 10⁻⁴
 *

6 100%

6: thesis book.docx 100%

Table (4.7)

Effect of Dyeing Temperature on Color Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Extracted by Water and Alum Mordant

Dye powder = 0.5 g Volume of dye solution = 200 ml Dyeing Method = Pre-mordanting method Weight of mercerized cotton fabrics = 25cm ? 25cm Alum = 1 g Mordanting temperature and time = 80°C, 30 min *

7 100%

the most suitable condition Note: 5 = excellent, 4 = good, 3 = fair, 2 = poor, 1 = very poor, p/c = polyester+cotton The experiments were conducted at the

No. (1), Development Centre for Textile Technology Industry, Textile Industry, Mayangone Township, Yangon Region.

8 100%

Sr. No. Sample Code Dyeing Condition Washing Fastness (60°C, 30min) Rubbing Fastness (500g,100 times) Temp. (°C) Time (min) Change of shade Staining on cotton Dry Wet Cotton p/c 1 A 1 50 45 1 4 4 4 2 2 A 2 60* 45 1 4 4 4 3 3 A 3 70 45 1 4 4 4 3 4 A 4 80 45 1 4 4 4 3-4 5 A 5 90 45 1 4 4 4 3

Table (4.7) Effect of Dyeing Temperature on Color Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Extracted by Water and Alum Mordant Dye powder = 0.5 g Volume of dye solution = 200 ml Dyeing Method = Pre-mordanting method Weight of mercerized cotton fabrics = 25cm 25cm Alum = 1 g Mordanting temperature and time = 80°C, 30 min

7: thesis book.docx 100%

the most suitable condition Note: 5 = excellent, 4 = good, 3 = fair, 2 = poor, 1 = very poor, p/c = polyester+cotton The experiments were conducted at the No. (1), Development Centre for Textile Technology Industry, Textile Industry, Mayangone Township, Yangon Region.

8: thesis book.docx 100%

Sr. No. Sample Code Dyeing Condition Washing Fastness (60°C, 30min) Rubbing Fastness (500g,100 times) Temp. (°C) Time (min) Change of shade Staining on cotton Dry Wet

Cotton p/c

1 A1

50 45

1 4 4 4 2

2 A2

60* 45

1 4 4 4 3

3 A3

70 45

1 4 4 4 3

4 A4

80 45

1 4 4 4 3-4

5 A5

90 45

1 4 4 4 3

9 100%

Table (4.8)

Effect of Dyeing Time on Color Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Extracted by Water and Alum Mordant

Dye powder = 0.5 g Volume of dye solution = 200 ml Dyeing Method = Pre-mordanting method Weight of mercerized cotton fabrics = 25cm ? 25cm Alum = 1 g Mordanting temperature and time = 80°C, 30 min *

10 100%

the most suitable condition Note: 5 = excellent, 4 = good, 3 = fair, 2 = poor, 1 = very poor, p/c = polyester+cotton The experiments were conducted at the

No. (1), Development Centre for Textile Technology Industry, Textile Industry, Mayangone Township, Yangon Region.

11 100%

*

9: thesis book.docx 100%

Table (4.8) Effect of Dyeing Time on Color Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Extracted by Water and Alum Mordant Dye powder = 0.5 g Volume of dye solution = 200 ml Dyeing Method = Pre-mordanting method Weight of mercerized cotton fabrics = 25cm 25cm Alum = 1 g Mordanting temperature and time = 80°C, 30 min

10: thesis book.docx 100%

the most suitable condition Note: 5 = excellent, 4 = good, 3 = fair, 2 = poor, 1 = very poor, p/c = polyester+cotton The experiments were conducted at the No. (1), Development Centre for Textile Technology Industry, Textile Industry, Mayangone Township, Yangon Region.

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Sr. No. Sample Code Dyeing Condition Washing Fastness (60 °C,
30min) Rubbing Fastness (500g,100 times) Time. (min) Temp (°C)
Change of shade Staining on cotton Dry Wet Cotton p/c 1 B 1 30
60 1 4 4 4 3 2 B 2 45 60 1 4 4 3-4 2-3 3 B 3 60* 60 2 4 4 4 3 4 B 4
75 60 1 4 4 3-4 2-3 5 B 5 90 60 1 4 4 4 3

50

Sr. No. Sample Code Dyeing Condition Washing Fastness (60 °C,
30min) Rubbing Fastness (500g,100 times)

Time. (min) Temp (°C)

Change of shade Staining on cotton Dry Wet

Cotton p/c

1 B1

30 60 1 4 4 4 3

2 B2

45 60 1 4 4 3-4 2-3

3 B3

60* 60 2 4 4 4 3

4 B4

75 60 1 4 4 3-4 2-3

5 B5

90 60 1 4 4 4 3

*

12

100%

Table (4.9)

Effect of Dyeing Temperature on Color Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Extracted by Water and Copper (II) Sulphate Mordant

Dye powder = 0.5 g Volume of dye solution = 200 ml Dyeing Method = Pre-mordanting method Weight of mercerized cotton fabrics = 25cm x 25cm Copper (II) sulphate = 0.2 g Mordanting temperature and time = 80 °C, 30 min *

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Table (4.9) Effect of Dyeing Temperature on Color Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Extracted by Water and Copper (II) Sulphate Mordant Dye powder = 0.5 g Volume of dye solution = 200 ml Dyeing Method = Pre-mordanting method Weight of mercerized cotton fabrics = 25cm x 25cm Copper (II) sulphate = 0.2 g Mordanting temperature and time = 80 °C, 30 min

13

100%

the most suitable condition Note: 5 = excellent, 4 = good, 3 = fair, 2 = poor, 1 = very poor, p/c = polyester+cotton The experiments were conducted at the

No. (1), Development Centre for Textile Technology Industry, Textile Industry, Mayangone Township, Yangon Region.

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100%

the most suitable condition Note: 5 = excellent, 4 = good, 3 = fair, 2 = poor, 1 = very poor, p/c = polyester+cotton The experiments were conducted at the No. (1), Development Centre for Textile Technology Industry, Textile Industry, Mayangone Township, Yangon Region.

14

100%

Sr. No. Sample Code Dyeing Condition Washing Fastness (60 °C, 30min) Rubbing Fastness (500g,100 times) Temp. (°C) Time (min) Change of shade Staining on cotton Dry Wet Cotton p/c 1 C 1 50

14: thesis book.docx

100%

Sr. No. Sample Code Dyeing Condition Washing Fastness (60 °C, 30min) Rubbing Fastness (500g,100 times)

45 3 4 4 4 3 2 C 2 60* 45 3 4 4 4 3-4 3 C 3 70 45 3 4 4 4 3-4 4 C 4
80 45 3 4 4 4 3-4 5 C 5 90 45 2 4 4 4 3

51

Temp. (°C) Time (min)

Change of shade Staining on cotton Dry Wet

Cotton p/c

1 C1

50 45

3 4 4 4 3

2 C2

60* 45

3 4 4 4 3-4

3 C3

70 45

3 4 4 4 3-4

4 C4

80 45

3 4 4 4 3-4

5 C5

15

100%

Table (4.10)

Effect of Dyeing Time on Color Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Extracted by Water and Copper (II) Sulphate Mordant

Dye powder = 0.5 g Volume of dye solution = 200 ml Dyeing Method = Pre-mordanting method Weight of mercerized cotton fabrics = 25cm ? 25cm Copper (II) sulphate = 0.2 g Mordanting temperature and time = 80 °C, 30 min *

90 45

2 4 4 4 3

*

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Table (4.10) Effect of Dyeing Time on Color Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Extracted by Water and Copper (II) Sulphate Mordant Dye powder = 0.5 g Volume of dye solution = 200 ml Dyeing Method = Pre-mordanting method Weight of mercerized cotton fabrics = 25cm 25cm Copper (II) sulphate = 0.2 g Mordanting temperature and time = 80 °C, 30 min

16

100%

the most suitable condition Note: 5 = excellent, 4 = good, 3 = fair, 2 = poor, 1 = very poor, p/c = polyester+cotton The experiments were conducted at the

No. (1), Development Centre for Textile Technology Industry, Textile Industry, Mayangone Township, Yangon Region.

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the most suitable condition Note: 5 = excellent, 4 = good, 3 = fair, 2 = poor, 1 = very poor, p/c = polyester+cotton The experiments were conducted at the No. (1), Development Centre for Textile Technology Industry, Textile Industry, Mayangone Township, Yangon Region.

17

100%

Sr. No. Sample Code Dyeing Condition Washing Fastness (60°C,
30min) Rubbing Fastness (500g,100 times) Time (min) Temp. (°C)
Change of shade Staining on cotton Dry Wet Cotton p/c 1 D 1 30
60 1 4 4 4 3 2 D 2 45 60 2 4 4 4 3 3 D 3 60* 60 3 4 4 4 3 4 D 4 75 60
1 4 4 4 3 5 D 5 90 60 1 4 4 4 3

52

17: thesis book.docx

100%

Sr. No. Sample Code Dyeing Condition Washing Fastness (60°C,
30min) Rubbing Fastness (500g,100 times)

Time (min) Temp. (°C)

Change of shade Staining on cotton Dry Wet

Cotton p/c

1 D1

30 60 1 4 4 4 3

2 D2

45 60 2 4 4 4 3

3 D3

60* 60 3 4 4 4 3

4 D4

75 60 1 4 4 4 3

5 D5

90 60 1 4 4 4 3

18

100%

Table (4.11)

Effect of Ethanol -Water Ratio on the Concentration of Dye Solution Extracted by 95% Ethanol-Water Mixture Weight of

mangrove bark powder = 2.5 g Wavelength = 482 nm Sr. No. Solvent Ratio Extraction Time (min) Extraction Temp. (°C) Absorbance Value Concentration (mol/ L) Ethanol : Water 1 1 : 1 90 80 0.795 2.57 x 10⁻⁴ 2 1: 2 90 80 0.821 2.67 x 10⁻⁴ 3 1: 3* 90 80 1.14 3.69 x 10⁻⁴ 4 1: 4 90 80 0.601 1.95 x 10⁻⁴ 5 1: 5 90 80 0.842 2.73 x 10⁻⁴ *the most suitable condition The experiments were conducted at the Laboratory of Industrial Chemistry Department, Dagon University.

53 Table (4.12)

Effect of Extraction Time on the Concentration of Dye Solution Extracted by 95 % Ethanol-Water Mixture Weight of

mangrove bark powder = 2.5 g Wavelength = 482 nm Sr. No. Extraction Time (min) Extraction Temp. (°C) Solvent Ratio Absorbance Value Concentration (mol/L) Ethanol : Water 1 30 80 1: 3 0.95 3.07 x 10⁻⁴ 2 60 80 1: 3 1.06 3.43 x 10⁻⁴ 3 90* 80 1: 3 1.14 3.69 x 10⁻⁴ 4 120 80 1: 3 0.917 2.97 x 10⁻⁴ 5 150 80 1: 3

*

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100%

Table (4.11) Effect of Ethanol -Water Ratio on the Concentration of Dye Solution Extracted by 95% Ethanol-Water Mixture Weight of mangrove bark powder = 2.5 g Wavelength = 482 nm Sr. No. Solvent Ratio Extraction Time (min) Extraction Temp. (°C) Absorbance Value Concentration (mol/ L)

Ethanol : Water 1 1 : 1 90 80 0.795 2.57 x 10⁻⁴ 2 1: 2 90 80 0.821 2.67 x 10⁻⁴ 3 1: 3* 90 80 1.14 3.69 x 10⁻⁴ 4 1: 4 90 80 0.601 1.95 x 10⁻⁴ 5 1: 5 90 80 0.842 2.73 x 10⁻⁴

*the most suitable condition The experiments were conducted at the Laboratory of Industrial Chemistry Department, Dagon University.

Table (4.12) Effect of Extraction Time on the Concentration of Dye Solution Extracted by 95 % Ethanol-Water Mixture Weight of mangrove bark powder = 2.5 g Wavelength = 482 nm Sr. No. Extraction Time (min) Extraction Temp. (°C) Solvent Ratio Absorbance Value Concentration (mol/L)

Ethanol : Water 1 30 80 1: 3 0.95 3.07 x 10⁻⁴ 2 60 80 1: 3 1.06 3.43 x 10⁻⁴ 3 90* 80 1: 3 1.14 3.69 x 10⁻⁴ 4 120 80 1: 3 0.917 2.97 x 10⁻⁴ 5 150 80 1: 3 0.717 2.32 x 10⁻⁴

0.717 2.32×10^{-4} *the most suitable condition The experiments were conducted at the Laboratory of Industrial Chemistry Department, Dagon University.

54 Table (4.13)

Effect of Extraction Temperature on the Concentration of Dye Solution Extracted by 95 % Ethanol-Water Mixture Weight of

mangrove bark powder = 2.5 g Wavelength = 482 nm Sr. No.

Extraction Temp. (°C) Extraction Time (min) Solvent Ratio

Absorbance Value Concentration (mol/L) Ethanol : Water 1 50 90

1: 3 0.852 2.76×10^{-4} 2 60 90 1: 3 0.964 3.12×10^{-4} 3 70* 90 1: 3

1.183 3.83×10^{-4} 4 80 90 1: 3 1.14 3.69×10^{-4} 5 90 90 1: 3 0.985

3.19×10^{-4} *the most suitable condition The experiments were

conducted at the Laboratory of Industrial Chemistry

Department, Dagon University.

55 Table (4.14)

Effect of Dyeing Temperature on Color

Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Extracted by 95 % Ethanol-Water Mixture

and Alum Mordant

Dye powder = 0.5 g Volume of dye solution = 200 ml Dyeing Method = Pre-mordanting method Weight of mercerized cotton

*the most suitable condition The experiments were conducted at the Laboratory of Industrial Chemistry Department, Dagon University.

Table (4.13) Effect of Extraction Temperature on the Concentration of Dye Solution Extracted by 95 % Ethanol-Water Mixture Weight of mangrove bark powder = 2.5 g Wavelength = 482 nm Sr. No. Extraction Temp. (°C) Extraction Time (min) Solvent Ratio Absorbance Value Concentration (mol/L)

Ethanol : Water 1 50 90 1: 3 0.852 2.76×10^{-4} 2 60 90 1: 3 0.964 3.12×10^{-4} 3 70* 90 1: 3 1.183 3.83×10^{-4} 4 80 90 1: 3 1.14 3.69×10^{-4} 5 90 90 1: 3 0.985 3.19×10^{-4}

*the most suitable condition The experiments were conducted at the Laboratory of Industrial Chemistry Department, Dagon University.

Table (4.14) Effect of Dyeing Temperature on Color Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Extracted by 95 % Ethanol-Water Mixture and Alum Mordant Dye powder = 0.5 g Volume of dye solution = 200 ml Dyeing Method = Pre-mordanting method Weight of mercerized cotton fabrics = 25cm 25cm Alum = 1 g Mordanting temperature and time = 80°C, 30 min

fabrics = 25cm ? 25cm Alum = 1 g Mordanting temperature and time = 80°C, 30 min *

19

100%

the most suitable condition Note: 5 = excellent, 4 = good, 3 = fair, 2 = poor, 1 = very poor p/c=polyester + cotton The experiments were conducted at the

No. (1), Development Centre for Textile Technology Industry, Textile Industry, Mayangone Township, Yangon Region.

20

100%

Sr. No. Sample Code Dyeing Condition Washing Fastness (60 °C, 30min) Rubbing Fastness (500g,100 times) Temp. (°C) Time (min) Change of shade Staining on cotton Dry Wet Cotton p/c 1 E 1 50* 45 2 4 4 4 3 2 E 2 60 45 1 4 4 4 3 3 E 3 70 45 1 4 4 4 3 4 E 4 80 45 1 4 4 4 3 5 E 5 90 45 1 4 4 4 3

56

19: thesis book.docx

100%

the most suitable condition Note: 5 = excellent, 4 = good, 3 = fair, 2 = poor, 1 = very poor, p/c = polyester+cotton The experiments were conducted at the No. (1), Development Centre for Textile Technology Industry, Textile Industry, Mayangone Township, Yangon Region.

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100%

Sr. No. Sample Code Dyeing Condition Washing Fastness (60 °C, 30min) Rubbing Fastness (500g,100 times)

Temp. (°C) Time (min)

Change of shade Staining on cotton Dry Wet

Cotton p/c

1 E1

50* 45

2 4 4 4 3

2 E2
 60 45
 1 4 4 4 3
 3 E3
 70 45
 1 4 4 4 3
 4 E4
 80 45
 1 4 4 4 3
 5 E5
 90 45
 1 4 4 4 3
 *

21 100%

Table (4.15)
 Effect of Dyeing Time on Color

21: thesis book.docx 100%

Table (4.15) Effect of Dyeing Time on Color Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Extracted by

Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Extracted by 95 % Ethanol- Water Mixture

and Alum Mordant

Dye powder = 0.5 g Volume of dye solution = 200 ml Dyeing Method = Pre-mordanting method Weight of mercerized cotton fabrics = 25cm ? 25cm Alum = 1 g Mordanting temperature and time = 80°C, 30 min *

22 100%

the most suitable condition Note: 5 =excellent, 4 = good, 3 = fair, 2 = poor, 1 = very poor p/c = polyester + cotton The experiments were conducted at the

No. (1), Development Centre for Textile Technology Industry, Textile Industry, Mayangone Township, Yangon Region.

23 100%

Sr. No. Sample Code Dyeing Condition Washing Fastness (60°C, 30min) Rubbing Fastness (500g,100 times) Time (min) Temp. (°C) Change of shade Staining on cotton Dry Wet Cotton p/c 1 F 1 30 50 1 4 4 4 3 2 F 2 45 50 1 4 4 4 3 3 F 3 60* 50 1 4 4 4 3-4 4 F 4 75 50 1 4 4 4 3 5 F 5 90 50 1 4 4 4 3

57

95 % Ethanol- Water Mixture and Alum Mordant Dye powder = 0.5 g Volume of dye solution = 200 ml Dyeing Method = Pre-mordanting method Weight of mercerized cotton fabrics = 25cm 25cm Alum = 1 g Mordanting temperature and time = 80°C, 30 min

22: thesis book.docx 100%

the most suitable condition Note: 5 = excellent, 4 = good, 3 = fair, 2 = poor, 1 = very poor, p/c = polyester+cotton The experiments were conducted at the No. (1), Development Centre for Textile Technology Industry, Textile Industry, Mayangone Township, Yangon Region.

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Sr. No. Sample Code Dyeing Condition Washing Fastness (60°C, 30min) Rubbing Fastness (500g,100 times) Time (min) Temp. (°C) Change of shade Staining on cotton Dry Wet

Cotton p/c
 1 F1
 30 50 1 4 4 4 3
 2 F2
 45 50 1 4 4 4 3
 3 F3
 60* 50 1 4 4 4 3-4
 4 F4
 75 50 1 4 4 4 3
 5 F5
 90 50 1 4 4 4 3
 *

24

100%

Table (4.16)

Effect of Dyeing Temperature on Color

24: thesis book.docx

100%

Table (4.16) Effect of Dyeing Temperature on Color Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Extracted by 95 % Ethanol-Water Mixture and Copper (II) Sulphate Mordant
 Dye powder = 0.5 g Volume of dye solution = 200 ml Dyeing

Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Extracted by 95 % Ethanol-Water Mixture

and Copper (II) Sulphate Mordant

Dye powder = 0.5 g Volume of dye solution = 200 ml Dyeing Method = Pre-mordanting method Weight of mercerized cotton fabrics = 25cm x 25cm Copper (II) sulphate = 0.2 g Mordanting temperature and time = 80 °C, 30 min *

Method = Pre-mordanting method Weight of mercerized cotton fabrics = 25cm x 25cm Copper (II) sulphate = 0.2 g Mordanting temperature and time = 80 °C, 30 min

25 100%

the most suitable condition Note: 5 =excellent, 4 = good, 3 = fair, 2 = poor, 1 = very poor p/c = polyester + cotton The experiments were conducted at the

No. (1), Development Centre for Textile Technology Industry, Textile Industry, Mayangone Township, Yangon Region.

25: thesis book.docx 100%

the most suitable condition Note: 5 = excellent, 4 = good, 3 = fair, 2 = poor, 1 = very poor, p/c = polyester+cotton The experiments were conducted at the No. (1), Development Centre for Textile Technology Industry, Textile Industry, Mayangone Township, Yangon Region.

26 100%

Sr. No. Sample Code Dyeing Condition Washing Fastness (60 °C, 30min) Rubbing Fastness (500g,100 times) Temp. (°C) Time (min) Change of shade Staining on cotton Dry Wet Cotton p/c 1 G 1 50 45 2 4 4 3 2 2 G 2 60* 45 3 4 4 3-4 3 3 G 3 70 45 3 4 4 4 3 4 G 4 80 45 3 4 4 4 3-4 5 G 5 90 45 3 4 4 3-4 3

58

26: thesis book.docx 100%

Sr. No. Sample Code Dyeing Condition Washing Fastness (60 °C, 30min) Rubbing Fastness (500g,100 times) Temp. (°C) Time (min) Change of shade Staining on cotton Dry Wet

Cotton p/c

1 G1

50 45

2 4 4 3 2

2 G2

60* 45

3 4 4 3-4 3

3 G3

70 45

3 4 4 4 3

4 G4

80 45

3 4 4 4 3-4

5 G5

90 45

3 4 4 3-4 3

27

100%

Table (4.17)

Effect of Dyeing Time on Color

Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Extracted by 95 % Ethanol- Water Mixture

and Copper (II) Sulphate Mordant

Dye powder = 0.5 g Volume of dye solution = 200 ml Dyeing Method = Pre-mordanting method Weight of mercerized cotton fabrics = 25cm ? 25cm Copper (II) sulphate = 0.2 g Mordanting temperature and time = 80 °C, 30 min *

28

100%

the most suitable condition Note: 5 =excellent, 4 = good, 3 = fair, 2 = poor, 1 = very poor p/c = polyester + cotton The experiments were conducted at the

No. (1), Development Centre for Textile Technology Industry, Textile Industry, Mayangone Township, Yangon Region.

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Table (4.17) Effect of Dyeing Time on Color Fastness of Dyed Cotton Fabrics Using Mangrove Bark Dye Powder Extracted by 95 % Ethanol- Water Mixture and Copper (II) Sulphate Mordant
Dye powder = 0.5 g Volume of dye solution = 200 ml Dyeing Method = Pre-mordanting method Weight of mercerized cotton fabrics = 25cm 25cm Copper (II) sulphate = 0.2 g Mordanting temperature and time = 80 °C, 30 min

28: thesis book.docx

100%

the most suitable condition Note: 5 = excellent, 4 = good, 3 = fair, 2 = poor, 1 = very poor, p/c = polyester+cotton The experiments were conducted at the No. (1), Development Centre for Textile Technology Industry, Textile Industry, Mayangone Township, Yangon Region.

29

100%

Sr. No. Sample Code Dyeing Condition Washing Fastness (60°C,
30min) Rubbing Fastness (500g,100 times) Time (min) Temp. (°C)
Change of shade Staining on cotton Dry Wet Cotton p/c 1 H 1 30
60 3 4 4 4 3 2 H 2 45 60 3 4 4 4 3 3 H 3 60* 60 3 4 4 4 3 4 H 4 75
60 2 4 4 4 3 5 H 5 90 60 2 4 4 4 3

59

29: thesis book.docx

100%

Sr. No. Sample Code Dyeing Condition Washing Fastness (60°C,
30min) Rubbing Fastness (500g,100 times)

Time (min) Temp. (°C)

Change of shade Staining on cotton Dry Wet

Cotton p/c

1 H1

30 60 3 4 4 4 3

2 H2

45 60 3 4 4 4 3

3 H3

60* 60 3 4 4 4 3

4 H4

75 60 2 4 4 4 3

5 H5

90 60 2 4 4 4 3

30

100%

Figure (4.1)

FT-IR Spectrum of Extracted Mangrove Bark Dye Powder by Water

60 Figure (4.2) FT-IR Spectrum of Extracted Mangrove Bark Dye Powder by 95% Ethanol-Water Mixture

61

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Figure (4.1) FT-IR Spectrum of Extracted Mangrove Bark Dye Powder by Water

Figure (4.2) FT-IR Spectrum of Extracted Mangrove Bark Dye Powder by 95% Ethanol-Water Mixture

3

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54

100%

<https://www.aims.gov.au/docs/projectnet/mangroves-uses.html>.

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<https://www.aims.gov.au/docs/projectnet/mangroves-uses.html>).

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31 100%

Color Fastness of Cotton Fabrics Dyeing with Extracted Dye Powder Using Water (Mordanted with Alum)

62

31: TABLE OF CONTENTS.DYE.docx 100%

Color Fastness of Cotton Fabrics Dyeing with Extracted Dye 61 Powder Using Water (Mordanted with Alum) (4.4)

32 100%

Color Fastness of Cotton Fabrics Dyeing with Extracted Dye Powder Using Water (Mordanted with Alum)

63

32: TABLE OF CONTENTS.DYE.docx 100%

Color Fastness of Cotton Fabrics Dyeing with Extracted Dye 61 Powder Using Water (Mordanted with Alum) (4.4)

33 100%

Color Fastness of Cotton Fabrics Dyeing with Extracted Dye Powder Using Water (Mordanted with Copper (II) Sulphate)

64

33: TABLE OF CONTENTS.DYE.docx 100%

Color Fastness of Cotton Fabrics Dyeing with Extracted Dye 63 Powder Using Water (Mordanted with Copper (II) Sulphate) (4.6)

34 100%

Color Fastness of Cotton Fabrics Dyeing with Extracted Dye Powder Using Water (Mordanted with Copper (II) Sulphate)

34: TABLE OF CONTENTS.DYE.docx 100%

Color Fastness of Cotton Fabrics Dyeing with Extracted Dye 63 Powder Using Water (Mordanted with Copper (II) Sulphate) (4.6)

65

35 100%

Color Fastness of Cotton Fabrics Dyeing with Extracted Dye Powder Using 95% Ethanol-Water Mixture (Mordanted with Alum)

66

36 100%

Color Fastness of Cotton Fabrics Dyeing with Extracted Dye Powder Using 95% Ethanol-Water Mixture (Mordanted with Alum)

67

37 96%

Color Fastness of Cotton Fabrics Dyeing with Extracted Dye Powder Using 95% Ethanol-Water Mixture (Mordanted with Copper (II) Sulphate)

68 Figure (4.10) Color Fastness of Cotton Fabrics Dyeing with Extracted Dye Powder Using 95% Ethanol-Water Mixture (Mordanted with Copper (II) Sulphate)

35: TABLE OF CONTENTS.DYE.docx 100%

Color Fastness of Cotton Fabrics Dyeing with Extracted Dye 65 Powder Using 95% Ethanol-Water Mixture (Mordanted with Alum) (4.8)

36: TABLE OF CONTENTS.DYE.docx 100%

Color Fastness of Cotton Fabrics Dyeing with Extracted Dye 65 Powder Using 95% Ethanol-Water Mixture (Mordanted with Alum) (4.8)

37: TABLE OF CONTENTS.DYE.docx 96%

Color Fastness of Cotton Fabrics Dyeing with Extracted Dye 67 Powder Using 95% Ethanol-Water Mixture (Mordanted with Copper (II) Sulphate) (4.10) Color Fastness of Cotton Fabrics Dyeing with Extracted Dye 68 Powder Using 95% Ethanol-Water Mixture (Mordanted with Copper (II) Sulphate)

Instances from: CONCLUSIO1.docx

38

100%

CONCLUSION

In this research work natural dye was extracted from mangrove bark

using two different media such as aqueous and alcoholic media. According to the results of phytochemical tests, it was found that the colour compounds such as

phenolic compound, tannins, flavonoids, saponins, alkaloids and polyphenols were present in mangrove bark. From the results of FT-IR

analysis, the structural assignment

of natural dye powder extracted by water and extracted by 95% ethanol-water mixture

were nearly the same. From the results of absorbance values and concentration of dye solution, it can be concluded that the suitable conditions for extraction of natural dye by using aqueous media were found to be material to solvent ratio (1:100) and extraction temperature 80°C for 45 min. It was also found that the most suitable conditions for extraction of natural dye solution were ethanol-water ratio (1:3), extraction time 90 min and extraction temperature 70°C. It can be seen that the

38: CONCLUSIO1.docx

100%

CONCLUSION In this research work natural dye was extracted from mangrove bark using two different media such as aqueous and alcoholic media.

According to the results of phytochemical tests, it was found that the colour compounds such as

phenolic compound, tannins, flavonoids, saponins, alkaloids and polyphenols were present in mangrove bark. From the results of FT-IR analysis, the structural assignment of natural dye powder extracted by water and extracted by 95% ethanol-water mixture

were nearly the same. From the results of absorbance values and concentration of dye solution, it can be concluded that the suitable conditions for extraction of natural dye by using aqueous media were found to be material to solvent ratio (1:100) and extraction temperature 80°C for 45 min. It was also found that the most suitable conditions for extraction of natural dye solution were ethanol-water ratio (1:3), extraction time 90 min and extraction temperature 70°C. It can be seen that the concentration of dye solution was decreased in increasing extraction time and temperature. According to the results of absorbance values and the concentration of dye solution extracted by aqueous media at 80°C for 45 min was (2.601) and the dye solution extracted by alcoholic media at 70°C for 90 min

concentration of dye solution was decreased in increasing extraction time and temperature. According to the results of absorbance values and the concentration of dye solution extracted by aqueous media at 80°C for 45 min was (2.601) and the dye solution extracted by alcoholic media at 70°C for 90 min was (1.183). It can be concluded that the aqueous media was more suitable than the alcoholic media. The colour fastness of

cotton fabrics dyeing by natural dye powder extracted by water at 60°C for 60 min using copper (II) sulphate gave the better results

than the colour fastness results of dyed cotton fabrics using alum. The colour

fastness of cotton fabrics dyeing by natural dye powder extracted by 95% ethanol-

water mixture

at 60°C for 60 min using copper (II) sulphate gave the better results

than the colour fastness results of dyed cotton fabrics using alum. The cotton fabrics dyeing by pre-mordanting method with copper (II) sulphate gave attractive colour and acceptable fastness properties than the alum mordant. It was observed that

was (1.183). It can be concluded that the aqueous media was more suitable than the alcoholic media. The colour fastness of cotton fabrics dyeing by natural dye powder extracted by water at 60°C for 60 min using copper (II) sulphate gave the better results than the colour fastness results of dyed cotton fabrics using alum. The colour fastness of cotton fabrics dyeing by natural dye powder extracted by 95% ethanol-water mixture at 60°C for 60 min using copper (II) sulphate gave the better results than the colour fastness results of dyed cotton fabrics using alum. The cotton fabrics dyeing by pre-mordanting method with copper (II) sulphate gave attractive colour and acceptable fastness properties than the alum mordant. It was observed that the cotton fabric dyeing by natural dye powder extracted by water at 60°C for 60 min using copper (II) sulphate gave the better result

of the rubbing fastness of dry mark 4 (good), wet mark 3-4 (fair-good)

and change of shade mark of 3 (fair)

than the colour

fastness of dyed cotton fabrics dyeing by natural dye powder extracted by 95% ethanol-water mixture

at 60°C for 60 min. SUGGESTIONS FOR FUTURE WORK For future research work, natural dye solution should be extracted from

the cotton fabric dyeing by natural dye powder extracted by water at 60°C for 60 min using copper (II) sulphate gave the better

result

of the rubbing fastness of dry mark 4 (good), wet mark 3-4 (fair-good) and change of shade mark

of 3 (fair) than the colour

fastness of dyed cotton fabrics dyeing by natural dye powder extracted by 95% ethanol-water mixture

at 60°C for 60 min.

70 SUGGESTIONS FOR FUTURE WORK For future research work, natural dye solution should be extracted from mangrove bark using different solvents such as n-hexane and methanol and converted into powder form. Extraction of natural dyes from mangrove bark should also be conducted using alkali and acidic media. Mangrove dye powder should be used for the preparation of food colourant and medicinal products. Furthermore, more studies dyeing processes should also be conducted on protein fibres such as silk and wool and also synthetic fibres such as nylon and polyester by using extracted dye powder from mangrove bark. Studies should also be conducted by using other mordants such as wood ash, salt, and iron etc. For accessing the quality and stability of dyeing product,

mangrove bark using different solvents such as n-hexane and methanol and converted into powder form. Extraction of natural dyes from mangrove bark should also be conducted using alkali and acidic media. Mangrove dye powder should be used for the preparation of food colourant and medicinal products.

Furthermore, more studies dyeing processes should also be conducted on protein fibres such as silk and wool and also synthetic fibres such as nylon and polyester by using extracted dye powder from mangrove bark. Studies should also be conducted by using other mordants such as wood ash, salt, and iron etc. For accessing the quality and stability of dyeing product, fastness to perspiration and light fastness should also be conducted.

HYPOTHETICAL PROCESS DESIGNS

fastness to perspiration and light fastness should also be conducted.

71 HYPOTHETICAL PROCESS DESIGNS

72

39

58%

Washing Debarking Drying Screening Grinding Figure A: Process Flow Diagram for the Extraction of Natural Dye Powder from Mangrove Bark (using Water) Extraction Water Natural Dye Powder Pieces of Mangrove Stem Evaporation Drying Grinding

73 Washing Debarking Drying Screening Grinding Pieces of Mangrove Stem Extraction Distillation Evaporation Drying Natural Dye Powder Figure B: Process Flow Diagram for the Extraction of Natural Dye Powder from Mangrove Bark (using 95% Ethanol-Water Mixture) 95%

39: CONCLUSIO1.docx

58%

Washing Debarking Drying Screening Grinding

Grinding

Water

Drying

Evaporation

Extraction

Figure A: Process Flow Diagram for the Extraction of Natural Dye Powder from Mangrove Bark (using Water)

Natural Dye Powder

Pieces of Mangrove Stem

Natural Dye Powder

Grinding
 Drying
 Evaporation
 Distillation
 95% Ethanol-Water Mixture
 Extraction
 Extraction
 Drying
 Evaporation
 Distillation

Figure B: Process Flow Diagram for the Extraction of Natural Dye Powder from Mangrove Bark (using 95% Ethanol-Water Mixture)

40 100%

Figure C: Process Flow Diagram for the Mercerizing of Cotton Fabrics

41 95%

40: CONCLUSIO1.docx 100%

Figure C: Process Flow Diagram for the Mercerizing of Cotton Fabrics

41: CONCLUSIO1.docx 95%

Figure D: Process Flow Diagram for Dyeing of Cotton Fabrics Using Pre-mordanting Method 0.5 g dye powder and 200 ml water

76 APPENDICES APPENDIX A COST ESTIMATION FOR THE EXTRACTED NATURAL DYE POWDER FROM MANGROVE BARK POWDER (USING WATER) Basis: 100g / day Capacity of one package = 50g Production day = 300 days / year One shift = 8 hours Yield of extracted natural dye powder = 20% Sr. No. Direct Production Cost Amount Cost / unit (Kyat) Total Cost (Kyat) 1 Raw Materials Mangrove bark powder Pure water Filter paper 500g/ day 50L/day 5sheets/day K. 5/g K. 25/L K. 35/sheet 750,000 375,000 52,500 2 Labour Cost Supervisor Unskilled worker 1 No. 2 No. K. 5000/ day K. 4000/ day 1,500,000 2,400,000 3 Utilities Cost Electricity Water 20unit/day 50L/day K. 75/ unit K. 5/ L 450,000 75,000 4 Packaging and labelling 10package/day K.10/ package 30,000 Total Cost 5,632,500 Purchased equipment cost, P = K.300,000 Salvage value, L = K. 10,000 Service Life, n = 10 years

77 Annual straight line depreciation = $\frac{P - L}{n} = \frac{300000 - 10000}{10} = K. 29,000$ Manufacturing Cost = Direct Production Cost + Fixed Charges = $K. 5632500 + K. 29000 = K. 5661500$ Manufacturing Cost/ package = $\frac{5661500}{1887.2} = K. 3000$ Only raw materials, labour, utilities and packing costs were taken into consideration for direct production costs. Only depreciation on equipment was taken into consideration in fixed charges.

Figure D: Process Flow Diagram for Dyeing of Cotton Fabrics Using Pre-mordanting Method

Dyed Cotton Fabric

Air drying

Washing

APPENDICES APPENDIX A COST ESTIMATION FOR THE EXTRACTED NATURAL DYE POWDER FROM MANGROVE BARK POWDER (USING WATER) Basis: 100g / day Capacity of one package = 50g Production day = 300 days / year One shift = 8 hours Yield of extracted natural dye powder = 20% Sr. No. Direct Production Cost Amount Cost / unit (Kyat) Total Cost (Kyat) 1 Raw Materials Mangrove bark powder Pure water Filter paper 500g/ day 50L/day 5sheets/day K. 5/g K. 25/L K. 35/sheet

750,000 375,000 52,500 2 Labour Cost Supervisor Unskilled worker

1 No. 2 No. K. 5000/ day K. 4000/ day

1,500,000 2,400,000

3 Utilities Cost Electricity Water

20unit/day 50L/day K. 75/ unit K. 5/ L 450,000 75,000 4 Packaging and labelling

78 COST ESTIMATION FOR THE EXTRACTED NATURAL DYE POWDER FROM MANGROVE BARK POWDER (USING 95% ETHANOL-WATER MIXTURE) Basis: 100g / day Capacity of one package = 50g Production day = 300 days / year One shift = 8 hours Yield of extracted natural dye powder = 16% Sr. No. Direct Production Cost Amount Cost / unit (Kyat) Total Cost (Kyat) 1 Raw Materials Mangrove bark powder Ethanol Water Filter paper 625g/day 16.25L/day 48.75L/day 5sheets/day K. 5/g K. 1700/L K. 25/L K. 35/sheet 937,500 8,287,500 365,625 52,500 2 Labour Cost Supervisor Unskilled worker 1 No. 2 No. K. 5000/ day K. 4000/ day 1,500,000 2,400,000 3 Utilities Cost Electricity Water 30unit/ day 50L/day K. 75/ unit K. 5/ L 675,000 75,000 4 Packaging and labelling 10package/day K.10/package 30,000 Total Cost 14,323,125 Purchased equipment cost, P = K.500, 000 Salvage value, L = K. 10, 000 Service Life, n = 10 years

79 Annual straight line depreciation = $\frac{P - L}{n} = \frac{500000 - 10000}{10} = K. 49,000$ Manufacturing Cost = Direct Production Cost + Fixed Charges = $K. 14323125 + K. 49000 = K. 14372125$ Manufacturing Cost/ package = $\frac{14372125}{3000} = K. 4790.71$ / package Only raw materials, labour, utilities and packing costs were taken into consideration for direct production costs. Only depreciation on equipment was taken into consideration in fixed charges.

80 COST ESTIMATION FOR DYED COTTON FABRICS USING EXTRACTED DYE POWDER FROM MANGROVE BARK POWDER WITH PRE- MORDANTING METHOD (EXTRACRED BY WATER) Basis: 50 yards of dyed cotton fabric/ day Capacity of one

10package/day K.10/package

30,000

Total Cost 5,632,500

Purchased equipment cost, P = K.300,000 Salvage value, L = K. 10,000 Service Life, n = 10 years Annual straight line depreciation = $\frac{P - L}{n} = \frac{300000 - 10000}{10} = K. 29,000$ Manufacturing Cost = Direct Production Cost + Fixed Charges = $K. 5632500 + K. 29000 = K. 5661500$ Manufacturing Cost/ package = $\frac{5661500}{3000} = K. 1887.2$ / package Only raw materials, labour, utilities and packing costs were taken into consideration for direct production costs. Only depreciation on equipment was taken into consideration in fixed charges.

COST ESTIMATION FOR THE EXTRACTED NATURAL DYE POWDER FROM MANGROVE BARK POWDER (USING 95% ETHANOL-WATER MIXTURE) Basis 100g / day Capacity of one package = 50g Production day = 300 days / year One shift = 8 hours Yield of extracted natural dye powder = 16% Sr. No. Direct Production Cost Amount Cost / unit (Kyat) Total Cost (Kyat) 1 Raw Materials Mangrove bark powder Ethanol Water Filter paper 625g/day 16.25L/day 48.75L/day 5sheets/day K. 5/g K. 1700/L K. 25/L K. 35/ sheet

937,500 8,287,500 365,625 52,500 2 Labour Cost Supervisor Unskilled worker 1 No. 2 No.

K. 5000/ day K. 4000/ day

package = 10 yard Production day = 300 days/ year One shift = 8 hours

1,500,000 2,400,000 3 Utilities Cost Electricity Water

30unit/day 50L/day K. 75/ unit K. 5/ L 675,000 75,000 4 Packaging and labelling

10package/day K.10/package

30,000

Total Cost 14,323,125

Purchased equipment cost, P = K.500, 000 Salvage value, L = K. 10, 000 Service Life, n = 10 years Annual straight line depreciation = = = K. 49,000 Manufacturing Cost = Direct Production Cost + Fixed Charges = K. 14323125 + K. 49000 = K. 14372125 Manufacturing Cost/ package = = K. 4790.7/ package Only raw materials, labour, utilities and packing costs were taken into consideration for direct production costs. Only depreciation on equipment was taken into consideration in fixed charges.

COST ESTIMATION FOR DYED COTTON FABRICS USING EXTRACTED DYE POWDER FROM MANGROVE BARK POWDER WITH PRE-MORDANTING METHOD (EXTRACRED BY WATER)
Basis: 50 yards of dyed cotton fabric/ day Capacity of one package = 10 yard

Production day = 300 days/ year One shift = 8 hours

Purchased equipment cost, P = K.300, 000 Salvage value, L = K. 10, 000 Service Life, n = 10 years Annual straight line depreciation =

43 100%

Sr. No. Direct Production Cost Amount Cost / unit (Kyat) Total Cost (Kyat) 1 2 Raw Materials Extracted dye powder Water Cotton fabrics Chemicals Sodium hydroxide Acetic acid Copper (II) sulphate 300g/day 120L/day 50yards/day 150g/day 200ml/day 120g/day K. 189/g K. 25/L K. 1300/yard K. 40/g K. 15/ml K. 40/g 17,010,000 900,000 19,500,000 1,800,000 900,000 1,440,000 3 Labour Cost Supervisor Unskilled worker 1No. 2No. K.5000/day K.4000/day 1,500,000 2,400,000 4 Utilities Cost 5 Electricity Water Packaging And labelling 20unit/day 100L/day 5package/day K. 75/unit K. 5/L K. 100/package 450,000 75,000 150,000 Total Cost 46,125,000

81 = 10 10000 300000 ? =

44 100%

Purchased equipment cost, P = K.300, 000 Salvage value, L = K. 10, 000 Service Life, n = 10 years Annual straight line depreciation = = =

43: CONCLUSIO1.docx 100%

Sr. No. Direct Production Cost Amount Cost / unit (Kyat) Total Cost (Kyat) 1

2 Raw Materials Extracted dye powder Water Cotton fabrics Chemicals Sodium hydroxide Acetic acid Copper (II) sulphate 300g/day 120L/day 50yards/day

150g/day 200ml/day 120g/day K. 189/g K. 25/L K. 1300/yard

K. 40/g K. 15/ml K. 40/g 17,010,000 900,000 19,500,000

1,800,000 900,000 1,440,000 3

Labour Cost Supervisor Unskilled worker 1No. 2No. K.5000/day K.4000/day 1,500,000 2,400,000 4 Utilities Cost

5 Electricity Water Packaging And labelling 20unit/day 100L/day 5package/day K. 75/unit K. 5/L K. 100/package 450,000 75,000 150,000

Total Cost 46,125,000

44: CONCLUSIO1.docx 100%

K. 29,000 Manufacturing Cost = Direct Production Cost + Fixed Charges = K. 46125000 + K. 29000 = K. 46,154,000 Manufacturing Cost/ package = 1500 46154000 = K. 30769.3/ package
 Manufacturing Cost/ yard = K. 3076.9/ yard Only raw materials, labour, utilities and packing costs were taken into consideration for direct production costs. Only depreciation on equipment was taken into consideration in fixed charges.

82 COST ESTIMATION FOR DYED COTTON FABRICS USING EXTRACTED DYE POWDER FROM MANGROVE BARK POWDER WITH PRE- MORDANTING METHOD (EXTRACRED BY 95% Ethanol-Water Mixture) Basis: 50 yards of dyed cotton fabric/ day
 Capacity of one package = 10 yard Production day = 300 days/ year

45

100%

One shift = 8 hours Purchased equipment cost, P = K.300, 000
 Salvage value, L = K. 10, 000 Service Life, n = 10 years Annual straight line depreciation =

46

100%

K. 29,000 Manufacturing Cost = Direct Production Cost + Fixed Charges = K. 46125000 + K. 29000 = K. 46,154,000 Manufacturing Cost/ package = = K. 30769.3/ package Manufacturing Cost/ yard = K. 3076.9/ yard Only raw materials, labour, utilities and packing costs were taken into consideration for direct production costs. Only depreciation on equipment was taken into consideration in fixed charges.

COST ESTIMATION FOR DYED COTTON FABRICS USING EXTRACTED DYE POWDER FROM MANGROVE BARK POWDER WITH PRE-MORDANTING METHOD (EXTRACRED BY 95% Ethanol-Water Mixture) Basis: 50 yards of dyed cotton fabric/ day
 Capacity of one package = 10 yard
 Production day = 300 days/ year

45: CONCLUSIO1.docx

100%

One shift = 8 hours

Purchased equipment cost, P = K.300, 000 Salvage value, L = K. 10, 000 Service Life, n = 10 years Annual straight line depreciation = = =

46: CONCLUSIO1.docx

100%

Sr. No. Direct Production Cost Amount Cost / unit (Kyat) Total Cost (Kyat) 1 2 Raw Materials Extracted dye powder Water Cotton fabrics Chemicals Sodium hydroxide Acetic acid Copper (II) sulphate 300g/day 120L/day 50yards/day 150g/day 200ml/day 120g/day K. 479/g K. 25/L K. 1300/yard K. 40/g K. 15/ml K. 40/g 43,110,000 900,000 19,500,000 1,800,000 900,000 1,440,000 3 4 Labour Cost Supervisor Unskilled worker Utilities Cost Electricity Water 1 No. 2 No. 20unit/day 100L/day K. 5000/ day K. 4000/ day K. 75/ unit K. 5/ L 1,500,000 2,400,000 450,000 75,000 5 Packaging and labelling 50package/day K.100/package 150,000 Total Cost 72,225,000

83 = 10 10000 300000 ? =

Sr. No. Direct Production Cost Amount Cost / unit (Kyat) Total Cost (Kyat) 1

2 Raw Materials Extracted dye powder Water Cotton fabrics Chemicals Sodium hydroxide Acetic acid Copper (II) sulphate 300g/day 120L/day 50yards/day

150g/day 200ml/day 120g/day K. 479/g K. 25/L K. 1300/yard

K. 40/g K. 15/ml K. 40/g 43,110,000 900,000 19,500,000

1,800,000 900,000 1,440,000 3

4

Labour Cost Supervisor Unskilled worker Utilities Cost Electricity Water 1 No. 2 No.

20unit/day 100L/day K. 5000/ day K. 4000/ day

K. 75/ unit K. 5/ L 1,500,000 2,400,000

450,000 75,000 5 Packaging and labelling 50package/day K.100/ package

150,000

Total Cost 72,225,000

K. 29,000 Manufacturing Cost = Direct Production Cost + Fixed Charges = K. 72225000 + K. 29000 = K. 72,254,000 Manufacturing Cost/ package = 1500 72254000 = K. 48169.3/ package
 Manufacturing Cost/ yard = K. 4816.9/ yard Only raw materials, labour, utilities and packing costs were taken into consideration for direct production costs. Only depreciation on equipment was taken into consideration in fixed charges.

84 APPENDIX B 1. Preparation of Dragendorff's Reagent Solution
 A: A 1.7 g bismuth nitrate in 100 ml mixture of water – acetic acid, H₂O – HOAc (80:20). Solution B: A 40 g of potassium iodide in 100 ml distilled water. The reagent was prepared by mixing 5 ml solution A with 5 ml solution B together with 20 ml of acetic acid and 70 ml of distilled water into reagent bottle. 2.
 Calculation of Concentration of Dye Solution According to Beer-lambert law, $A = \epsilon l c$ Where, A= Absorbance of the solution ϵ = Molar absorptivity (L/ mol cm) l = Cell path length (cm) c = Concentration of absorbing species (mol/L) For example: A = 0.795 ϵ = 30900 L/mol cm (Pratap Reddy, 2005) l = 1cm c =? c = = $30900 \times 0.795 \times 10^{-5} = 2.57 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol/L}$

85

K. 29,000 Manufacturing Cost = Direct Production Cost + Fixed Charges = K. 72225000 + K. 29000 = K. 72,254,000 Manufacturing Cost/ package = = K. 48169.3/ package Manufacturing Cost/ yard = K. 4816.9/ yard Only raw materials, labour, utilities and packing costs were taken into consideration for direct production costs. Only depreciation on equipment was taken into consideration in fixed charges.

APPENDIX B 1. Preparation of Dragendorff's Reagent

Solution A: A 1.7 g bismuth nitrate in 100 ml mixture of water – acetic acid, H₂O – HOAc (80:20). Solution B: A 40 g of potassium iodide in 100 ml distilled water. The reagent was prepared by mixing 5 ml solution A with 5 ml solution B together with 20 ml of acetic acid and 70 ml of distilled water into reagent bottle.

2. Calculation of Concentration of Dye Solution According to Beer- lambert law, $A = \epsilon l c$ Where, A= Absorbance of the solution ϵ = Molar absorptivity (L/ mol cm) l = Cell path length (cm) c = Concentration of absorbing species (mol/L) For example: A = 0.795 ϵ = 30900 L/mol cm (Pratap Reddy, 2005) l = 1cm c =? c = = $30900 \times 0.795 \times 10^{-5} = 2.57 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol/L}$

82

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